

SymExA: An Extension of the Symbolic Model for Authentication

A formal specification

Gijs Vanspauwen Bart Jacobs

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1 Strings, lists, partial functions and auxiliary definitions

1.1 Strings and lists

The notion of finite strings over some alphabet and the notion of lists of elements from a specific set are used interchangeably throughout this document. The functions shown below deal with strings and lists, and they have a straightforward meaning. Their exact definitions are left implicit, but some properties are stated below.

Definition 1.1.A. Lists of elements from the set Σ : $\bar{\sigma} = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n]$, $\bar{\sigma} \in \Sigma^*$ and the empty list $[]$

Definition 1.1.B. Finite strings over some alphabet Σ : $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_1\sigma_2\dots\sigma_n$, $\bar{\sigma} \in \Sigma^*$ and the empty string ε

Definition 1.1.C. Binary strings: $s \in S$ and $S \equiv \{0, 1\}^*$

Definition 1.1.D. List/string operations:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 | _ | : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} & \text{(the length of a list/string)} \\
 _ :: _ : \Sigma \times \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^* & \text{(the cons/prepend operator for lists/strings)} \\
 _[-] : \Sigma^* \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \Sigma \cup \perp & \text{(0-based selection of elements from a list/string)} \\
 _ ++ _ : \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^* & \text{(append/concatenate two lists/strings)} \\
 _[: _] : \Sigma^* \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \Sigma^* & \text{(take a prefix of a list/string)} \\
 _[- : _] : \Sigma^* \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \Sigma^* & \text{(take a suffix of a list/string)} \\
 \{\{ _ \} \} : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \mathbf{2}^\Sigma & \text{(transform a list/string to a set)}
 \end{array}$$

Axiom 1.1.A. Some properties of list/string operations:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \forall n. \varepsilon[n] = [][n] = \perp & \forall \sigma, \bar{\sigma}. (\sigma :: \bar{\sigma})[0] = \sigma \\
 \forall \bar{\sigma}. \bar{\sigma} ++ \varepsilon = \bar{\sigma} & \forall \sigma, \bar{\sigma}, n. (\sigma :: \bar{\sigma})[n+1] = \bar{\sigma}[n] \\
 \forall \bar{\sigma}. \varepsilon ++ \bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma} & \forall n, \bar{\sigma}. n \geq |\bar{\sigma}| \Rightarrow \bar{\sigma}[: n] = \bar{\sigma} \\
 \forall \bar{\sigma}. \bar{\sigma}[: 0] = \varepsilon & \forall n, \bar{\sigma}. n \geq |\bar{\sigma}| \Rightarrow \bar{\sigma}[n :] = \varepsilon \\
 \forall \bar{\sigma}. \bar{\sigma}[0 :] = \bar{\sigma} & \forall n, \bar{\sigma}. \bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}[: n] ++ \bar{\sigma}[n :]
 \end{array}$$

1.2 Partial functions

Definition 1.2.A. Partial functions: $\vec{f} \in \vec{Y}^X$ and $\vec{Y}^X \equiv \{Y \cup \perp\}^X$

Definition 1.2.B. Empty partial function: $\vec{\emptyset} \in \vec{Y}^X$ and $\forall x. \vec{\emptyset}(x) = \perp$

Definition 1.2.C. Domain of a partial function $\vec{f} \in \vec{Y}^X$:

$$\text{dom}(\vec{f}) \equiv \left\{ x \mid x \in X \wedge \vec{f}(x) \neq \perp \right\}$$

1.3 Function update

Definition 1.3.A. Function update of $\vec{f} \in \vec{Y}^X$ with $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$: $\vec{f}[x := y]$

$$\vec{f}[x := y] \equiv \lambda x'. \begin{cases} y & (\text{if } x = x') \\ \vec{f}(x') & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

Definition 1.3.B. *Multiple update defined as general as possible for reusability:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x. x[\varepsilon := \varepsilon] &\equiv x \\ \forall x, y, \bar{y}, z, \bar{z}. x[y :: \bar{y} := z :: \bar{z}] &\equiv (x[y := z])[\bar{y} := \bar{z}] \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1.3.C. *Updating a list defined as general as possible for reusability:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall y, z. \varepsilon[y := z] &\equiv \varepsilon \\ \forall x, \bar{x}, y, z. (x :: \bar{x})[y := z] &\equiv x[y := z] :: \bar{x}[y := z] \end{aligned}$$

1.4 Auxiliary definitions

Definition 1.4.A. *The security parameter: $N_s \in \mathbb{N}$*

Definition 1.4.B. *Subtraction of natural numbers as a total function:*

$$\forall n_1, n_2. n_1 - n_2 = \begin{cases} n & (\text{if } n_2 + n = n_1 \text{ for some } n) \\ \mathbf{0} & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 1.4.A. *Subtraction of natural numbers has the following property:*

$$\forall n_1, n_2. n_1 + (n_2 - n_1) = \max(n_1, n_2)$$

Proof. For some n_1 and n_2 we perform a case analysis:

- $n_1 \leq n_2$ Now $\max(n_1, n_2) = n_2$ and $n_1 + (n_2 - n_1) = n_2$.
- $n_1 > n_2$ Now $\max(n_1, n_2) = n_1$ and $n_1 + (n_2 - n_1) = n_1 + \mathbf{0} = n_1$.

□

Definition 1.4.C. *Notation for boolean values $b \in \mathbb{B}$ and $\mathbb{B} = \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$*

Definition 1.4.D. *Notation for sets of elements of some other set X : $\dot{x} \in 2^X$ and thus $\dot{x} \subseteq X$*

Definition 1.4.E. *The first element of a pair for some sets X and Y is given by the function $f: X \times Y \rightarrow X$*

$$\forall x, y. f((x, y)) \equiv x$$

Definition 1.4.F. *The second element of a pair for some sets X and Y is given by the function $s: X \times Y \rightarrow Y$*

$$\forall x, y. s((x, y)) \equiv y$$

2 Syntax and semantics of SymExA's language

2.1 Expressions and evaluation

2.1.1 Syntax of expressions

Definition 2.1.A. *Program variables:* $v \in \mathbf{V}$

Definition 2.1.B. *Program expressions:* $e \in \mathbf{E}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 e ::= \\
 | \quad s \qquad \qquad \qquad (s \in \mathbf{S}) \\
 | \quad v \qquad \qquad \qquad (v \in \mathbf{V}) \\
 | \quad e[:n] \qquad \qquad \qquad (n \in \mathbf{N}) \\
 | \quad e[n:] \qquad \qquad \qquad (n \in \mathbf{N}) \\
 | \quad e ++ e
 \end{array}$$

Definition 2.1.C. *Retrieve the set of variables that occur in an expression:* $\text{VARS}(-) : \mathbf{E} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbf{V}}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \forall s. \quad \text{VARS}(s) \qquad \equiv \quad \emptyset \\
 \forall v. \quad \text{VARS}(v) \qquad \equiv \quad \{v\} \\
 \forall e, n. \quad \text{VARS}(e[:n]) \qquad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(e) \\
 \forall e, n. \quad \text{VARS}(e[n:]) \qquad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(e) \\
 \forall e_1, e_2. \quad \text{VARS}(e_1 ++ e_2) \qquad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(e_1) \cup \text{VARS}(e_2)
 \end{array}$$

Definition 2.1.D. *Boolean conditions:* $q \in \mathbf{Q}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 q ::= \\
 | \quad e_1 = e_2 \qquad \qquad \qquad (e_1, e_2 \in \mathbf{E}) \\
 | \quad |e| = n \qquad \qquad \qquad (e \in \mathbf{E}, n \in \mathbf{N})
 \end{array}$$

2.1.2 Evaluation of expressions

Definition 2.1.E. *Stores:* $st \in \mathbf{ST}$ and $\mathbf{ST} \equiv \mathbf{S}^{\mathbf{V}}$

Definition 2.1.F. *The empty store:* $st_\varepsilon \in \mathbf{ST}$ and $\forall v. st_\varepsilon(v) = \varepsilon$

Definition 2.1.G. *The evaluation for expressions and boolean conditions:* $\text{EVAL}(st, e)$

$$\forall st, e. \text{EVAL}(st, e) \equiv \begin{cases} s & (\text{if } e = s) \\
 st(v) & (\text{if } e = v) \\
 \text{EVAL}(st, e')[n] & (\text{if } e = e'[:n]) \\
 \text{EVAL}(st, e')[n:] & (\text{if } e = e'[n:]) \\
 \text{EVAL}(st, e_1) ++ \text{EVAL}(st, e_2) & (\text{if } e = e_1 ++ e_2) \end{cases}$$

$$\forall \text{st}, q. \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) \equiv \begin{cases} \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, e_1) = \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, e_2) & (\text{if } q = (e_1 = e_2)) \\ |\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, e)| = n & (\text{if } q = (|e| = n)) \end{cases}$$

2.2 Commands and properties

Definition 2.2.A. *Actions:* $\alpha \in \mathbf{A}$

$$\alpha ::= \text{rotate} \mid \text{step}$$

Definition 2.2.B. *Commands:* $c \in \mathbf{C}$

$$c ::= \begin{array}{l} | \text{skip} \\ | \text{stuck} \\ | \text{fail} \\ \\ | \text{snd}(e) \quad (e \in \mathbf{E}) \\ | \text{rcv}(v) \quad (v \in \mathbf{V}) \\ \\ | v := e \quad (v \in \mathbf{V}, e \in \mathbf{E}) \\ | v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s \quad (v \in \mathbf{V}) \\ | v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \quad (v, v_k, v_p \in \mathbf{V}) \\ \\ | q ? c : c \quad (q \in \mathbf{Q}) \\ | \text{fork}(c) \\ | c ; c \\ \\ | \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}) \quad (\bar{\alpha} \in \mathbf{A}^* \wedge \bar{\alpha} \neq \varepsilon) \end{array}$$

Definition 2.2.C. *Retrieve the set of variables assigned by a command:* $\text{VARS}_{:=}(-) : \mathbf{C} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbf{V}}$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{skip}) & \equiv & \emptyset \\ \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{stuck}) & \equiv & \emptyset \\ \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{fail}) & \equiv & \emptyset \\ \forall e. \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{snd}(e)) & \equiv & \emptyset \\ \forall v. \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{rcv}(v)) & \equiv & \{v\} \\ \forall v. \text{VARS}_{:=}(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s) & \equiv & \{v\} \\ \forall v, e. \text{VARS}_{:=}(v := e) & \equiv & \{v\} \\ \forall v, v_k, v_p. \text{VARS}_{:=}(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)) & \equiv & \{v\} \\ \forall q, c_1, c_2. \text{VARS}_{:=}(q ? c_1 : c_2) & \equiv & \text{VARS}_{:=}(c_1) \cup \text{VARS}_{:=}(c_2) \\ \forall c. \text{VARS}_{:=}(\text{fork}(c)) & \equiv & \text{VARS}_{:=}(c) \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall c_1, c_2. \quad \text{VARS} := (c_1 ; c_2) &\equiv \text{VARS} := (c_1) \cup \text{VARS} := (c_2) \\
\forall \bar{\alpha}. \quad \text{VARS} := (\text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})) &\equiv \emptyset
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.2.D. Check if a given command contains a non-composite command with some specific property:

$$\text{CONTAINS}(-, -) : \mathbb{C} \times (\mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$$

$$\forall c, f. \quad \text{CONTAINS}(c, f) \equiv \begin{cases} \text{CONTAINS}(c_1, f) \vee \text{CONTAINS}(c_2, f) & (\text{if } c = q ? c_1 : c_2) \\ \text{CONTAINS}(c', f) & (\text{if } c = \text{fork}(c')) \\ \text{CONTAINS}(c_1, f) \vee \text{CONTAINS}(c_2, f) & (\text{if } c = c_1 ; c_2) \\ f(c) & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.2.E. An attacker command is any command that does not fork or fail: $\text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(-) : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$

$$\forall c_{\text{attacker}}. \quad \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \equiv \begin{cases} \neg \text{CONTAINS}(c_{\text{attacker}}, \lambda c. c = \text{fail}) \wedge \\ \neg \text{CONTAINS}(c_{\text{attacker}}, \lambda c. \exists c'. c = \text{fork}(c')) \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.2.F. Transform a list of commands into a single command: $\overline{\text{CMD}}(-) : \mathbb{C}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\overline{\text{CMD}}([\]) &\equiv \text{skip} \\
\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}) &\equiv c ; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})
\end{aligned}$$

2.3 World configurations and execution

2.3.1 Syntax for threads and world configurations

Definition 2.3.A. Syntax for threads: $t \in \mathbb{T}$

$$\begin{aligned}
t &::= (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) && (\text{st} \in \text{ST}, c \in \mathbb{C}, \bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}^*) \\
\forall c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \quad t_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c) &\equiv (\text{st}_\varepsilon \triangleright \text{fork}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \circ [c])
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.3.B. Network: $\beta \in \mathbb{B}$ and $\mathbb{B} \equiv \mathbb{S}^*$

Definition 2.3.C. Keep track of generated HMAC values: $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \equiv \overline{\mathbb{S}}^{\mathbb{S} \times \mathbb{S}}$

$$\forall \gamma. \quad \text{keys}(\gamma) \equiv \left\{ s_k \mid \exists s_p. (s_k, s_p) \in \text{dom}(\gamma) \right\}$$

Definition 2.3.D. Syntax for a world configuration: $w \in \mathbb{W}$

$$\begin{aligned}
w &::= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \triangleright \bar{t} \rangle && (\bar{\alpha} \in \mathbb{A}^*, \beta \in \mathbb{B}, \gamma \in \Gamma, \bar{t} \in \mathbb{T}^*) \\
\forall c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \quad w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c) &\equiv \langle [\text{step}, \text{step}] \cdot [\] \cdot \vec{\emptyset} \triangleright [t_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)] \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

2.3.2 Execution relation for worlds

Definition 2.3.E. Probabilities: $\pi \in \Pi$ and $\Pi \equiv \{\pi \in \mathbb{Q} \mid 0 \leq \pi \leq 1\}$.

Definition 2.3.F. *The probabilistic small-step execution relation for world configurations: $w_1 \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w_2$*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{snd}(e) \circ \bar{c}) \quad \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, e) = s \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot s :: \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XSEND} \\
\\
\frac{(\beta_1 = s :: \beta_2) \vee (\beta_1 = [] \wedge \beta_2 = [] \wedge s = \varepsilon) \quad t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{rcv}(v) \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} [v := s] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta_1 \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta_2 \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XRECEIVE} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright v := e \circ \bar{c}) \quad \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, e) = s \quad t_2 = (\text{st} [v := s] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XASSIGN} \\
\\
\frac{|s| = N_s \quad \pi = 2^{-N_s} \quad t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright v \overset{s}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} [v := s] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XSAMPLE} \\
\\
\frac{\gamma_1(\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) = \perp \quad \gamma_2 = \gamma_1[(\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) := s] \quad |s| = N_s \quad \pi = 2^{-N_s} \quad t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright v \overset{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} [v := s] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma_1 \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma_2 \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XHMACNEW} \\
\\
\frac{\gamma(\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) = s \quad t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright v \overset{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} [v := s] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XHMACOLD} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright q ? c_{\text{true}} : c_{\text{false}} \circ \bar{c}) \quad \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright c_{\text{true}} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XIFTRUE} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright q ? c_{\text{true}} : c_{\text{false}} \circ \bar{c}) \quad \neg \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright c_{\text{false}} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XIFFALSE} \\
\\
\frac{}{\langle \text{rotate} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} ++ [t] \rangle} \text{XROTATE} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{sched}(\bar{\alpha}') \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} ++ \bar{\alpha}' \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XSCHEDULE} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ c :: \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XSKIP} \\
\\
\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright c_1 ; c_2 \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ c_2 :: \bar{c})}{\langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XSEQ}
\end{array}$$

$$\frac{t_1 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{fork}(c) \circ \bar{c}) \quad t_2 = (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})}{\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t_1 :: \bar{t} \rangle \xrightarrow{\perp} \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ []) :: t_2 :: \bar{t} \rangle} \text{XFORK}$$

Definition 2.3.G. Values for \rightsquigarrow :

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \text{st}, c, \bar{c}. \quad \mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) &\equiv c = \mathbf{stuck} \vee c = \mathbf{fail} \vee (c = \mathbf{skip} \wedge \bar{c} = []) \\ \forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, \bar{t}. \quad \mathbf{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) &\equiv \begin{cases} \mathbf{VALUE}(t) & (\text{if } \bar{t} = t :: \bar{t}' \wedge \bar{\alpha} = \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha}') \\ \mathbf{false} & (\text{if } \bar{t} = t :: \bar{t}' \wedge \bar{\alpha} = \mathbf{rotate} :: \bar{\alpha}') \\ \mathbf{true} & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3.A. Thread values for \rightsquigarrow cannot take a step:

$$\forall t. \mathbf{VALUE}(t) \Leftrightarrow (\forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, \bar{t}. \neg \exists \pi, w'. \langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t :: \bar{t} \rangle \xrightarrow{\pi} w')$$

Proof. Using Definition 2.3.A we know for some t that there must exist some st , c and \bar{c} such that $t = (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})$. The proof continues by a case analysis of c :

- $c = \mathbf{skip}$ Here we perform a case analysis of \bar{c} :
 - $\bar{c} = []$
In this case $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ [])) = \mathbf{true}$, but that is fine since there is no execution step possible starting from $\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ []) :: \bar{t} \rangle$ for all $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$ and \bar{t} .
 - $\bar{c} = c' :: \bar{c}'$
In this case $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ c' :: \bar{c}')) = \mathbf{false}$ and that is fine since there is also a XSKIP step possible starting from $\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (\text{st} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ c' :: \bar{c}') :: \bar{t} \rangle$ for all $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$ and \bar{t} .
- $c = \mathbf{stuck}$ $c = \mathbf{fail}$
In these cases $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) = \mathbf{true}$, but that is fine since there is no execution step possible for all $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$ and \bar{t} starting from $\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$.
- $c = \mathbf{snd}(e)$ $c = \mathbf{rcv}(v)$ $c = v ::= e$ $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$ $c = \mathbf{fork}(c)$ $c = \mathbf{sched}(\bar{\alpha})$ $c = c_1 ; c_2$
In these cases $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) = \mathbf{false}$ and there is also an execution step possible for all $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$ and \bar{t} starting from $\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$ (using the rules XSEND, XRECEIVE, XASSIGN, XSAMPLE, XFORK, XSCHEDULE and XSEQ respectively).
- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p)$
In this case $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) = \mathbf{false}$ and there is also an execution step possible. For some γ this possible step is XHMACNEW if $\gamma(\mathbf{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \mathbf{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) = \perp$ and otherwise it is XHMACOLD.
- $c = q ? c_{\text{true}} : c_{\text{false}}$
In this case $\mathbf{VALUE}((\text{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) = \mathbf{false}$ and there is also an execution step possible. If $\mathbf{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) = \mathbf{true}$ this possible step is XIFTRUE and if $\mathbf{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) = \mathbf{false}$ it is XIFFALSE.

□

Theorem 2.3.B. *World configuration values for \rightsquigarrow cannot perform an execution step:*

$$\forall w. \text{VALUE}(w) \Leftrightarrow \neg(\exists \pi, w'. w \xrightarrow{\pi} w')$$

Proof. Using definition Definition 2.3.D, we have to prove for some $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$, and \bar{t} that:

$$\text{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) \Leftrightarrow \neg(\exists \pi, w'. \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle \xrightarrow{\pi} w')$$

We now proceed by case analysis of \bar{t} :

- $\bar{t} = \varepsilon$

There is no rule for \rightsquigarrow in Definition 2.3.F to perform an execution step in this case, but this is no problem since now we also have $\text{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) = \mathbf{true}$.

- $\bar{t} = t :: \bar{t}'$

We continue in this case with a case analysis of $\bar{\alpha}$:

- $\bar{\alpha} = \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha}'$

Applying Theorem 2.3.A finishes the proof.

- $\bar{\alpha} = \mathbf{rotate} :: \bar{\alpha}'$

Now $\text{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) = \mathbf{false}$ and the rule XROTATE provides us with a possible execution step.

- $\bar{\alpha} = \varepsilon$

Now $\text{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) = \mathbf{true}$ and obviously no execution step is possible.

□

Theorem 2.3.C. *Starting from a thread that is not a value for \rightsquigarrow , the probabilities of all possible execution steps starting from a world configuration with that thread sum up to $\mathbf{1}$:*

$$\forall t. \neg \text{VALUE}(t) \Rightarrow \forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, \bar{t}. \sum_{\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright t :: \bar{t} \rangle \xrightarrow{\pi} w'} (\pi) = \mathbf{1}$$

Proof. For some t , and using Definition 2.3.A thus for some st, c and \bar{c} such that $t = (st \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})$, we assume $\neg \text{VALUE}((st \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}))$ and must prove for some $\bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma$, and \bar{t} :

$$\sum_{\langle \mathbf{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright (st \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle \xrightarrow{\pi} w'} (\pi) = \mathbf{1}$$

The proof proceeds with a case analysis of c :

- $c = \mathbf{skip}$

Here we perform a case analysis of \bar{c} :

- $\bar{c} = []$

This cases are impossible as we have $\neg \text{VALUE}((st \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}))$.

- $\bar{c} = c' :: \bar{c}'$

Now we know only the rule XSKIP is applicable and the associated probability is $\mathbf{1}$ so we are done.

- $c = \mathbf{stuck}$

- $c = \mathbf{fail}$

These cases are impossible as we have $\neg \text{VALUE}((st \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}))$.

- $c = \text{snd}(e)$ $c = \text{rcv}(v)$ $c = v := e$ $c = \text{fork}(c)$ $c = \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})$ $c = c_1 ; c_2$

Now, respectively, only the rule XSEND, XRECEIVE, XASSIGN, XFORK, XSCHEDULE or XSEQ is applicable and the associated probability is $\mathbf{1}$ so we are done.

- $c = q ? c_{\text{true}} : c_{\text{false}}$

If $\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) = \mathbf{true}$ the only possible rule to perform an execution step is XIFTRUE and if $\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, q) = \mathbf{false}$ the only possible rule is XIFFALSE. Both rules have as associated probability $\mathbf{1}$, so we are done.

- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$

The only applicable rule to perform an execution step now is XSAMPLE. Note that there are 2^{N_s} different strings of size N_s that each give rise to a different transition. Each of these transitions occurs with a probability of 2^{-N_s} and so we need to prove that $2^{N_s} \times 2^{-N_s} = \mathbf{1}$ which is obvious.

- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)$ We can distinguish two cases here:

- $\gamma(\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) = \perp$

Similar reasoning as in the case that c is a sampling command finishes the proof here.

- $\gamma(\text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_k), \text{EVAL}(\text{st}, v_p)) \neq \perp$

Now only XHMACOLD is applicable and the associated probability is $\mathbf{1}$ so we are done. □

Theorem 2.3.D. *Starting from a world configuration that is not a value for \rightsquigarrow , the probabilities of all possible execution steps starting in that configuration sum up to $\mathbf{1}$:*

$$\forall w. \neg \text{VALUE}(w) \Rightarrow \sum_{w \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi) = \mathbf{1}$$

Proof. Using Definition 2.3.D we have to prove for some $\bar{\alpha}$, β , γ , and \bar{t} such that $\neg \text{VALUE}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle)$, it is true that:

$$\sum_{\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi) = \mathbf{1}$$

Using Definition 2.3.G we can conclude that $\bar{\alpha}$ must be equal to $\alpha' :: \bar{\alpha}'$ for some α' and $\bar{\alpha}'$, and that \bar{t} must be equal to $t' :: \bar{t}'$ for some t' and \bar{t}' . We now proceed by case analysis of α' :

- $\alpha' = \text{rotate}$

Now only the rule XROTATE is applicable and the associated probability is $\mathbf{1}$ so we are done.

- $\alpha' = \text{step}$

Applying Theorem 2.3.C finishes the proof. □

2.4 The probability of failure

Definition 2.4.A. *A failed thread or world configuration:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall t \quad \text{FAILED}(t) &\equiv \exists st, \bar{c}. t = (st \triangleright \text{fail} \circ \bar{c}) \\
\forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, \bar{t} \quad \text{FAILED}((\bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \triangleright \bar{t})) &\equiv \exists t. t \in \bar{t} \wedge \text{FAILED}(t)
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.4.B. Compute the probability of failure within some specific number of steps starting from a specific world configuration: $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) : \mathbb{N} \times \mathbf{W} \rightarrow \Pi$

$$\forall \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}. \quad \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) \equiv \begin{cases} \mathbf{1} & \text{(if } \text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w})\text{)} \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{(if } \neg \text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w}) \wedge \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{0}\text{)} \\ \sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n} - \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{w}')) & \text{(otherwise)} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2.4.A. The computed probability of failure is indeed a probability:

$$\forall \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}. \quad \mathbf{0} \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) \leq \mathbf{1}$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on \mathbf{n} for some \mathbf{w} . If $\text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w})$ or $\neg \text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w}) \wedge \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{0}$, the stated theorem trivially holds. So now we can assume $\neg \text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w})$ and $\mathbf{n} = 1 + \mathbf{n}'$ for some \mathbf{n}' and we know that the value of $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w})$ is determined by a weighted average over all possible \rightsquigarrow transitions:

$$\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) = \sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}', \mathbf{w}'))$$

We now separately prove $\mathbf{0} \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w})$ and $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) \leq \mathbf{1}$:

$\mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{0}$	(By Theorem 2.3.D)	$\sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi) = \mathbf{1}$
$\mathbf{0} \leq \sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \mathbf{0})$	(By rewriting)	$\sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \mathbf{1}) \leq \mathbf{1}$
$\mathbf{0} \leq \sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}', \mathbf{w}'))$	(By the induction hypothesis)	$\sum_{\mathbf{w} \xrightarrow{\pi} \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}', \mathbf{w}')) \leq \mathbf{1}$
$\mathbf{0} \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w})$	(By rewriting)	$\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{w}) \leq \mathbf{1}$

□

Theorem 2.4.B. The probability of failure decreases with fewer steps:

$$\forall \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2. \quad \mathbf{n}_1 \leq \mathbf{n}_2 \Rightarrow \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{w}) \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_2, \mathbf{w})$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on \mathbf{n}_2 for some \mathbf{w} and \mathbf{n}_1 such that $\mathbf{n}_1 \leq \mathbf{n}_2$. In the case that $\mathbf{n}_2 = \mathbf{0}$ it must be that also $\mathbf{n}_1 = \mathbf{0}$ and so we trivially have $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{w}) = \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_2, \mathbf{w})$. In the case that $\mathbf{n}_2 = \mathbf{n}'_2 + 1$ for some \mathbf{n}'_2 , we can distinguish two cases:

- FAILED(\mathbf{w})

In this case $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_2, \mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{1}$ and the proof is finished by using Theorem 2.4.A.

- $\neg \text{FAILED}(\mathbf{w})$

If now $\mathbf{n}_1 = \mathbf{0}$ then $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{0}$ and by using Theorem 2.4.A we can finish the proof. So we can now assume that $\mathbf{n}_1 > \mathbf{0}$ and starting from the induction hypothesis we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall w', n'_1. (n'_1 \leq n'_2 \Rightarrow \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n'_1, w') \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n'_2, w')) \Rightarrow \\
& \forall w'. (n_1 - 1 \leq n'_2 \Rightarrow \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_1 - 1, w') \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n'_2, w')) \Rightarrow \\
& \quad \forall w'. \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_1 - 1, w') \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n'_2, w') \Rightarrow \\
& \sum_{w \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_1 - 1, w')) \leq \sum_{w \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n'_2, w')) \Rightarrow \\
& \quad \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_1, w) \leq \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_2, w)
\end{aligned}$$

□

2.5 The example protocol: A single-message authentication protocol

2.5.1 Protocol transcript

Message 1 $A \Rightarrow B$: $m, \text{HMAC}(k, m)$

2.5.2 Implementation

Definition 2.5.A. *Implementation of role A:*

$$\begin{aligned}
c_A(s_m) \equiv & \quad v_m := s_m ; \\
& \quad v_h \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_m) ; \\
& \quad v_{\text{msg}} := s_m ++ v_h ; \\
& \quad \text{snd}(v_{\text{msg}})
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.5.B. *Implementation of role B:*

$$\begin{aligned}
c_B(s_m) \equiv & \quad \text{rcv}(v_{\text{msg}}) ; \\
& \quad v_m := v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] ; v_h := v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|:] ; \\
& \quad v_{h'} \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_m) ; \\
& \quad v_h = v_{h'} ? \text{skip} : \text{stuck} ; \\
& \quad v_m = s_m ? \text{skip} : \text{fail}
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.5.C. *Implementation of a single protocol session:*

$$c_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \equiv v_k \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s ; \text{fork}(c_A(s_m)) ; c_B(s_m)$$

2.5.3 Security goal

Definition 2.5.D. *We want to show that executing any attacker command in parallel with the protocol implementation fails with a probability that decreases exponential in the security parameter and only grows polynomially in the number of execution steps:*

$$\forall c_{\text{attacker}}, n, s_m. \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \Rightarrow \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n, w_{\varepsilon}(c_{\text{attacker}}, c_{\text{auth}}(s_m))) \leq \frac{n^2}{2^{N_s}}$$

3 A proof system for SymExA

3.1 Assertions and invariants

3.1.1 String and cryptogram expressions

Definition 3.1.A. String expressions $\hat{e} \in \widehat{\mathbf{E}}$ and cryptogram expressions $\hat{c}g \in \widehat{\mathbf{CG}}$:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \hat{e} ::= \\
 | \quad \mathbf{e} \qquad \qquad \qquad (\mathbf{e} \in \mathbf{E}) \\
 | \quad \widehat{\mathbf{cg2s}}(\hat{c}g) \qquad \qquad (\hat{c}g \in \widehat{\mathbf{CG}}) \\
 | \quad \hat{e}[: \mathbf{n}] \qquad \qquad \qquad (\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{N}) \\
 | \quad \hat{e}[\mathbf{n} :] \qquad \qquad \qquad (\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{N}) \\
 | \quad \hat{e} ++ \hat{e} \\
 \\
 \hat{c}g ::= \\
 | \quad \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}) \qquad \qquad (\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} \in \mathbb{N}) \\
 | \quad \widehat{\mathbf{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \hat{e}_p) \qquad (\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} \in \mathbb{N}, \hat{e}_p \in \widehat{\mathbf{E}})
 \end{array}$$

Definition 3.1.B. Retrieve the set of variables that occur in a string or cryptogram expression:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \forall \hat{c}g. \quad \text{VARS}(\widehat{\mathbf{cg2s}}(\hat{c}g)) \quad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{c}g) \\
 \forall \hat{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}[: \mathbf{n}]) \quad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}) \\
 \forall \hat{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}[\mathbf{n} :]) \quad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}) \\
 \forall \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_1 ++ \hat{e}_2) \quad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_1) \cup \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_2) \\
 \\
 \forall \mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}. \quad \text{VARS}(\widehat{\mathbf{key}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#})) \quad \equiv \quad \emptyset \\
 \forall \mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \hat{e}_p. \quad \text{VARS}(\widehat{\mathbf{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \hat{e}_p)) \quad \equiv \quad \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_p)
 \end{array}$$

Definition 3.1.C. Substitute a variable v' in a program expression with the string expression \hat{e}' :

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \mathbf{s}. \quad (\mathbf{s})[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad \mathbf{s} \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \mathbf{v}. \quad (\mathbf{v})[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad \begin{cases} \hat{e}' & (\text{if } \mathbf{v} = v') \\ \mathbf{v} & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases} \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad (\mathbf{e}[: \mathbf{n}])[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad ((\mathbf{e})[\hat{e}'/v'][: \mathbf{n}]) \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad (\mathbf{e}[\mathbf{n} :])[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad ((\mathbf{e})[\hat{e}'/v'][\mathbf{n} :]) \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2. \quad (\mathbf{e}_1 ++ \mathbf{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad ((\mathbf{e}_1)[\hat{e}'/v'] ++ (\mathbf{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'])
 \end{array}$$

Definition 3.1.D. Substitute a variable v' in a string or cryptogram expression with the string expression \hat{e}' :

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{c}g. \quad (\widehat{\mathbf{cg2s}}(\hat{c}g))[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad \widehat{\mathbf{cg2s}}((\hat{c}g)[\hat{e}'/v']) \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad (\hat{e}[: \mathbf{n}])[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad (\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v'][: \mathbf{n}] \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}, \mathbf{n}. \quad (\hat{e}[\mathbf{n} :])[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad (\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v'][\mathbf{n} :] \\
 \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. \quad (\hat{e}_1 ++ \hat{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] \quad \equiv \quad (\hat{e}_1)[\hat{e}'/v'] ++ (\hat{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v']
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall v', \hat{e}', n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \quad & \widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})[\hat{e}'/v'] \equiv \widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \\
\forall v', \hat{e}', n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \hat{e}_p. \quad & \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \hat{e}_p)[\hat{e}'/v'] \equiv \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, (\hat{e}_p)[\hat{e}'/v'])
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.1.E. *The depth of a string or cryptogram expression:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall e. \quad & \|e\| \equiv \mathbf{0} \\
\forall \hat{c}\hat{g}. \quad & \|\widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\hat{c}\hat{g})\| \equiv \mathbf{1} + \|\hat{c}\hat{g}\| \\
\forall \hat{e}, n. \quad & \|\hat{e}[n]\| \equiv \mathbf{1} + \|\hat{e}\| \\
\forall \hat{e}, n. \quad & \|\hat{e}[n :]\| \equiv \mathbf{1} + \|\hat{e}\| \\
\forall \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. \quad & \|\hat{e}_1 ++ \hat{e}_2\| \equiv \mathbf{1} + \max(\|\hat{e}_1\|, \|\hat{e}_2\|) \\
\\
\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \quad & \|\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})\| \equiv \mathbf{0} \\
\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \quad & \|\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \hat{e}_p)\| \equiv \mathbf{1} + \|\hat{e}_p\|
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.1.F. *Cryptogram patterns: $\tilde{c}\tilde{g} \in \widetilde{\text{CG}}$ and $\tilde{c}\tilde{g} \equiv \left\{ \tilde{c}\tilde{g} \in \widetilde{\text{CG}} \mid \text{PAT}(\tilde{c}\tilde{g}) \right\}$ where*

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \quad & \text{PAT}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})) \equiv \mathbf{true} \\
\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \hat{e}_p. \quad & \text{PAT}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \hat{e}_p)) \equiv \hat{e}_p \in V
\end{aligned}$$

3.1.2 Boolean expressions

Definition 3.1.G. *Boolean expressions $\hat{b} \in \hat{\mathbf{B}}$:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{b} ::= & \\
& | \mathbf{true} \\
& | \mathbf{false} \\
& | \neg(\hat{b}) \\
& | \hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2 \\
& | \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \quad (\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2 \in \hat{\mathbf{E}}) \\
& | |\hat{c}| = n \quad (\hat{c} \in \hat{\mathbf{E}}, n \in \mathbb{N}) \\
& | \mathbf{pub}(\hat{e}) \quad (\hat{e} \in \hat{\mathbf{E}})
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.1.H. *Retrieve the set of variables that occur in a boolean expression:*

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{VARS}(\mathbf{true}) \equiv \emptyset \\
& \text{VARS}(\mathbf{false}) \equiv \emptyset \\
\forall \hat{b}. \quad & \text{VARS}(\neg(\hat{b})) \equiv \text{VARS}(\hat{b}) \\
\forall \hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2. \quad & \text{VARS}(\hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2) \equiv \text{VARS}(\hat{b}_1) \cup \text{VARS}(\hat{b}_2) \\
\forall \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. \quad & \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2) \equiv \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_1) \cup \text{VARS}(\hat{e}_2) \\
\forall \hat{e}, n. \quad & \text{VARS}(|\hat{c}| = n) \equiv \text{VARS}(\hat{c})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\forall \hat{e}. \quad \text{VARS}(\text{pub}(\hat{e})) \equiv \text{VARS}(\hat{e})$$

Definition 3.1.I. Substitute a variable v' in a boolean expression with the expression \hat{e}' :

$$\begin{aligned} \forall v', \hat{e}' & \quad (\text{true})[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & \text{true} \\ \forall v', \hat{e}' & \quad (\text{false})[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & \text{false} \\ \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{b}. & \quad (\neg(\hat{b}))[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & \neg((\hat{b})[\hat{e}'/v']) \\ \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2. & \quad (\hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & (\hat{b}_1)[\hat{e}'/v'] \wedge (\hat{b}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] \\ \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. & \quad (\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & (\hat{e}_1)[\hat{e}'/v'] = (\hat{e}_2)[\hat{e}'/v'] \\ \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}, n. & \quad (|\hat{e}| = n)[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & |(\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v']| = n \\ \forall v', \hat{e}', \hat{e}. & \quad (\text{pub}(\hat{e}))[\hat{e}'/v'] & \equiv & \text{pub}((\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v']) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.1.J. Boolean patterns: $\tilde{b} \in \tilde{\mathbb{B}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbb{B}} \equiv \left\{ \tilde{b} \in \hat{\mathbb{B}} \mid \text{PAT}(\tilde{b}) \right\}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{PAT}(\text{true}) & \equiv & \text{true} \\ & \text{PAT}(\text{false}) & \equiv & \text{true} \\ \forall \hat{b}. & \quad \text{PAT}(\neg(\hat{b})) & \equiv & \text{PAT}(\hat{b}) \\ \forall \hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2. & \quad \text{PAT}(\hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2) & \equiv & \text{PAT}(\hat{b}_1) \wedge \text{PAT}(\hat{b}_2) \\ \forall \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. & \quad \text{PAT}(\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2) & \equiv & \hat{e}_1 \in \mathbb{E} \wedge \hat{e}_2 \in \mathbb{E} \\ \forall \hat{e}, n. & \quad \text{PAT}(|\hat{e}| = n) & \equiv & \hat{e} \in \mathbb{E} \\ \forall \hat{e}. & \quad \text{PAT}(\text{pub}(\hat{e})) & \equiv & \text{false} \end{aligned}$$

3.1.3 Invariants

Definition 3.1.K. Invariants are specific sets of cryptogram and boolean pattern pairs $I \in \text{Inv}$:

$$\text{Inv} = \left\{ I \subseteq \widetilde{\text{CG}} \times \tilde{\mathbb{B}} \mid \begin{array}{l} \forall (\tilde{\text{cg}}, \tilde{b}) \in I. \text{VARS}(\tilde{b}) \subseteq \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{cg}}) \wedge \\ \forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \exists! \tilde{b}. (\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}), \tilde{b}) \in I \wedge \\ \forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \exists! v_{\text{p}}, \tilde{b}. (\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_{\text{p}}), \tilde{b}) \in I \end{array} \right\}$$

3.2 Proof rules

3.2.1 Syntactical entailment of boolean expressions

Definition 3.2.A. Rules to deduce facts about boolean expressions with the judgment $_ \cdot _ \vdash _ : \text{Inv} \times \hat{\mathbb{B}} \times \hat{\mathbb{B}}$

$$\begin{array}{c} \frac{}{I \cdot \hat{b} \vdash \hat{b}} \text{BREFL} \quad \frac{I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \hat{b}_2 \quad I \cdot \hat{b}_2 \vdash \hat{b}_3}{I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \hat{b}_3} \text{BTRANS} \\ \\ \frac{}{I \cdot \hat{b} \vdash \text{true}} \text{BTRUE} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \text{false} \vdash \hat{b}} \text{BFALSE} \quad \frac{I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \hat{b}_2 \quad I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \neg(\hat{b}_2)}{I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \text{false}} \text{BCONTRA} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \widehat{b}_2 \vdash \widehat{b}_1} \text{BANDL} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \widehat{b}_2 \vdash \widehat{b}_2} \text{BANDR} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{b}_1 \quad I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{b}_2}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \widehat{b}_2} \text{BAND} \\
\\
\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e} = \widehat{e}} \text{BEQREFL} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_2 \quad I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e}_2 = \widehat{e}_3}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_3} \text{BEQTRANS} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e}_2 = \widehat{e}_1}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_2} \text{BEQSYM} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash v = \widehat{e} \quad I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash (\widehat{b}_2)[\widehat{e}/v]}{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \widehat{b}_2} \text{BVARINTRO} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash v = \widehat{e} \quad I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \widehat{b}_2}{I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash (\widehat{b}_2)[\widehat{e}/v]} \text{BVARELIM} \\
\\
\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |s| = |s|} \text{BLENLIT} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}_1| = n_1 \quad I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}_2| = n_1}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2| = n_1 + n_2} \text{BLENCONC} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}| = n_1}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}[n_2]| = \min(n_1, n_2)} \text{BLENPREF} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}| = n_1}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash |\widehat{e}[n_2 :]| = n_1 - \min(n_1, n_2)} \text{BLENSUFF} \\
\\
\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(s)} \text{BPUBLIT} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e}_1) \quad I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e}_2)}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2)} \text{BPUBCONC} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e})}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e}[n :])} \text{BPUBPREF} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e})}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{e}[n :])} \text{BPUBSUFF} \\
\\
\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}, \widetilde{b}) \in I \quad \{\{\widetilde{v}\}\} = \text{VARS}(\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}) \\ I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash (\widetilde{b})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}] \quad \forall e \in \{\{\widetilde{e}\}\}. I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(e) \end{array}}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}2s((\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}]))} \text{BPUBINTRO} \\
\\
\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}, \widetilde{b}) \in I \quad \{\{\widetilde{v}\}\} = \text{VARS}(\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}) \\ I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g}2s((\widetilde{c}\widetilde{g})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}])) \quad \forall e \in \{\{\widetilde{e}\}\}. I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \text{pub}(e) \end{array}}{I \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash (\widetilde{b})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}]} \text{BPUBELIM}
\end{array}$$

3.2.2 Proof rules for Hoare triples of non-forking commands

Definition 3.2.B. *Proof rules for Hoare triples with the judgment $\cdot \vdash \{- : -\} \{- : -\} : \text{Inv} \times \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \times \widehat{B} \times C \times \mathbb{N} \times \widehat{B}$*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} \text{skip} \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\}} \text{HSKIP} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} \text{stuck} \{n_{\#} : \text{false}\}} \text{HSTUCK} \\
\\
\frac{}{I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \text{false}\} \text{fail} \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\}} \text{HFAIL}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \mathbf{pub}(e)\} \mathbf{snd}(e) \{n_{\#} : \mathbf{true}\}} \text{HSEND} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \mathbf{true}\} \mathbf{rcv}(v) \{n_{\#} : \mathbf{pub}(v)\}} \text{HRECEIVE} \\
\\
\frac{}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : (\widehat{b})[e/v]\} v := e \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\}} \text{HASSIGN} \\
\\
\frac{\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_k = \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(n_{id}, n_{\#})}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} + \mathbf{1} : (\widehat{b})[\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}2s(\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_k)/v]\} v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s\}} \text{HSAMPLE} \\
\\
\frac{\begin{array}{c} I \cdot \widehat{b}' \vdash v_k = \widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}2s(\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_k) \quad I \cdot \widehat{b}' \vdash \mathbf{pub}(v_p) \\ \widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_k = \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}) \quad \widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_h = \widehat{\mathbf{hmac}}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, v_p) \quad \widehat{b}' = (\widehat{b})[\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}2s(\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}_h)/v] \end{array}}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\} v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s\}} \text{HHMAC} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge |e| = n\} c_1 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\} \quad I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(|e| = n)\} c_2 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\}}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{\max(n_{\#_1}, n_{\#_2}) : \widehat{b}_1\} |e| = n ? c_1 : c_2 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\}} \text{HIFLEN} \\
\\
\frac{\begin{array}{c} I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \mathbf{pub}(e_1) \quad I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \mathbf{pub}(e_2) \vee I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash e_2 = \widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}2s(\widetilde{\mathbf{cg}}) \\ I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge e_1 = e_2\} c_1 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\} \quad I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(e_1 = e_2)\} c_2 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\} \end{array}}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{\max(n_{\#_1}, n_{\#_2}) : \widehat{b}_1\} e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}_2\}} \text{HIFEQ} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c_1 \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\} \quad I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\} c_2 \{n_{\#_3} : \widehat{b}_3\}}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c_1 ; c_2 \{n_{\#_3} : \widehat{b}_3\}} \text{HSEQ} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot \widehat{b}'_1 \vdash \widehat{b}_1 \quad I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\} \quad I \cdot \widehat{b}_2 \vdash \widehat{b}'_2}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}'_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}'_2\}} \text{HCONSEQ} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\} \quad \text{VARS} := (c) \cap \text{VARS}(\widehat{b}) = \emptyset}{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b} \wedge \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b} \wedge \widehat{b}_2\}} \text{HCONST}
\end{array}$$

3.2.3 Proof rules for forking commands

Definition 3.2.C. *Proof rules for forking commands given an invariant I and an identity number n_{id} :*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\}}{I \cdot n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c} \text{FLIFT} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c_1 \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\} \quad I \cdot n_{id} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b}' \vdash c_2}{I \cdot n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c_1 ; c_2} \text{FSEQ} \\
\\
\frac{I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c_1 \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\} \quad I \cdot n_{id} + \mathbf{1} \cdot n''_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c_2}{I \cdot n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash \mathbf{fork}(c_1) ; c_2} \text{FFORK}
\end{array}$$

3.2.4 Valid protocol implementations

Definition 3.2.D. *The attacker identity: $\text{ATT}_{ID} \equiv \mathbf{0}$*

Definition 3.2.E. A attacker approved invariant is any invariant which is closed under attacker actions; i.e. ensures that all cryptogram expressions that can be produced by the attacker are public.

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall I. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I) \\ & \equiv \\ & \left(\forall n_{\#}. (\widehat{\text{key}}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}), \text{true}) \in I \right) \wedge \\ & \left(\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_p, \tilde{b}_1, \tilde{b}_2. (\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}), \tilde{b}_1) \in I \wedge (\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_p), \tilde{b}_2) \in I \Rightarrow I \cdot \tilde{b}_1 \vdash \tilde{b}_2 \right) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.2.F. Validity of a command that implements a protocol given an invariant:

$$\forall I, c. \text{VERIFIED}_I(c) \equiv \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I) \wedge \exists n_{\#}. I \cdot \mathbf{1} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{true} \vdash c$$

3.3 Verification of the example protocol

3.3.1 Verification goal

- We choose the identity number for principal A as $n_a = \mathbf{1}$
- We choose the identity number for principal B as $n_b = \mathbf{2}$
- The key shared between A and B is denoted by $\widehat{\text{key}}(n_a, \mathbf{0})$
- To verify the protocol we must specify some I such that for any s_m we can show $\text{VERIFIED}_I(c_{\text{auth}}(s_m))$.

3.3.2 Invariant for the protocol implementation

Definition 3.3.A. The proposed invariant for some message s_m after picking the fixed variable v_x :

$$I_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \equiv \left\{ (\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}), \text{false}) \mid n_{\text{id}} \neq \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \right\} \cup \left\{ (\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}), \text{true}) \mid n_{\text{id}} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \right\} \cup \left\{ (\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_x), v_x = s_m) \mid n_{\text{id}} \neq \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \right\} \cup \left\{ (\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_x), \text{true}) \mid n_{\text{id}} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \right\}$$

- Clearly $(\widehat{\text{key}}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}), \text{true}) \in I_{\text{auth}}(s_m)$ for any $n_{\#}$.
- For any $n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_p, \tilde{b}_1$ and \tilde{b}_2 such that
 - $(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}), \tilde{b}_1) \in I_{\text{auth}}(s_m)$
 - $(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_p), \tilde{b}_2) \in I_{\text{auth}}(s_m)$

We can derive $I \cdot \tilde{b}_1 \vdash \tilde{b}_2$ in both possible cases:

- $\boxed{n_{\text{id}} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}$ By applying BTRUE since $\tilde{b}_2 = \text{true}$.
- $\boxed{n_{\text{id}} \neq \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}$ By applying BFALSE since $\tilde{b}_1 = \text{false}$.

- So from Definition 3.2.E one can derive that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I_{\text{auth}}(s_m))$.

3.3.3 Verification of implementation protocol role A

To verify the implementation of role A for the message s_m we show $I_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \cdot n_a \vdash \{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K}\}_{c_A(s_m)} \{\mathbf{0} : \text{true}\}$ where we make use of the abbreviations:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &\equiv I_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \\
\widehat{K} &\equiv v_k = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_a, \mathbf{0})) \wedge |v_k| = N_s \\
\widehat{M}_1 &\equiv v_m = s_m \\
\widehat{H}_{\text{eq}} &\equiv \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) \\
\widehat{H} &\equiv v_h = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) \wedge |v_h| = N_s \\
\widehat{M}_2 &\equiv v_{\text{msg}} = s_m ++ v_h \\
\widehat{B} &\equiv \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \wedge \widehat{M}_2
\end{aligned}$$

HSEQ/HCONSEQ

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K}\}$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash \widehat{K}} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash s_m = s_m} \text{BEQREFL}}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge s_m = s_m} \text{BAND}$$

HASSIGN

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \wedge s_m = s_m\}$

$v_m := s_m$

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1\}$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \vdash \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}}} \text{BEQREFL}}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}}} \text{BAND}$$

HHMAC

$$\frac{\dots (\text{BANDR}/\text{BANDL}/\text{BTRANS})}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}} \vdash v_k = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}))}$$

$$\frac{\dots (\text{BANDR}/\text{BANDL}/\text{BTRANS}) \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}} \vdash v_m = s_m} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}} \vdash \text{pub}(s_m)} \text{BPUBLIT}}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_m)} \text{BVARINTRO}$$

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}_{\text{eq}}\}$

$v_h \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_m)$

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}\}$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H}} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash s_m ++ v_h = s_m ++ v_h} \text{BEQREFL}}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \wedge s_m ++ v_h = s_m ++ v_h} \text{BAND}$$

HASSIGN

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M}_1 \wedge \widehat{H} \wedge s_m ++ v_h = s_m ++ v_h\}$

$v_{\text{msg}} := s_m ++ v_h$

$\{\mathbf{0} : \widehat{B}\}$

3.3.4 Verification of implementation protocol role B

To verify the implementation of role B for the message s_m we show $I_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \cdot n_b \vdash \{ \mathbf{0} : \widehat{K} \} c_B(s_m) \{ \mathbf{0} : \text{true} \}$ where we make use of the abbreviations:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &\equiv I_{\text{auth}}(s_m) \\
\widehat{K} &\equiv v_k = \widehat{cg2s}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_a, \mathbf{0})) \wedge |v_k| = N_s \\
\widehat{P} &\equiv \text{pub}(v_{msg}) \\
\widehat{M} &\equiv v_m = v_{msg}[:|s_m|] \\
\widehat{H} &\equiv v_h = v_{msg}[|s_m|:] \\
\widehat{H}'_{\text{eq}} &\equiv \widehat{cg2s}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) = \widehat{cg2s}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) \\
\widehat{H}' &\equiv v_{h'} = \widehat{cg2s}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, \mathbf{0}, v_m)) \wedge |v_{h'}| = N_s \\
\widehat{B} &\equiv \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H} \wedge \widehat{H}' \\
\widehat{B}_{\text{false}} &\equiv \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'} \wedge \neg(v_m = s_m)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash \widehat{K}} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash \text{true}} \text{BTRUE}}{\text{BAND} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \text{true}}}$$

HCONST

HRECV

$\{0 : \text{true}\}$
 $\text{rcv}(v_{\text{msg}})$
 $\{0 : \widehat{P}\}$

$\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \text{true}\}$
 $\text{rcv}(v_{\text{msg}})$
 $\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P}\}$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P}} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \vdash v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]} \text{BEQREFL}}{\text{BAND} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]}}$$

HASSIGN

$\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]\}$
 $v_m := v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]$
 $\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M}\}$

$$\frac{\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M}} \text{BREFL} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \vdash v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]} \text{BEQREFL}}{\text{BAND} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]}}$$

HASSIGN

$\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|] = v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]\}$
 $v_h := v_{\text{msg}}[|s_m|]$
 $\{0 : \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H}\}$

$$\frac{\text{BREFL} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H}} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash \widehat{H}'_{\text{eq}}} \text{BEQREFL}}{\text{BAND} \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H} \vdash \widehat{K} \wedge \widehat{P} \wedge \widehat{M} \wedge \widehat{H} \wedge \widehat{H}'_{\text{eq}}}}$$

HCONSEQ

$$\frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{B} \wedge \neg(v_h = v_{h'}) \vdash \widehat{B} \wedge \neg(v_h = v_{h'})} \text{BREFL} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \text{false} \vdash \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'}} \text{BFALSE}$$

HSTUCK

$\{0 : \widehat{B} \wedge \neg(v_h = v_{h'})\}$
stuck
 $\{0 : \text{false}\}$

$\{0 : \widehat{B} \wedge \neg(v_h = v_{h'})\}$
stuck
 $\{0 : \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'}\}$

H_{B2}

$$\frac{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}})}{I \cdot \widehat{B} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m|])} \text{BPUBPREF}}{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B} \vdash v_h = v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m| :]}{I \cdot \widehat{B} \vdash \text{pub}(v_m)} \text{BVARINTRO}} \text{BPUBLIT} \quad \frac{}{I \cdot \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'} \vdash \text{pub}(s_m)} \text{BPUBLIT}$$

HSKIP

$\{0 : \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'} \wedge v_m = s_m\}$
skip
 $\{0 : \widehat{B} \wedge v_h = v_{h'} \wedge v_m = s_m\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{T}_{B1} &\equiv \frac{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}})}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m|])} \text{BPUBPREF}}{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash v_m = v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m| :]}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_m)} \text{BVARINTRO}} \text{BVARINTRO} \\ \text{T}_{B2} &\equiv \frac{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}})}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m| :])} \text{BPUBSUFF}}{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash v_h = v_{\text{msg}}[: |s_m| :]}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_h)} \text{BVARELIM}} \text{BVARELIM} \\ \text{T}_{B3} &\equiv \frac{\dots \text{ (BANDR/BANDL/BTRANS)} \quad \frac{v_{h'} = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, 0, v_m)) \quad \frac{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash v_h = v_{h'}}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(v_{h'})} \text{BVARELIM}}{I \cdot \widehat{B}_{\text{false}} \vdash \text{pub}(\widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_a, 0, v_m)))} \text{BVARELIM}} \text{BVARELIM} \end{aligned}$$

4 Semantics of assertions

4.1 Crypto strings, crypto stores and cryptograms

4.1.1 Secret coin tosses

Definition 4.1.A. The parameter N_ψ of the proof system: it represents the number of secret N_s -fold coin tosses such that $N_\psi > 0$.

Definition 4.1.B. A series of secret N_s -fold coin tosses: $\psi \in \Psi$ and

$$\Psi = \left\{ \psi \in S^* \mid |\psi| = N_\psi \wedge \forall s \in \{\psi\}. |s| = N_s \right\}$$

Theorem 4.1.A. The number of possible secret N_s -fold coin tosses is finite: $|\Psi| = (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi}$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.1.B □

Definition 4.1.C. A series of all zero N_s -fold coin tosses: $\psi_0 \in \Psi$ and $\forall s \in \{\psi_0\}. \forall n < N_s. s[n] = 0$

Definition 4.1.D. The N_s -fold coin toss series where the n^{th} N_s -fold coin toss is equal/not equal to a string:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall s, n \quad \Psi_{n=s} &\equiv \left\{ \psi \in \Psi \mid \psi[n] = s \right\} \\ \forall s, n \quad \Psi_{n \neq s} &\equiv \Psi \setminus \Psi_{n=s} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1.B. Some cardinality properties of N_s -fold coin toss series where a single N_s -fold coin toss is checked for equality with a string:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall s, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{n=s}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \\ \forall s, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{n \neq s}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \times (2^{N_s} - 1) \\ \forall s, n. \frac{|\Psi_{n=s}|}{|\Psi|} &= \frac{1}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.1.B and 4.1.D. □

Definition 4.1.E. The N_s -fold coin toss series where the n^{th} N_s -fold coin toss is a member/not a member of some set of strings:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \dot{s}, n \quad \Psi_{n \in \dot{s}} &\equiv \left\{ \psi \in \Psi \mid \psi[n] \in \dot{s} \right\} \\ \forall \dot{s}, n \quad \Psi_{n \notin \dot{s}} &\equiv \Psi \setminus \Psi_{n \in \dot{s}} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1.C. Some cardinality properties of N_s -fold coin toss series where a single N_s -fold coin toss is checked for membership of some set of strings:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \dot{s}, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{n \in \dot{s}}| &= |\dot{s}| \times (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \\ \forall \dot{s}, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{n \notin \dot{s}}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \times (2^{N_s} - |\dot{s}|) \\ \forall \dot{s}, n. \frac{|\Psi_{n \in \dot{s}}|}{|\Psi|} &= \frac{|\dot{s}|}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.1.B and 4.1.E. □

Definition 4.1.F. The N_s -fold coin toss series where one/none of the n first N_s -fold coin tosses is equal to a given string:

$$\begin{aligned}\forall s, n \quad \Psi_{s \in n} &\equiv \left\{ \psi \in \Psi \mid \exists n' < n. \psi[n'] = s \right\} \\ \forall s, n \quad \Psi_{s \notin n} &\equiv \Psi \setminus \Psi_{s \in n}\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1.D. Some cardinality properties of N_s -fold coin toss series where the n first N_s -fold coin tosses are checked for equality with a string:

$$\begin{aligned}\forall s, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{s \in n}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - n} \times ((2^{N_s})^n - (2^{N_s} - 1)^n) \leq n \times (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \\ \forall s, n < N_\psi. |\Psi_{s \notin n}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - n} \times (2^{N_s} - 1)^n \\ \forall s, n. \frac{|\Psi_{s \in n}|}{|\Psi|} &\leq \frac{n}{2^{N_s}}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.1.B and 4.1.F. □

Definition 4.1.G. The N_s -fold coin toss series where some N_s -fold coin toss clashes with some other N_s -fold coin toss within a specific range:

$$\begin{aligned}\forall n', n \quad \Psi_{n' \in n} &\equiv \left\{ \psi \in \Psi \mid \exists n'' < n. n' \neq n'' \wedge \psi[n'] = \psi[n''] \right\} \\ \forall n', n \quad \Psi_{n' \notin n} &\equiv \Psi \setminus \Psi_{n' \in n}\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1.E. Some cardinality properties of N_s -fold coin toss series where a N_s -fold coin toss clashes with some other N_s -fold coin toss within a specific range:

$$\begin{aligned}\forall n < N_\psi, n' < n. |\Psi_{n' \in n}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - n + 1} \times ((2^{N_s})^{n-1} - (2^{N_s} - 1)^{n-1}) \leq (n-1) \times (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - 1} \\ \forall n < N_\psi, n' < n. |\Psi_{n' \notin n}| &= (2^{N_s})^{N_\psi - n + 1} \times (2^{N_s} - 1)^{n-1} \\ \forall n, n'. \frac{|\Psi_{n' \in n}|}{|\Psi|} &\leq \frac{n-1}{2^{N_s}}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.1.B and 4.1.G. □

4.1.2 Crypto strings

Definition 4.1.H. A crypto string is a string that is dependent on the secret coin tosses; i.e. it maps a series of secret coin tosses to a concrete string: $\underline{s} \in \underline{S}$ and $\underline{S} = \left\{ \underline{s} \in S^\Psi \mid \exists n. \forall \psi. |\underline{s}(\psi)| = n \right\}$. Two crypto strings are considered equal if they exhibit extensional equality, that is $\forall \underline{s}_1, \underline{s}_2. \underline{s}_1 = \underline{s}_2 \Leftrightarrow (\forall \psi. \underline{s}_1(\psi) = \underline{s}_2(\psi))$.

Definition 4.1.I. The length of a crypto string: $\forall \underline{s}, n. (|\underline{s}| = n \Leftrightarrow \forall \psi. |\underline{s}(\psi)| = n)$.

Definition 4.1.J. Notation for collapsing a crypto string into a concrete string: $\underline{s} \downarrow \psi$

$$\forall \underline{s}, \psi. \underline{s} \downarrow \psi \equiv \underline{s}(\psi)$$

Definition 4.1.K. Notation for collapsing a list defined as general as possible for reusability: $\bar{x} \downarrow \psi$

$$\begin{aligned}\forall \psi. \quad [] \downarrow \psi &\equiv [] \\ \forall \underline{x}, \bar{x}, \psi. \quad (\underline{x} :: \bar{x}) \downarrow \psi &\equiv \underline{x} \downarrow \psi :: \bar{x} \downarrow \psi\end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.1.L. One can lift a regular string to a crypto string: $s2\underline{s}(s) \equiv \lambda \dots s$.

Theorem 4.1.F. A crypto string that is independent from the secret coin tosses is simply a lifted string:

$$\forall \underline{s}, s. (\forall \psi. \underline{s}(\psi) = s) \Rightarrow \underline{s} = s2\underline{s}(s)$$

Proof. Using extensional equality this is straightforwardly proven. Indeed, if we assume $\forall \psi. \underline{s}(\psi) = s$ for some \underline{s} and s , it is obvious that for any ψ we have $\underline{s}(\psi) = s = (\lambda \dots s)(\psi) = (s2\underline{s}(s))(\psi)$. \square

Definition 4.1.M. Lifting some string operations to crypto string operations:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \underline{s}, n. \quad \underline{s}[: n] &\equiv \lambda \psi. \underline{s}(\psi)[: n] \\ \forall \underline{s}, n. \quad \underline{s}[n :] &\equiv \lambda \psi. \underline{s}(\psi)[n :] \\ \forall \underline{s}_1, \underline{s}_2. \quad \underline{s}_1 ++ \underline{s}_2 &\equiv \lambda \psi. \underline{s}_1(\psi) ++ \underline{s}_2(\psi) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1.G. Equality of crypto strings under a prefix or suffix operation:

$$\forall \underline{s}_1, \underline{s}_2, n. \underline{s}_1 = \underline{s}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{s}_1[: n] = \underline{s}_2[: n] \wedge \underline{s}_1[n :] = \underline{s}_2[n :]$$

Proof. Using extensional equality this theorem is straightforwardly proven. \square

Theorem 4.1.H. Equality of crypto strings after concatenation:

$$(\forall \underline{s}, n. \underline{s} = \underline{s}[: n] ++ \underline{s}[n :]) \wedge (\forall \underline{s}_1, \underline{s}_2, \underline{s}_3, \underline{s}_4. \underline{s}_1 = \underline{s}_2 \wedge \underline{s}_3 = \underline{s}_4 \Rightarrow \underline{s}_1 ++ \underline{s}_3 = \underline{s}_2 ++ \underline{s}_4)$$

Proof. Using extensional equality this theorem is straightforwardly proven. \square

4.1.3 Crypto stores

Definition 4.1.N. Crypto stores: $st \in \underline{ST}$ and $\underline{ST} \equiv \mathbb{S}^V$

Definition 4.1.O. The empty crypto store: $st_\varepsilon \in \underline{ST}$ and $\forall v. st_\varepsilon(v) = s2\underline{s}(\varepsilon)$

Definition 4.1.P. Collapsing a crypto store to a concrete store : $\underline{st} \downarrow \psi$ and $\forall \underline{st}, \psi. \underline{st} \downarrow \psi \equiv \lambda v. \underline{st}(v) \downarrow \psi$.

4.1.4 Cryptograms

Definition 4.1.Q. A cryptogram represents the result of a cryptographic primitive $cg \in \underline{CG}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{cg} & ::= \\ & | \text{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \quad (n_{id}, n_{\#} \in \mathbb{N}) \\ & | \text{hmac}(n_{id}, n_{\#}, s_p) \quad (n_{id}, n_{\#} \in \mathbb{N}, s_p \in \mathbb{S}) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.1.R. The identity number of a cryptogram: $\text{id}(_) : \underline{CG} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall n_{id}, n_{\#}. \quad \text{id}(\text{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#})) &\equiv n_{id} \\ \forall n_{id}, n_{\#}, s_p. \quad \text{id}(\text{hmac}(n_{id}, n_{\#}, s_p)) &\equiv n_{id} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.1.S. The sequence number of a cryptogram: $\text{seq}(-) : \text{CG} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}. \quad \text{seq}(\text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})) &\equiv n_{\#} \\ \forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}}. \quad \text{seq}(\text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}})) &\equiv n_{\#} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.1.T. An upper bound for the identity numbers of all cryptograms in some list: $-\prec- : \text{CG}^* \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$

$$\forall \bar{\text{cg}}, n_{\text{id}}. \quad \bar{\text{cg}} \prec n_{\text{id}} \equiv \forall \text{cg} \in \{\{\bar{\text{cg}}\}\}. \quad \text{id}(\text{cg}) < n_{\text{id}}$$

Definition 4.1.U. A lower bound for the sequence numbers of all cryptograms in some list for a given identity number: $-\succ- : \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \times \text{CG}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$

$$\forall n_{\#}, n_{\text{id}}, \bar{\text{cg}}. \quad n_{\#} \succ_{n_{\text{id}}} \bar{\text{cg}} \equiv \forall \text{cg} \in \{\{\bar{\text{cg}}\}\}. \quad \text{id}(\text{cg}) = n_{\text{id}} \Rightarrow n_{\#} \leq \text{seq}(\text{cg})$$

Definition 4.1.V. Mappings from cryptograms to crypto strings: $\text{cs} \in \text{CS}$:

$$\text{CS} = \left\{ \text{cs} \in \underline{\text{S}}^{\text{CG}} \mid \forall \text{cg}. \quad |\text{cs}(\text{cg})| = N_s \right\}$$

4.2 The semantics of all expressions and invariants

4.2.1 A semantics for expressions

Definition 4.2.A. The semantics of program expressions given a crypto store

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \underline{\text{st}}, s. \quad \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} &\equiv s2\underline{\text{s}}(s) \\ \forall \underline{\text{st}}, v. \quad \llbracket v \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} &\equiv \underline{\text{st}}(v) \\ \forall \underline{\text{st}}, e, n. \quad \llbracket e[: n] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} &\equiv \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}[: n] \\ \forall \underline{\text{st}}, e, n. \quad \llbracket e[n :] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} &\equiv \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} [n :] \\ \forall \underline{\text{st}}, e_1, e_2. \quad \llbracket e_1 ++ e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} &\equiv \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} ++ \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.2.A. Evaluation of expressions in a collapsed crypto store is the same as collapsing their semantics:

$$\forall \underline{\text{st}}, \psi, e. \quad \text{EVAL}(\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi, e) = (\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \rrbracket_{\psi})$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on e for some $\underline{\text{st}}$ and ψ :

- $\boxed{e = s}$ We have in this case that $\text{EVAL}(\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi, s) = s = (s2\underline{\text{s}}(s))(\psi) = (\llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \rrbracket_{\psi})$.
- $\boxed{e = v}$ Now we have $\text{EVAL}(\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi, v) = (\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi)(v) = \underline{\text{st}}(v) \downarrow \psi = (\llbracket v \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \rrbracket_{\psi})$.
- $\boxed{e = e'[: n]}$ Using induction we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EVAL}(\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi, e'[: n]) &= (\text{EVAL}(\underline{\text{st}} \downarrow \psi, e'))[: n] = \\ &((\llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \rrbracket_{\psi}))[: n] = (\lambda \psi'. \quad (\llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}(\psi'))[: n])(\psi) = (\llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}[: n] \rrbracket_{\psi}) \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{e = e'[n :]}$ This case is analogue to the previous case.

- $e = e_1 ++ e_2$ Using induction we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EVAL}(\underline{st} \downarrow \psi, e_1 ++ e_2) &= \text{EVAL}(\underline{st} \downarrow \psi, e_1) ++ \text{EVAL}(\underline{st} \downarrow \psi, e_2) = ([e_1]_{\underline{st}})(\psi) ++ ([e_2]_{\underline{st}})(\psi) = \\ &(\lambda \psi'. [e_1]_{\underline{st}}(\psi'))(\psi) ++ (\lambda \psi'. [e_2]_{\underline{st}}(\psi'))(\psi) = (\lambda \psi'. [e_1]_{\underline{st}}(\psi') ++ [e_2]_{\underline{st}}(\psi'))(\psi) = \\ &(\lambda \psi'. [e_1 ++ e_2]_{\underline{st}}(\psi'))(\psi) = ([e_1 ++ e_2]_{\underline{st}})(\psi) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.2.B. *The semantics of a program expression is the same in crypto stores that map all the variables that occur in that expression to the same crypto string:*

$$\forall e, \underline{st}_1, \underline{st}_2. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(e). \underline{st}_1(v) = \underline{st}_2(v)) \Rightarrow ([e]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e]_{\underline{st}_2})$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on e . So for each case we need to prove for some \underline{st}_1 and \underline{st}_2 that $[e]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e]_{\underline{st}_2}$ given $\forall v \in \text{VARS}(e). \underline{st}_1(v) = \underline{st}_2(v)$. Using Definition 2.1.C we have:

- $e = s$

We trivially have $[s]_{\underline{st}_1} = s2s(s) = [s]_{\underline{st}_2}$.

- $e = v$

$[v]_{\underline{st}_1} = \underline{st}_1(v) = \underline{st}_2(v) = [v]_{\underline{st}_2}$ follows directly from $v \in \text{VARS}(e)$ and $\forall v \in \text{VARS}(e). \underline{st}_1(v) = \underline{st}_2(v)$.

- $e = e'[: n]$

Using the induction hypothesis and $\text{VARS}(e') \subseteq \text{VARS}(e)$ we get $[e']_{\underline{st}_1} = [e']_{\underline{st}_2}$. With Theorem 4.1.G we can now show: $[e'[: n]]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e']_{\underline{st}_1}[n:] = [e']_{\underline{st}_2}[n:] = [e'[: n]]_{\underline{st}_2}$.

- $e = e'[n:]$

This case is analogue to the previous case.

- $e = e_1 ++ e_2$

Using the induction hypothesis and $\text{VARS}(e_1) \subseteq \text{VARS}(e)$ and $\text{VARS}(e_2) \subseteq \text{VARS}(e)$ we get $[e_1]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e_1]_{\underline{st}_2}$ and $[e_2]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e_2]_{\underline{st}_2}$. With Theorem 4.1.H we can now show: $[e_1 ++ e_2]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e_1]_{\underline{st}_1} ++ [e_2]_{\underline{st}_1} = [e_1]_{\underline{st}_2} ++ [e_2]_{\underline{st}_2} = [e_1 ++ e_2]_{\underline{st}_2}$.

□

Definition 4.2.B. *The semantics of string/ciphertext expressions for a crypto store and ciphertext mapping*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall cs, \underline{st}, e. & [e]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & [e]_{\underline{st}} \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, \widehat{cg}. & [\widehat{cg}2s(\widehat{cg})]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & cs([\widehat{cg}]_{\underline{st}}^{cs}) \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, \widehat{e}, n. & [\widehat{e}[: n]]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & [e]_{\underline{st}}^{cs}[: n] \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, \widehat{e}, n. & [\widehat{e}[n:]]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & [e]_{\underline{st}}^{cs}[n:] \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, \widehat{e}_1, \widehat{e}_2. & [\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & [\widehat{e}_1]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} ++ [\widehat{e}_2]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \\ \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, n_{id}, n_{\#}. & [\widehat{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#})]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & key(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \\ \forall cs, \underline{st}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \widehat{e}_p. & [\widehat{hmac}(n_{id}, n_{\#}, \widehat{e}_p)]_{\underline{st}}^{cs} & \equiv & hmac(n_{id}, n_{\#}, ([\widehat{e}_p]_{\underline{st}}^{cs})(\psi_0)) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.2.C. *The semantics of boolean expressions for a crypto store and cryptogram mapping:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall \text{cs, st.} \quad & \llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \text{true} \\
\forall \text{cs, st.} \quad & \llbracket \text{false} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \text{false} \\
\forall \text{cs, st, } \hat{b}. \quad & \llbracket \neg(\hat{b}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \neg \llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \\
\forall \text{cs, st, } \hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2. \quad & \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \\
\forall \text{cs, st, } \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2. \quad & \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \\
\forall \text{cs, st, } \hat{e}, n. \quad & \llbracket |\hat{e}| = n \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv |\llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}| = n \\
\forall \text{cs, st, } \hat{e}. \quad & \llbracket \text{pub}(\hat{e}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \exists s. \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = \text{s2s}(s)
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.2.D. *The semantics of a list of expressions defined as general as possible for reusability:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall \text{cs, st.} \quad & \llbracket [] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv [] \\
\forall \text{cs, st, x, } \bar{x}. \quad & \llbracket x :: \bar{x} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \equiv \llbracket x \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} :: \llbracket \bar{x} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.2.C. *Syntactic entailment implies semantical entailment*

$$\forall I, \hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2 \quad I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \hat{b}_2 \Rightarrow \left(\forall \text{st, cs. } I \propto \text{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \right)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on the derivation of $I \cdot \hat{b}_1 \vdash \hat{b}_2$ for some I , \hat{b}_1 and \hat{b}_2 . Definition 4.2.C and 3.2.A are used implicitly throughout this proof. We thus must show for each inductive case that for any cs and st such that $I \propto \text{cs}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ it must hold that $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$:

- **BREFL** From $\hat{b}_1 = \hat{b}_2$ it clearly follows that $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BTRANS** Now $\llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ for some \hat{b} by induction and so clearly $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BTRUE** Since now $\hat{b}_2 = \text{true}$ and we know that $\llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \text{true}$ we have $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BFALSE** Since now $\hat{b}_1 = \text{false}$ and we know that $\llbracket \text{false} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \text{false}$ we have a contradiction.
- **BCONTRA** Now we have $\llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \neg(\hat{b}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ for some \hat{b} by induction and so we have a contradiction.
- **BANDL** We now have $\hat{b}_1 = \hat{b}_2 \wedge \hat{b}$ for some \hat{b} and thus $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BANDR** This case is analogous to the previous one.
- **BAND**
Fore some \hat{b}_3 and \hat{b}_4 we now know that $\hat{b}_2 = \hat{b}_3 \wedge \hat{b}_4$, $\llbracket \hat{b}_3 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b}_4 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ by induction. Then it is easy to see that $\llbracket \hat{b}_3 \wedge \hat{b}_4 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and thus $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BEQREFL**
We know that $\hat{b}_2 = (\hat{e} = \hat{e})$ for some \hat{e} . It is obviously true that $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{e} = \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \text{true}$ and so we can conclude that $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$.
- **BEQTRANS**
In this case we know for some \hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2 and \hat{e}_3 that $\hat{b}_2 = (\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_3)$ and we have by induction that $\llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \hat{e}_2 = \hat{e}_3 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$. We can now deduce that:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{e}_2 = \hat{e}_3 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e}_3 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e}_3 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_3 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BEQSYM**

For some \hat{e}_1 and \hat{e}_2 we have $\hat{b}_2 = (\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2)$ and by induction $\llbracket \hat{e}_2 = \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. We now have:

$$\llbracket \hat{e}_2 = \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$$

- **BVARINTRO**

By induction we have $\llbracket v = \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ and $\llbracket (\hat{b}_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ for some v and \hat{e} . Using Theorem 4.3.C we can now establish:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\llbracket v = \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket (\hat{b}_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket v \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \llbracket v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \llbracket v := \llbracket v \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{b}_2)[v/v] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BVARELIM**

We now have that $\hat{b}_2 = (\hat{b})[\hat{e}/v]$ for some \hat{b} , v and \hat{e} . By induction we also know that $\llbracket v = \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. So now we can establish:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\llbracket v = \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket v \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket (\hat{b})[v/v] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\llbracket v \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \llbracket v := \llbracket v \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \right) \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \llbracket v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{b})[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BLENLIT**

In this case we have $\hat{b}_2 = (|s| = |s|)$ for some s . It is obvious that $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket |s| = |s| \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow |s| = |s| \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{true}$ and so we can conclude $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$.

- **BLENPREF**

We now have $\hat{b}_2 = (\llbracket \hat{e} : n_2 \rrbracket = \min(n_1, n_2))$ for some \hat{e} , n_1 and n_2 . By induction we know that $\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e} = n_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket$ and so we can deduce:

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e} = n_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = n_1 \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} : n_2 \rrbracket = \min(n_1, n_2) \Rightarrow \\ & \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e} : n_2 \rrbracket = \min(n_1, n_2) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BLENSUFF** This case is analogous to the previous one.

- **BLENCONC**

We now have $\hat{b}_2 = (\llbracket \hat{e}_1 ++ \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket = n_1 + n_2)$ for some \hat{e}_1 , \hat{e}_2 , n_1 and n_2 . By induction we know that $\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = n_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket$ and $\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_2 = n_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket$ and so we derive:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = n_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \wedge \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_2 = n_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \rrbracket \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = n_1 \wedge \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = n_2 \rrbracket \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} ++ \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = n_1 + n_2 \rrbracket \right) \Rightarrow \llbracket \llbracket \hat{e}_1 ++ \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket = n_1 + n_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BPUBLIT**

For some s we know that $\hat{b}_2 = \mathbf{pub}(s)$ and it is clear that $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(s) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow (\exists s'. \llbracket s \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s')) \Leftrightarrow (\exists s'. s2s(s) = s2s(s')) \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{true}$. So definitely $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$.

- **BPUBPREF**

In this case we have that $\widehat{b}_2 = \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}[:n])$ for some \widehat{e} and n . We also know that $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}[:n]) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow (\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e}[:n] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s))$ By induction we have $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ and so

$$\begin{aligned} (\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s)) &\Rightarrow (\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[:n] = s2s(s)[:n]) \Rightarrow \\ &(\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e}[:n] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s)) \Rightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BPUBSUFF**

This case is analogous to the previous one.

- **BPUBCONC**

In this case we have $\widehat{b}_2 = \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2)$ for some \widehat{e}_1 and \widehat{e}_2 . We know that $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = (\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s))$ and by induction we have that both $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_1) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ and $\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_2) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. So now we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_1) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_2) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}) &\Rightarrow (\exists s_1. \llbracket \widehat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s_1) \wedge \exists s_2. \llbracket \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s_2)) \Rightarrow \\ (\exists s_1, s_2. \llbracket \widehat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} ++ \llbracket \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &= s2s(s_1) ++ s2s(s_2)) \Rightarrow (\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s)) \Rightarrow \\ \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Rightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BPUBINTRO**

For some $\widetilde{c\hat{g}}, \widetilde{b}, \widetilde{v}$ and \widetilde{e} we know $(\widetilde{c\hat{g}}, \widetilde{b}) \in I$, $\widehat{b}_2 = \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{c\hat{g}}2s((\widetilde{c\hat{g}})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}]))$ and $\{\widetilde{v}\} = \mathbf{VARS}(\widetilde{c\hat{g}})$. By induction we also have $\forall e \in \widetilde{e}. \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(e) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ and $\llbracket (\widetilde{b})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. Observe then that according to Definition 4.2.C for any $e \in \widetilde{e}$ there exists a s_e such that $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = s2s(s_e) = \llbracket s_e \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. Let \widetilde{s}_e denote the list of such strings that correspond to the list \widetilde{e} , then clearly $\llbracket \widetilde{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \widetilde{s}_e \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$. Using Theorem 4.3.C and 4.2.G we can now derive $\llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\widetilde{b})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Rightarrow \llbracket \widetilde{b} \rrbracket_{st[\widetilde{v}:=\llbracket \widetilde{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}]}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \widetilde{b} \rrbracket_{st[\widetilde{v}:=\llbracket \widetilde{s}_e \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}]}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{c\hat{g}}2s(\widetilde{c\hat{g}})) \rrbracket_{st[\widetilde{v}:=\llbracket \widetilde{s}_e \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}]}^{cs} \Rightarrow \\ \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{c\hat{g}}2s(\widetilde{c\hat{g}})) \rrbracket_{st[\widetilde{v}:=\llbracket \widetilde{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}]}^{cs} &\Rightarrow \llbracket \mathbf{pub}(\widehat{c\hat{g}}2s((\widetilde{c\hat{g}})[\widetilde{e}/\widetilde{v}])) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

- **BPUBELIM**

This case is analogous to the previous one. □

4.2.2 A semantics for invariants

Theorem 4.2.D. *The semantics of a cryptogram pattern only depends on the crypto strings to which the crypto store maps the variables that occur in that expression:*

$$\forall \widetilde{c\hat{g}}, cs_1, cs_2, st_1, st_2. (\forall v \in \mathbf{VARS}(\widetilde{c\hat{g}}). st_1(v) = st_2(v)) \Rightarrow (\llbracket \widetilde{c\hat{g}} \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \widetilde{c\hat{g}} \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2})$$

Proof. The proof goes by case analysis of $\widetilde{c\hat{g}}$. So for each case we need to prove for some cs_1, cs_2, st_1 and st_2 that $\llbracket \widetilde{c\hat{g}} \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \widetilde{c\hat{g}} \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$ given $\forall v \in \mathbf{VARS}(\widetilde{c\hat{g}}). st_1(v) = st_2(v)$. Using Definition 3.1.B we have:

- $\widetilde{c\hat{g}} = \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(n_{id}, n_{\#})$

$$\llbracket \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) = \llbracket \widehat{\mathbf{key}}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$$

- $\widetilde{c\hat{g}} = \widehat{\mathbf{hmac}}(n_{id}, n_{\#}, v_p)$

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}})_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} &= \text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, ([\text{v}_{\text{p}}]_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1})(\psi_0)) = \text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, (\text{st}_1(\text{v}_{\text{p}}))(\psi_0)) = \\ & \text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, (\text{st}_2(\text{v}_{\text{p}}))(\psi_0)) = \text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, ([\text{v}_{\text{p}}]_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2})(\psi_0)) = \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}})_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.2.E. *Under specific conditions, the equality of the semantics of a cryptogram pattern in two crypto stores is equivalent to the equality of all corresponding crypto strings to which the variables of the pattern map:*

$$\forall \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}, \text{cs}_1, \text{cs}_2, \text{st}_1, \text{st}_2. (\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \exists \mathbf{s}. \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s})) \wedge (\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \exists \mathbf{s}. \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s})) \Rightarrow \\ \left(\llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} = \llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \Leftrightarrow \forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v}) \right)$$

Proof. For some $\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}, \text{cs}_1, \text{cs}_2, \text{st}_1$ and st_2 we assume that $\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \exists \mathbf{s}. \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s})$ and $\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \exists \mathbf{s}. \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s})$. Theorem 4.2.D gives us $\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v}) \Rightarrow \llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} = \llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$ and we still must show $\llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} = \llbracket \tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \Rightarrow \forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v})$. We proceed with a case analysis of $\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}$:

- $\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} = \widehat{\text{key}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#})$

Now $\text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}) = \emptyset$ and so $\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v})$ is trivially true.

- $\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g} = \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}})$

Now $\text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{c}}\text{g}) = \{\text{v}_{\text{p}}\}$ and we must show that $\text{st}_1(\text{v}_{\text{p}}) = \text{st}_2(\text{v}_{\text{p}})$ assuming $\llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$. From the assumptions we know there must exist some \mathbf{s}_1 and \mathbf{s}_2 such that $\text{st}_1(\text{v}_{\text{p}}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s}_1)$ and $\text{st}_2(\text{v}_{\text{p}}) = \text{s2s}(\mathbf{s}_2)$ so it is sufficient to show $\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{s}_2$ and we do this as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \text{v}_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \right) \Rightarrow \\ \left(\text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, ([\text{v}_{\text{p}}]_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1})(\psi_0)) = \text{hmac}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, ([\text{v}_{\text{p}}]_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2})(\psi_0)) \right) \Rightarrow (\text{st}_1(\text{v}_{\text{p}}))(\psi_0) = (\text{st}_2(\text{v}_{\text{p}}))(\psi_0) \Rightarrow \\ (\text{s2s}(\mathbf{s}_1))(\psi_0) = (\text{s2s}(\mathbf{s}_2))(\psi_0) \Rightarrow \mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{s}_2 \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.2.F. *The semantics of a boolean pattern only depends on the crypto strings to which the crypto store maps the variables that occur in that expression:*

$$\forall \tilde{\text{b}}, \text{cs}_1, \text{cs}_2, \text{st}_1, \text{st}_2. \left(\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{b}}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v}) \right) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \tilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \tilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \right)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on $\tilde{\text{b}}$. So for each case we need to prove for some $\text{cs}_1, \text{cs}_2, \text{st}_1$ and st_2 that $\llbracket \tilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \tilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$ given $\forall \mathbf{v} \in \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{b}}). \text{st}_1(\mathbf{v}) = \text{st}_2(\mathbf{v})$. Using Definition 3.1.H we have:

- $\tilde{\text{b}} = \text{true}$

$$\llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \text{true} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$$

- $\tilde{\text{b}} = \text{false}$

$$\llbracket \text{false} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \text{false} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \text{false} \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$$

- $\tilde{\text{b}} = \neg(\hat{\text{b}}')$

According to Definition 3.1.J $\hat{\text{b}}' \in \tilde{\text{B}}$ and since $\text{VARS}(\hat{\text{b}}') \subseteq \text{VARS}(\tilde{\text{b}})$ we can use the induction hypothesis to get $\llbracket \hat{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$. We can now show $\llbracket \neg(\hat{\text{b}}') \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \neg \llbracket \hat{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}_1}^{\text{CS}_1} \Leftrightarrow \neg \llbracket \hat{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \neg(\hat{\text{b}}') \rrbracket_{\text{st}_2}^{\text{CS}_2}$.

- $\boxed{\tilde{b} = \hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2}$

According to Definition 3.1.J we have that $\hat{b}_1 \in \tilde{B}$ and $\hat{b}_2 \in \tilde{B}$. Since also $\text{VAR}(\hat{b}_1) \subseteq \text{VAR}(\tilde{b})$ and $\text{VAR}(\hat{b}_2) \subseteq \text{VAR}(\tilde{b})$ we can use the induction hypothesis to get $\llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$ and $\llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$. So now we derive $\llbracket \hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2} \wedge \llbracket \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{b}_1 \wedge \hat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$.

- $\boxed{\tilde{b} = (\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2)}$

According to Definition 3.1.J we have that $\hat{e}_1 \in \mathbf{E}$ and $\hat{e}_2 \in \mathbf{E}$. Since also $\text{VAR}(\hat{e}_1) \subseteq \text{VAR}(\tilde{b})$ and $\text{VAR}(\hat{e}_2) \subseteq \text{VAR}(\tilde{b})$ we apply Theorem 4.2.B to get $\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_1} = \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_2} = \llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$ and $\llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$. So now we get $\llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow (\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1}) \Leftrightarrow (\llbracket \hat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2} = \llbracket \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}) \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$.

- $\boxed{\tilde{b} = (|\hat{e}| = n)}$

According to Definition 3.1.J $\hat{e} \in \mathbf{E}$ and since also $\text{VAR}(\hat{e}) \subseteq \text{VAR}(\tilde{b})$ we can apply Theorem 4.2.B to get $\llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_1} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_2} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$. Now we derive $\llbracket |\hat{e}| = n \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1} \Leftrightarrow (|\llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_1}^{cs_1}| = n) \Leftrightarrow (|\llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}| = n) \Leftrightarrow \llbracket |\hat{e}| = n \rrbracket_{st_2}^{cs_2}$.

- $\boxed{\tilde{b} = \text{pub}(\hat{e})}$

These cases cannot occur according to Definition 3.1.J. □

Definition 4.2.E. *The semantics of an invariant:*

$$\forall I. \llbracket I \rrbracket \equiv \left\{ cg \mid \exists (\tilde{cg}, \tilde{b}) \in I, \exists cs, st. cg = \llbracket \tilde{cg} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \tilde{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge (\forall v \in \text{VAR}(\tilde{cg}). \exists s. st(v) = s2s(s)) \right\}$$

Definition 4.2.F. *A cryptogram mapping that is compatible with an invariant:*

$$\forall I, cs. I \propto cs \equiv \forall cg. cg \in \llbracket I \rrbracket \Leftrightarrow \exists s. cs(cg) = s2s(s)$$

Theorem 4.2.G. *For any cryptogram and boolean pattern pair in an invariant, under specific conditions, publicness of the cryptogram pattern and validity of the boolean pattern are interchangeable:*

$$\forall I, \tilde{cg}, \tilde{b}, cs, st. (\tilde{cg}, \tilde{b}) \in I \wedge I \propto cs \wedge (\forall v \in \text{VAR}(\tilde{cg}). \exists s. st(v) = s2s(s)) \Rightarrow \left(\llbracket \text{pub}(\tilde{cg}2s(\tilde{cg})) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \tilde{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right)$$

Proof. We assume $(\tilde{cg}, \tilde{b}) \in I, I \propto cs$ and $\forall v \in \text{VAR}(\tilde{cg}). \exists s. st(v) = s2s(s)$ for some $I, \tilde{cg}, \tilde{b}, cs$ and st . Now we need to show $\llbracket \text{pub}(\tilde{cg}2s(\tilde{cg})) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \tilde{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$, but first we establish the following equivalences:

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \text{pub}(\tilde{cg}2s(\tilde{cg})) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} && \Leftrightarrow \\ & \exists s. cs(\tilde{cg}) = s2s(s) && \Leftrightarrow \text{(Definition 4.2.C)} \\ & \llbracket \tilde{cg} \rrbracket_{st} \in \llbracket I \rrbracket && \Leftrightarrow \text{(Definition 4.2.F and assumption)} \\ & \left(\begin{array}{l} \exists (\tilde{cg}', \tilde{b}') \in I, \exists cs', st'. \llbracket \tilde{cg} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket \tilde{cg}' \rrbracket_{st'}^{cs'} \wedge \llbracket \tilde{b}' \rrbracket_{st'}^{cs'} \wedge \\ (\forall v \in \text{VAR}(\tilde{cg}). \exists s. st'(v) = s2s(s)) \end{array} \right) && \text{(Definition 4.2.E)} \end{aligned}$$

Now we first show $\llbracket \text{pub}(\tilde{cg}2s(\tilde{cg})) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Rightarrow \llbracket \tilde{b} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \text{pub}(\widehat{\text{cg}}2\text{s}(\widetilde{\text{cg}})) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} && \Rightarrow \\
& \left(\exists (\widetilde{\text{cg}}', \widetilde{\text{b}}') \in \mathbf{I}, \exists \text{cs}', \text{st}'. \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \right. && \Rightarrow \text{ (Earlier derived)} \\
& \quad \left. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{cg}}). \exists s. \text{st}'(v) = \text{s2s}(s)) \right) && \\
& \left(\exists \text{cs}', \text{st}'. \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \right. && \Rightarrow \text{ (Definition 3.1.K)} \\
& \quad \left. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{cg}}). \exists s. \text{st}'(v) = \text{s2s}(s)) \right) && \\
& \exists \text{cs}', \text{st}'. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{cg}}). \text{st}(v) = \text{st}'(v)) \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} && \Rightarrow \text{ (Theorem 4.2.E)} \\
& \exists \text{cs}', \text{st}'. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{b}}). \text{st}(v) = \text{st}'(v)) \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} && \Rightarrow \text{ (Definition 3.1.K)} \\
& \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} && \Rightarrow \text{ (Theorem 4.2.F)}
\end{aligned}$$

Going in the other direction we now show $\llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Rightarrow \llbracket \text{pub}(\widehat{\text{cg}}2\text{s}(\widetilde{\text{cg}})) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} && \Rightarrow \\
& \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{cg}}). \exists s. \text{st}(v) = \text{s2s}(s)) && \Rightarrow \text{ (Rewriting and assumption)} \\
& \left(\exists (\widetilde{\text{cg}}', \widetilde{\text{b}}') \in \mathbf{I}, \exists \text{cs}', \text{st}'. \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}'} \wedge \right. && \Rightarrow \text{ (Existential quantification)} \\
& \quad \left. (\forall v \in \text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{cg}}). \exists s. \text{st}'(v) = \text{s2s}(s)) \right) && \\
& \llbracket \text{pub}(\widehat{\text{cg}}2\text{s}(\widetilde{\text{cg}})) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} && \Rightarrow \text{ (Earlier derived)}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.2.H. *Cryptograms that are a member of the semantics of an attacker approved invariant:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I}) \Rightarrow (\forall n_{\#}. \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket) \wedge (\forall n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}}. \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket \Rightarrow \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket)$$

Proof. For some \mathbf{I} such that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I})$ we need to prove for some $n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}$ and s_{p} that:

- $\text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket$

Using Definition 4.2.E and 3.2.E, and after choosing $(\widehat{\text{key}}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}), \text{true})$ it is sufficient to show $\exists \text{cs}, \text{st}. \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) = \llbracket \widehat{\text{key}}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$. But this holds for any choice for cs and st , so we are done.

- $\text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket \Rightarrow \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket$

If we assume $\text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket$ we know according to Definition 4.2.E that there exists some $\widetilde{\text{cg}}, \widetilde{\text{b}}_1, \text{cs}$ and st such that $(\widetilde{\text{cg}}, \widetilde{\text{b}}_1) \in \mathbf{I}$, $\text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{cg}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}$. This implies that $\widetilde{\text{cg}} = \widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})$ and $\text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{b}}_1) = \emptyset$ and from Definition 3.2.E we can conclude that then also $(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_{\text{p}}), \widetilde{\text{b}}_2) \in \mathbf{I}$ for some $\widetilde{\text{b}}_2$ and v_{p} such that $\text{VARS}(\widetilde{\text{b}}_2) \subseteq \{v_{\text{p}}\}$ and $\mathbf{I} \cdot \widetilde{\text{b}}_1 \vdash \widetilde{\text{b}}_2$. We must now show for any s_{p} that $\text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket$. According to Definition 4.2.E it is sufficient to prove $\llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}} = \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}})$, $\llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}}$ and $\exists s. \text{st}'(v_{\text{p}}) = \text{s2s}(s_{\text{p}})$ for $\text{st}' = \text{st}[v_{\text{p}} := \text{s2s}(s_{\text{p}})]$. Clearly he have that $\text{st}'(v_{\text{p}}) = \text{s2s}(s_{\text{p}})$ and using Theorem 4.2.C and 4.2.F that $\llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widetilde{\text{b}}_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}}$. Finally, using Definition 4.2.C we can derive:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, v_{\text{p}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}} = \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, (\llbracket v_{\text{p}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}'}^{\text{cs}})(\psi_0)) = \\
& \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, (\text{s2s}(s_{\text{p}}))(\psi_0)) = \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_{\text{p}})
\end{aligned}$$

□

4.3 Substitution and semantics of assertions

Definition 4.3.A. Multiple substitution defined as general as possible for reusability (syntactic sugar):

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \quad (x)[\varepsilon/\varepsilon] &\equiv x \\ \forall x, y, \bar{y}, z, \bar{z}. \quad (x)[z :: \bar{z}/y :: \bar{y}] &\equiv (((x)[z/y]))[\bar{z}/\bar{y}] \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3.A. The semantics of a program expression is invariant under a substitution and a corresponding crypto store update:

$$\forall cs, \underline{st}, e, v, \hat{e}. \quad \llbracket (e)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on e and throughout this proof Definition 2.1.G and Definition 4.2.A are implicitly used. For each case need to prove $\llbracket (e)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ for some cs, \underline{st}, v and \hat{e} :

- $e = s$

Now $\llbracket (s)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = s2s(s) = \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ and we are done.

- $e = v'$ We can distinguish two cases here:

- $v = v'$ $\llbracket (v')[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \left(\underline{st} \left[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right] \right) (v) = \left(\underline{st} \left[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right] \right) (v') = \llbracket v' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$

- $v \neq v'$ $\llbracket (v')[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket v' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \underline{st}(v') = \left(\underline{st} \left[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right] \right) (v') = \llbracket v' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$

- $e = e'[: n]$

By induction we know that $\llbracket (e')[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ and so we have:

$$\llbracket (e'[: n])[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket (e')[\hat{e}/v][: n] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket (e')[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}[: n] = \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}[: n] = \llbracket e'[: n] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$$

- $e = e'[n :]$

Analogous to previous case

- $e = e_1 ++ e_2$

By induction we know $\llbracket (e_1)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ and $\llbracket (e_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (e_1 ++ e_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} &= \llbracket (e_1)[\hat{e}/v] ++ (e_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket (e_1)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} ++ \llbracket (e_2)[\hat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \\ &= \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} ++ \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} = \llbracket e_1 ++ e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.3.B. The semantics of a string or cryptogram expression is invariant under a substitution and a similar crypto store update:

$$\forall \underline{st}, v', \hat{e}'. \quad \begin{cases} \forall \hat{e}. \llbracket (\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v' := \llbracket \hat{e}' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} \wedge \\ \forall \hat{c}g. \llbracket (\hat{c}g)[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{c}g \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v' := \llbracket \hat{e}' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} \end{cases}$$

Proof. To allow for induction in this proof we generalize the theorem to a suitable form:

$$\forall n, \underline{st}, v', \hat{e}'. \quad \begin{cases} \forall \hat{e}. \|\hat{e}\| \leq n \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v' := \llbracket \hat{e}' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} \wedge \\ \forall \hat{c}g. \|\hat{c}g\| \leq n \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{c}g)[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{c}g \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v' := \llbracket \hat{e}' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs} \end{cases}$$

We proceed by induction on n and leverage Definition 3.1.E, 4.2.B and 3.1.D throughout this proof. We prove for some \underline{st}, v' and \hat{e}' that $\forall \hat{e}. \|\hat{e}\| \leq n \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{e})[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} = \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}[v' := \llbracket \hat{e}' \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}]}^{cs}$ and $\forall \hat{c}g. \|\hat{c}g\| \leq n \Rightarrow \llbracket (\hat{c}g)[\hat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} =$

$\llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$:

• $\widehat{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{0}$

$$- \quad \boxed{\|\widehat{e}\| \leq \mathbf{0} \Rightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{e})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \widehat{e}']}$$

$\|\widehat{e}\| \leq \mathbf{0}$ means $\widehat{e} = \mathbf{e}$ for some \mathbf{e} . Applying Theorem 4.3.A finishes the proof in this case.

$$- \quad \boxed{\|\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\| \leq \mathbf{0} \Rightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \widehat{e}']}$$

$\|\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\| \leq \mathbf{0}$ means $\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} = \widehat{\text{key}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#})$ for some \mathbf{n}_{id} and $\mathbf{n}_{\#}$ we now have:

$$\llbracket (\widehat{\text{key}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}))[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \text{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}) = \llbracket \widehat{\text{key}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \widehat{e}']$$

• $\widehat{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1}$

By induction we know that $\llbracket (\widehat{e}'')[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{e}'' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$ for all \widehat{e}'' with $\|\widehat{e}''\| \leq \mathbf{n}'$ and we also know that $\llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}'')[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}'' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$ for all $\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}''$ with $\|\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}''\| \leq \mathbf{n}'$. We now still need to prove the following cases:

$$- \quad \boxed{\|\widehat{e}\| = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1} \Rightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{e})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]}$$

$\|\widehat{e}\| = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1}$ means that $\widehat{e} = \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\mathbf{2s}(\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})$ for some $\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}$, $\widehat{e} = \widehat{e}'[n :]$ for some \widehat{e}' and n , $\widehat{e} = \widehat{e}'[n :]$ for some \widehat{e}' and n or $\widehat{e} = \widehat{e}_1 ++ \widehat{e}_2$ for some \widehat{e}_1 and \widehat{e}_2 . We only explicitly discuss the case in which $\widehat{e} = \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\mathbf{2s}(\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})$ for some $\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}$. The other cases follow similarly from the induction hypothesis. By induction we know in the selected case $\llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\mathbf{2s}(\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}))[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} &= \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\mathbf{2s}(\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \text{cs}(\llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}) = \text{cs}(\llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]) \\ &= \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\mathbf{2s}(\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}] \end{aligned}$$

$$- \quad \boxed{\|\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\| = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1} \Rightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]}$$

$\|\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}}\| = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1}$ means that $\widehat{\text{c}}\widehat{\text{g}} = \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \widehat{e}_p)$ for some \mathbf{n}_{id} , $\mathbf{n}_{\#}$ and \widehat{e}_p . By induction we now know $\llbracket (\widehat{e}_p)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \llbracket \widehat{e}_p \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$ and we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\widehat{\text{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \widehat{e}_p))[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} &= \llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, (\widehat{e}_p)[\widehat{e}'/v']) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} = \\ \text{hmac}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, (\llbracket (\widehat{e}_p)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}})(\psi_0)) &= \text{hmac}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, (\llbracket \widehat{e}_p \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}])(\psi_0)) = \\ \llbracket \widehat{\text{hmac}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#}, \widehat{e}_p) \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}] & \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.3.C. *The semantics of a boolean expression under a substitution and a crypto store state update:*

$$\forall \text{cs}, \text{st}, \widehat{\mathbf{b}}, v', \widehat{e}'. \quad \llbracket (\widehat{\mathbf{b}})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \widehat{\mathbf{b}} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on $\widehat{\mathbf{b}}$ for some cs , st , v' and \widehat{e}' :

• $\widehat{\mathbf{b}} = \text{true}$ $\widehat{\mathbf{b}} = \text{false}$ These cases are trivial.

• $\widehat{\mathbf{b}} = \neg(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}')$ Applying the induction hypothesis:

$$\llbracket (\neg(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}'))[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \neg(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}')[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \neg \llbracket (\widehat{\mathbf{b}}')[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} \Leftrightarrow \neg \llbracket \widehat{\mathbf{b}}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}] \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \neg(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}') \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}[v' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}]$$

• $\widehat{\mathbf{b}} = \widehat{\mathbf{b}}_1 \wedge \widehat{\mathbf{b}}_2$ Applying the induction hypothesis:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\widehat{b}_1 \wedge \widehat{b}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Leftrightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{b}_1)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \wedge (\widehat{b}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \left(\llbracket (\widehat{b}_1)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket (\widehat{b}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ &\left(\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \right) \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \end{aligned}$$

- $\widehat{b} = (\widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_2)$ Applying Theorem 4.3.B:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Leftrightarrow \llbracket (\widehat{e}_1)[\widehat{e}'/v'] = (\widehat{e}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \left(\llbracket (\widehat{e}_1)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} = \llbracket (\widehat{e}_2)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ &\left(\llbracket \widehat{e}_1 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] = \llbracket \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \right) \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \widehat{e}_1 = \widehat{e}_2 \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \end{aligned}$$

- $\widehat{b} = (|\widehat{e}| = n)$ Applying Theorem 4.3.B:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (|\widehat{e}| = n)[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Leftrightarrow \llbracket (|\widehat{e}|)[\widehat{e}'/v'] = n \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \left(|\llbracket (\widehat{e})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}| = n \right) \Leftrightarrow \left(|\llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}]| = n \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ &\llbracket |\widehat{e}| = n \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \end{aligned}$$

- $\widehat{b} = \text{pub}(\widehat{e})$ We have using Theorem 4.3.B:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket (\text{pub}(\widehat{e}))[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} &\Leftrightarrow \llbracket \text{pub}(\widehat{e})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st}^{cs} \Leftrightarrow \left(\exists s. \llbracket (\widehat{e})[\widehat{e}'/v'] \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s) \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ &\left(\exists s. \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{st}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] = s2s(s) \right) \Leftrightarrow \llbracket \text{pub}(\widehat{e}) \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}[\widehat{v}' := \llbracket \widehat{e}' \rrbracket_{st}^{cs}] \end{aligned}$$

□

5 The weakest precondition, crypto threads and crypto worlds

5.1 Cryptogram records

5.1.1 Records of generated cryptograms

Definition 5.1.A. A record of generated cryptograms: $r \in \mathbf{R}$

$$r ::= [\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}] \quad (\bar{c}g_{\square}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} \in \mathbf{CG}^*, \bar{s} \in \mathbf{S}^*, |\bar{c}g_{\square}| = |\bar{s}|)$$

$$\forall \bar{c}g_{\square}, \bar{s}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}. \quad \mathbf{strs}([\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}]) \equiv \bar{s}$$

$$\forall \bar{c}g_{\square}, \bar{s}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}. \quad \mathbf{cgs}([\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}]) \equiv \bar{c}g_{\square} ++ \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}$$

Definition 5.1.B. Composing cryptogram records: $_+ : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$

$$\forall \bar{c}g_{\square 1}, \bar{c}g_{\square 2}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 1}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 2}, \bar{s}_1, \bar{s}_2. \quad [\bar{c}g_{\square 1} \cdot \bar{s}_1 \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 1}] ++ [\bar{c}g_{\square 2} \cdot \bar{s}_2 \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 2}]$$

$$\equiv$$

$$[(\bar{c}g_{\square 1} ++ \bar{c}g_{\square 2}) \cdot (\bar{s}_1 ++ \bar{s}_2) \cdot (\bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 1} ++ \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare 2})]$$

Theorem 5.1.A. Associativity of composing cryptogram records:

$$\forall r_1, r_2, r_3. \quad (r_1 ++ r_2) ++ r_3 = r_1 ++ (r_2 ++ r_3)$$

Proof. This follows from Definition 5.1.B. □

Definition 5.1.C. A record maps cryptograms to crypto strings: $\bar{\nabla} : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{CG} \rightarrow \underline{\mathbf{S}}$ and $\bar{\nabla}^n : \mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{N} \times \mathbf{CG} \rightarrow \underline{\mathbf{S}}$

$$\forall cg, \bar{c}g_{\square}, s, \bar{s}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}, cg'. \quad [cg :: \bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot s :: \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}] \bar{\nabla} cg' \equiv \begin{cases} s2s(s) & (\text{if } cg = cg') \\ [\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}] \bar{\nabla} cg' & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

$$\forall \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}, cg'. \quad [[] \cdot [] \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}] \bar{\nabla} cg' \equiv \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} \bar{\nabla}^0 cg'$$

$$\forall cg, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}, n, cg'. \quad cg :: \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} \bar{\nabla}^n cg' \equiv \begin{cases} \lambda \psi. \psi[n] & (\text{if } cg = cg') \\ \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} \bar{\nabla}^{n+1} cg' & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

$$\forall n, cg'. \quad [] \bar{\nabla}^n cg' \equiv s2s(\varepsilon)$$

5.1.2 Safe records

Definition 5.1.D. A cryptogram record is safe for an invariant \mathbf{I} when:

$$\forall \bar{c}g_{\square}, \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}, \bar{s}. \quad \mathbf{SAFE}_1([\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}])$$

$$\equiv$$

$$(\forall cg. cg \in \{\{\bar{c}g_{\square}\}\} \Rightarrow cg \in \{\{\mathbf{I}\}\}) \wedge (\forall cg. cg \in \{\{\bar{c}g_{\blacksquare}\}\} \Rightarrow cg \notin \{\{\mathbf{I}\}\}) \wedge$$

$$(\forall s \in \{\{\bar{s}\}\}. |s| = \mathbf{N}_s) \wedge (\forall n_1, n_2. n_1 \neq n_2 \wedge n_1 < |\bar{s}| \wedge n_2 < |\bar{s}| \Rightarrow \bar{s}[n_1] \neq \bar{s}[n_2]) \wedge$$

$$(\forall n_1, n_2, \bar{c}g. \bar{c}g = \bar{c}g_{\square} ++ \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} \wedge n_1 \neq n_2 \wedge n_1 < |\bar{c}g| \wedge n_2 < |\bar{c}g| \Rightarrow \bar{c}g[n_1] \neq \bar{c}g[n_2])$$

Theorem 5.1.B. *Property of a composed safe cryptogram record:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, \gamma, \bar{c}_{g_{\square 1}}, \bar{c}_{g_{\square 2}}, \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 1}}, \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 2}}, \bar{s}_1, \bar{s}_2. \text{SAFE}_1([\bar{c}_{g_{\square 1}} \cdot \bar{s}_1 \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 1}}] ++ [\bar{c}_{g_{\square 2}} \cdot \bar{s}_2 \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 2}}]) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_1([\bar{c}_{g_{\square 1}} \cdot \bar{s}_1 \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 1}}]) \wedge \text{SAFE}_1([\bar{c}_{g_{\square 2}} \cdot \bar{s}_2 \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare 2}}])$$

Proof. This follows from Definition 5.1.B and 5.1.D. \square

Theorem 5.1.C. *Mapping determined by a composed safe cryptogram record:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, r_1, r_2, \text{cg}. \text{SAFE}_1(r_1 ++ r_2) \wedge \text{cg} \in \{\{\text{cgs}(r_1)\}\} \Rightarrow r_1 \blacktriangledown \text{cg} = (r_1 ++ r_2) \blacktriangledown \text{cg}$$

Proof. This follows from Definition 5.1.C, 5.1.B and 5.1.D. \square

5.1.3 Cryptogram records and cryptogram mappings

Definition 5.1.E. *All cryptogram mappings for a cryptogram record: $\odot_{\square}(-) \in \text{CG}^* \times \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{2}^{\text{CS}}$:*

$$\forall \bar{c}_{g}, r. \odot_{\bar{c}_{g}}(r) \equiv \left\{ \text{cs} \left| \begin{array}{l} \forall \text{cg} \in \{\{\text{cgs}(r)\}\}. \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = r \blacktriangledown \text{cg} \wedge \\ \forall \text{cg}. \text{cg} \in \bar{c}_{g} \Rightarrow \exists \underline{s}. \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = \underline{s} \text{2s}(\underline{s}) \wedge \\ \forall \text{cg}. \text{cg} \notin \bar{c}_{g} \Rightarrow \exists \underline{n}. \underline{n} < N_{\psi} \wedge \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = \lambda \psi. \psi[\underline{n}] \end{array} \right. \right\}$$

Theorem 5.1.D. *Properties of all cryptogram mappings for an invariant and record:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, r. (\forall \text{cg}. \text{cg} \in \{\{\text{cgs}(r)\}\} \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\blacksquare}(\mathbf{I})(r). \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}) \wedge (\forall \text{cs}. \text{cs} \in \odot_{\blacksquare}(\mathbf{I})(r) \Rightarrow \mathbf{I} \propto \text{cs}) \wedge \\ (\forall \text{cg}. \exists \underline{s}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\blacksquare}(\mathbf{I})(r). \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = \underline{s} \Rightarrow \text{cg} \in \{\{\text{cgs}(r)\}\})$$

Proof. This follows directly from Definition 4.2.F and 5.1.E. \square

Theorem 5.1.E. *The crypto strings that a cryptogram mapping for a safe record maps to:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, \text{cs}, \bar{c}_{g_{\square}}, \bar{s}, \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare}}, \underline{n}, \text{cg}. \text{SAFE}_1([\bar{c}_{g_{\square}} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare}}]) \wedge \text{cs} \in \odot_{\blacksquare}([\bar{c}_{g_{\square}} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare}}]) \Rightarrow \\ (\underline{n} < |\bar{c}_{g_{\square}}| \Rightarrow \text{cs}(\bar{c}_{g_{\square}}[\underline{n}]) = \text{2s}(\bar{s}[\underline{n}])) \wedge (\underline{n} < |\bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare}}| \Rightarrow \text{cs}(\bar{c}_{g_{\blacksquare}}[\underline{n}]) = \lambda \psi. \psi[\underline{n}])$$

Proof. This follows from Definition 5.1.C, 5.1.D and 5.1.E. \square

5.2 Safe commands

5.2.1 The sampling number of a command

Definition 5.2.A. *The sampling number of a (non-forking) command: $\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(-) : \mathbf{N}^{\text{C}}$*

$$\forall c. \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & (\text{if } c = v \stackrel{\mathcal{S}}{\leftarrow} N_s) \\ \max(\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1), \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2)) & (\text{if } c = q ? c_1 : c_2) \\ \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) & (\text{if } c = c_1 ; c_2) \\ 0 & (\text{otherwise}) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 5.2.A. *Sampling numbers have a associativity property for a sequential composition:*

$$\forall c_1, c_2, c_3. \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1 ; (c_2 ; c_3)) = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}((c_1 ; c_2) ; c_3)$$

Proof. For some c_1, c_2 and c_3 we have using Definition 5.2.A:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1 ; (c_2 ; c_3)) &= \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2 ; c_3) = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_3) = \\ &= \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1 ; c_2) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_3) = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}((c_1 ; c_2) ; c_3) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 5.2.B. *The deduction rules for Hoare triples establish the following property for sampling numbers:*

$$\forall I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#_1}, n_{\#_2}, c, \widehat{b}_1, \widehat{b}_2. I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\} \Rightarrow n_{\#_1} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on the derivation of $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#_1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$ for some $I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#_1}, n_{\#_2}, c, \widehat{b}_1$ and \widehat{b}_2 :

- HSKIP HSTUCK HFAIL HSEND HRECEIVE HASSIGN HHMAC

Now we know $n_{\#_1} = n_{\#_2}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) = \mathbf{0}$. So we immediately get $n_{\#_1} = \mathbf{0} + n_{\#_2} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$.

- HSAMPLE

Now we know $n_{\#_1} = n_{\#_2} + \mathbf{1}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) = \mathbf{1}$. So we can easily derive $n_{\#_1} = \mathbf{1} + n_{\#_2} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$.

- HIFLEN HIFEQ

We now have that $c = q ? c_1 : c_2$ for some q, c_1 and c_2 . By induction we get for some $n_{\#_a}$ and $n_{\#_b}$ that $n_{\#_a} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n_{\#_2}$, $n_{\#_b} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#_2}$ and $n_{\#_1} = \max(n_{\#_a}, n_{\#_b})$. So now we can derive $n_{\#_1} = \max(n_{\#_a}, n_{\#_b}) = \max(\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n_{\#_2}, \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#_2}) = \max(\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1), \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2)) + n_{\#_2} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$.

- HSEQ

We now have that $c = c_1 ; c_2$ for some c_1 and c_2 . By induction we get for some $n_{\#}$ that $n_{\#_1} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n_{\#}$ and $n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#_2}$. From Definition 5.2.A we know that $\mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2)$. So now we can derive $n_{\#_1} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#_2} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$.

- HCONSEQ HCONST

By induction we immediately get $n_{\#_1} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#_2}$.

□

5.2.2 The weakest precondition

Definition 5.2.B. *The semantics as a set of crypto stores of boolean expressions for a cryptogram record:*

$$\forall I, r, \widehat{b}. \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \equiv \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right\}$$

Definition 5.2.C. *The weakest precondition for a complete cryptogram record, invariant, identity number, command, final sampling number and postcondition is given by $\text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(-, -, -) : (\underline{ST}^*)^{\text{R} \times \text{Inv} \times \text{N} \times \text{C} \times \text{N} \times \underline{ST}^*}$. For some $I, r, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}$ and \underline{st} we have:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall e. \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}) &\equiv \underline{st} \\ \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{stuck}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}) &\equiv \underline{ST} \\ \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{fail}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}) &\equiv \emptyset \\ \forall e. \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n_{\#}, \underline{st}) &\equiv \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{st} \in \underline{st} \right\} \\ \forall v. \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{rcv}(v), n_{\#}, \underline{st}) &\equiv \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \underline{st} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\forall v, e. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (v := e, n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \left\{ \dot{st} \mid \dot{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\dot{st}}] \in \dot{st} \right\} \\
\forall v. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \left\{ \dot{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#)] \in \dot{st} \right\} \\
\forall v, v_k, v_p. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \left\{ \dot{st} \mid \exists s_p. \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_I^r (v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) \vee \text{H_KEY}_I^r (v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) \right) \right\} \\
\forall v, s_k, s_p, \dot{st}. \quad & \text{H_ATT}_I^r (v, s_k, s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \left(\nexists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\square]}(r). s_k = cs(\text{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \right) \wedge \exists s_k. s_k = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \dot{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st} \\
\forall v, s_k, s_p, \dot{st}. \quad & \text{H_KEY}_I^r (v, s_k, s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\square]}(r). s_k = cs(\text{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \\
& \left(\text{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st} \right) \\
\forall e, n, c_1, c_2. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \left\{ \dot{st} \mid (|e|_{\dot{st}} = n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_1, n\#, \dot{st})) \wedge (|e|_{\dot{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_2, n\#, \dot{st})) \right\} \\
\forall e_1, e_2, c_1, c_2. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \\
& \left\{ \dot{st} \mid \left(\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_1) \right) \wedge \left(\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_2) \right) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\square]}(r). cs(cg) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} \wedge \right. \\
& \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_1, n\#, \dot{st}) \right) \wedge \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) \right) \right\} \\
\forall c. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (\text{fork}(c), n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \emptyset \\
\forall \bar{\alpha}. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (\text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}), n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \dot{st} \\
\forall c_1, c_2. \quad & \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_1 ; c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) && \equiv \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n\#, \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c_2, n\#, \dot{st}))
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.2.C. *The weakest precondition has a monotonicity property for any command:*

$$\forall I, n_{id}, n\#, c, r, \dot{st}_1, \dot{st}_2. \dot{st}_1 \subseteq \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \subseteq \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c, n\#, \dot{st}_2)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on c for some $I, n_{id}, n\#, r, \dot{st}_1$ and \dot{st}_2 . We use the abbreviations $\dot{st}'_1 = \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c, n\#, \dot{st}_1)$ and $\dot{st}'_2 = \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r (c, n\#, \dot{st}_2)$. So given that $\dot{st}_1 \subseteq \dot{st}_2$ we need to prove $\dot{st}'_1 \subseteq \dot{st}'_2$:

- $c = \text{skip}$ $c = \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})$

From $\dot{st}'_1 = \dot{st}_1$ and $\dot{st}'_2 = \dot{st}_2$ we can simply conclude $\dot{st}'_1 \subseteq \dot{st}'_2$ from $\dot{st}_1 \subseteq \dot{st}_2$ and we are done.

- $c = \text{stuck}$

From $\dot{st}'_1 = \text{ST}$ and $\dot{st}'_2 = \text{ST}$ we can directly conclude $\dot{st}'_1 \subseteq \dot{st}'_2$ and we are done.

- $c = \text{fail}$ $c = \text{fork}(c)$

From $\dot{st}'_1 = \emptyset$ and $\dot{st}'_2 = \emptyset$ we can directly conclude $\dot{st}'_1 \subseteq \dot{st}'_2$ and we are done.

- $c = \text{snd}(e)$

We now know $\dot{st}'_1 = \left\{ \dot{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_1 \right\}$ and similarly for \dot{st}'_2 . From $\dot{st}_1 \subseteq \dot{st}_2$ it follows that $\left\{ \dot{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_1 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \dot{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\}$ and thus we conclude $\dot{st}'_1 \subseteq \dot{st}'_2$.

- $c = \text{rcv}(v)$

We now know $\text{st}'_1 = \left\{ \text{st} \mid \forall s. \text{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\}$ and similarly for st'_2 . From $\dot{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_2$ it follows that $\left\{ \text{st} \mid \forall s. \text{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \text{st} \mid \forall s. \text{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{\text{st}}_2 \right\}$ and thus we conclude $\text{st}'_1 \subseteq \text{st}'_2$.

- $c = v := e$

We now know $\text{st}'_1 = \left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{st}[v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\}$ and also that $\text{st}'_2 = \left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{st}[v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}] \in \dot{\text{st}}_2 \right\}$. From $\dot{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_2$ it follows that $\left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{st}[v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{st}[v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}] \in \dot{\text{st}}_2 \right\}$ and thus we conclude $\text{st}'_1 \subseteq \text{st}'_2$.

- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$

We now know $\text{st}'_1 = \left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \text{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\}$ and similarly for st'_2 . From $\dot{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_2$ it follows that

$$\left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \text{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{\text{st}}_1 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \text{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \text{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{\text{st}}_2 \right\}$$

and thus we conclude $\text{st}'_1 \subseteq \text{st}'_2$.

- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)$

We now know that $\text{st}'_1 =$

$$\left\{ \text{st} \mid \exists s_p. \text{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \vee \text{H_KEY}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \right) \right\}$$

and similarly for st'_2 . From $\dot{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_2$ we know for any st that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{H_ATT}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) &\Rightarrow \text{H_ATT}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \\ \text{H_KEY}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) &\Rightarrow \text{H_KEY}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \end{aligned}$$

So it follows that

$$\left\{ \text{st} \mid \exists s_p. \text{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \vee \text{H_KEY}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \right) \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \text{st} \mid \exists s_p. \text{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \vee \text{H_KEY}_1^r(v, \text{st}(v_k), s_p, \text{st}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \right) \right\}$$

and thus we conclude $\text{st}'_1 \subseteq \text{st}'_2$.

- $c = q ? c_1 : c_2$

Using the abbreviations:

$$\begin{aligned} - \dot{\text{st}}_{11} &= \text{WP}_{1.n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n_{\#}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \text{ and } \dot{\text{st}}_{12} = \text{WP}_{1.n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n_{\#}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \\ - \dot{\text{st}}_{21} &= \text{WP}_{1.n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{\text{st}}_1) \text{ and } \dot{\text{st}}_{22} = \text{WP}_{1.n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{\text{st}}_2) \end{aligned}$$

we have by induction that $\dot{\text{st}}_{11} \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_{12}$ and $\dot{\text{st}}_{21} \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_{22}$. We now proceed with case analysis of q :

- $q = (|e| = n)$

We now know $\text{st}'_1 = \left\{ \text{st} \mid (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}| = n \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \dot{\text{st}}_{11}) \wedge (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}| \neq n \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \dot{\text{st}}_{21}) \right\}$ and similarly for st'_2 . From $\dot{\text{st}}_{11} \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_{12}$ and $\dot{\text{st}}_{21} \subseteq \dot{\text{st}}_{22}$ it follows that

$$\left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \right\} \subseteq \\ \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{12}) \wedge (|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{22}) \right\}$$

and thus we conclude $\underline{st}'_1 \subseteq \underline{st}'_2$.

– $\boxed{q = (e_1 = e_2)}$

We now know $\underline{st}'_1 =$

$$\left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). cs(cg) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st}) \wedge \\ (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \end{array} \right\}$$

and similarly for \underline{st}'_2 . From $\dot{st}_{11} \subseteq \dot{st}_{12}$ and $\dot{st}_{21} \subseteq \dot{st}_{22}$ it follows that

$$\left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). cs(cg) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st}) \wedge \\ (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \end{array} \right\} \subseteq \\ \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). cs(cg) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st}) \wedge \\ (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{12}) \wedge (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{22}) \end{array} \right\}$$

and thus we conclude $\underline{st}'_1 \subseteq \underline{st}'_2$.

• $\boxed{c = c_1 ; c_2}$

By induction we have $\forall n'_{\#}, \dot{st}', \dot{st}'' . \dot{st}' \subseteq \dot{st}'' \Rightarrow \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \dot{st}') \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \dot{st}'')$ and similarly for c_2 . From $\dot{st}_1 \subseteq \dot{st}_2$ we can deduce $\text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1) \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_2)$. Using the induction hypothesis again together with this knowledge we get:

$$\text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{key}(c_2) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1)) \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{key}(c_2) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_2))$$

This finally implies $\underline{st}'_1 \subseteq \underline{st}'_2$. □

Theorem 5.2.D. *The weakest precondition has a associativity property for a sequential composition:*

$$\forall I, n_{id}, n_{\#}, c_1, c_2, c_3, cs, \dot{st}. \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1 ; (c_2 ; c_3), n_{\#}, \dot{st}) = \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r((c_1 ; c_2) ; c_3, n_{\#}, \dot{st})$$

Proof. For some $I, n_{id}, n_{\#}, c_1, c_2, c_3, cs$ and \dot{st} we have using Definition 5.2.A and Definition 5.2.C:

$$\text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1 ; (c_2 ; c_3), n_{\#}, \dot{st}) = \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{key}(c_2 ; c_3) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2 ; c_3, n_{\#}, \dot{st})) = \\ \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{key}(c_2) + \$_{key}(c_3) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_2, \$_{key}(c_3) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_3, n_{\#}, \dot{st}))) = \\ \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_1 ; c_2, \$_{key}(c_3) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c_3, n_{\#}, \dot{st})) = \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r((c_1 ; c_2) ; c_3, n_{\#}, \dot{st})$$

□

Lemma 5.2.A. *The weakest precondition has the following property used in Theorem 5.2.E:*

$$\forall I, n_{id}, n_{\#}, c, \dot{st}_1, \dot{st}_2. \left(\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. v \in \text{VARS}_{:=}(c) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st} \left[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right] \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \Rightarrow \\ \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on c . For some $I, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1$ and \dot{st}_2 such that $\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. v \in \text{VARS}_{:=}(c) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st} \left[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right] \in \dot{st}_2$, we need to prove that $\text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$. Using

Theorem 4.3.C, we now have for all the inductive cases:

- $c = \text{skip}$ $c = \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})$

We have $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) = \dot{st}_1$ and $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) = \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2$. So it is straightforward to see that $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$.

- $c = \text{stuck}$

We have $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) = \underline{ST}$ and $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) = \underline{ST}$. So it is straightforward to see that $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$.

- $c = \text{fail}$ $c = \text{fork}(c')$

We have $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) = \emptyset$ and $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) = \emptyset$. So it is straightforward to see that $\text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(c, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$.

- $c = \text{snd}(e)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_1 \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $c = \text{rcv}(v)$ Since $v \in \text{VARS}(c)$ we have $\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} [v := \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall s. \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $c = v := e$ Since $v \in \text{VARS}(c)$ we have $\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_1 \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \underline{st} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}] \in \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$

Since $v \in \text{VARS}(c)$ we have $\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2$ and so using Definition 5.1.E:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I\text{-nid}}^r(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 &= \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#)] \in \dot{st}_1 \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \\ \forall cs. \underline{st} [v := \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\llbracket \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs})] \in \dot{st}_2 \end{array} \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{id}, n\#)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \\ \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st} [v := cs(\text{key}(n_{id}, n\#))] \in \dot{st}_2 \end{array} \right\} \subseteq \end{aligned}$$

$$\left\{ \underline{st} \mid \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#}) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right\} = \mathbf{WP}_{I-nid}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right)$$

- $\boxed{c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p)}$

Since $v \in \mathbf{VARS}(c)$ we have $\forall \underline{st}, cs, \hat{e}. \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := \llbracket \hat{e} \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2$ and so Definition 5.1.E gives us:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\nexists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \right) \wedge \right. \\ & \left. \left(\exists s_k. \underline{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \underline{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\nexists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \right) \wedge \right. \\ & \left. \left(\exists s_k. \underline{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \underline{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st}[v := \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}] \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\nexists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \right) \wedge \right. \\ & \left. \left(\exists s_k. \underline{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \underline{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st}[v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \mathbf{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left(\left(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left. \forall cs' \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}[v := \llbracket \widehat{\mathbf{cg2s}}(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs'}] \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left(\left(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st}_1 \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left. \forall cs' \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}[v := cs'(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, v_p))] \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \left(\left(\exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = cs(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left(\mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{st}[v := r \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2 \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \mathbf{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

We thus may conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{WP}_{I-nid}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1 \right) \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left(\mathbf{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \vee \mathbf{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right) \right\} \subseteq \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left(\mathbf{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \vee \mathbf{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{st}(v_k), s_p, \underline{st}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \right) \right\} = \\ & \mathbf{WP}_{I-nid}^r(c, n_{\#}, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{c = q ? c_1 : c_2}$

Using the abbreviations:

- $\dot{st}_{11} = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n\#, \dot{st}_1)$ and $\dot{st}_{12} = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$
- $\dot{st}_{21} = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1)$ and $\dot{st}_{22} = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$

we know by induction that $\dot{st}_{11} \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \dot{st}_{12}$ and $\dot{st}_{21} \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq \dot{st}_{22}$. We now proceed by a case analysis of q :

- $\boxed{q = (|e| = n)}$ In this case we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} & WP_{I.nid}^r(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|[e]_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge (|[e]_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|[e]_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge (|[e]_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \right\} \subseteq \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|[e]_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11} \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \wedge (|[e]_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21} \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \right\} = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|[e]_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11} \cap \dot{st}_2) \wedge (|[e]_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21} \cap \dot{st}_2) \right\} \subseteq \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid (|[e]_{st}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{12}) \wedge (|[e]_{st}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{22}) \right\} = \\ & WP_{I.nid}^r(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{q = (e_1 = e_2)}$ In this case we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} & WP_{I.nid}^r(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{st}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{st} = [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge ([e_1]_{st} \neq [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \end{array} \right\} \cap \dot{st}_2 = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{st}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{st} = [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11}) \wedge ([e_1]_{st} \neq [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21}) \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2 \end{array} \right\} \subseteq \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{st}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{st} = [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11} \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \wedge ([e_1]_{st} \neq [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21} \wedge \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \end{array} \right\} = \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{st}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{st} = [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{11} \cap \dot{st}_2) \wedge ([e_1]_{st} \neq [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{21} \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{array} \right\} \subseteq \\ & \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{st} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{st} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{st}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{st} = [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{12}) \wedge ([e_1]_{st} \neq [e_2]_{st} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \dot{st}_{22}) \end{array} \right\} = \\ & WP_{I.nid}^r(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2) \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{c = c_1 ; c_2}$

Using the abbreviations $n'_\# = \$_{key}(c_2) + n\#$ and $\dot{st}' = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1)$ we can derive:

- $WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n'_\#, \dot{st}') \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n'_\#, \dot{st}' \cap \dot{st}_2)$ (By induction)
- $\dot{st}' \cap \dot{st}_2 = WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1) \cap \dot{st}_2 \subseteq WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2)$ (By induction)
- $WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n'_\#, \dot{st}' \cap \dot{st}_2) \subseteq WP_{I.nid}^r(c_1, n'_\#, WP_{I.nid}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st}_1 \cap \dot{st}_2))$ (By Theorem 5.2.C)

We now can establish the required relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_1 ; c_2, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1) \cap \underline{\text{st}}_2 &= \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \cap \underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}' \cap \underline{\text{st}}_2) \subseteq \\ &\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_1, n'_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_2, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1 \cap \underline{\text{st}}_2)) = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c_1 ; c_2, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1 \cap \underline{\text{st}}_2) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 5.2.E. *The deduction rules for Hoare triples establish the following for the weakest precondition:*

$$\forall r, I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, c, \widehat{b}_1, \widehat{b}_2. I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#2} : \widehat{b}_2\} \Rightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on the derivation of $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c \{n_{\#2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$ for some $r, I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, c, \widehat{b}_1$ and \widehat{b}_2 . So we must show in all the cases that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. We use Theorem 4.3.C and 5.1.D, 4.2.C implicitly throughout the remainder of this proof:

• **HSKIP**

We have $c = \text{skip}$, $\widehat{b}_1 = \widehat{b}_2$ and $\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{skip}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) = \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r$, so we can directly conclude that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r = \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{skip}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$.

• **HSTUCK**

We have $c = \text{stuck}$, $\widehat{b}_2 = \text{false}$ and $\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{stuck}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) = \underline{\text{ST}}$, so we can directly conclude that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \underline{\text{ST}} = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{skip}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$.

• **HFAIL**

We have $c = \text{fail}$, $\widehat{b}_1 = \text{false}$ and $\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{fail}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) = \emptyset$, so we can directly conclude that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r = \llbracket \text{false} \rrbracket_I^r = \emptyset = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{skip}, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$.

• **HSEND**

In this case we have $c = \text{snd}(e)$, $\widehat{b}_1 = \text{pub}(e)$ and $\widehat{b}_2 = \text{true}$. So we can conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \llbracket \text{pub}(e) \rrbracket_I^r = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s) \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s) \right\} = \\ &\left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{ST}} \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s)) \wedge \underline{\text{st}} \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \\ &\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{snd}(e), n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

• **HRECEIVE**

Now we have for some v that $c = \text{rcv}(v)$, $\widehat{b}_1 = \text{true}$ and $\widehat{b}_2 = \text{pub}(v)$. So we can conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \llbracket \text{true} \rrbracket_I^r = \underline{\text{ST}} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \exists s_2. s2s(s_1) = s2s(s_2) \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \exists s_2. \llbracket s_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s_2) \right\} = \\ &\left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \exists s_2. \llbracket (v)[s_1/v] \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s_2) \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \exists s_2. \llbracket v \rrbracket_{\text{st}[v:=s2s(s_1)]} = s_2 \right\} = \\ &\left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \exists s_2. \llbracket v \rrbracket_{\text{st}[v:=s2s(s_1)]}^{\text{cs}} = s_2 \right\} = \\ &\left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s_1. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \llbracket \text{pub}(v) \rrbracket_{\text{st}[v:=s2s(s_1)]}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s. \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \in \llbracket \text{pub}(v) \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \\ &\left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s. \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{rcv}(v), n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

• **HASSIGN**

Here we know for some v and e that $c = (v := e)$ and $\widehat{b}_1 = (\widehat{b}_2)[e/v]$. So we can conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \llbracket (\widehat{b}_2)[e/v] \rrbracket_I^r = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket (\widehat{b}_2)[e/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}]^{\text{cs}}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \underline{\text{st}}[v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \text{WP}_{I, n_{\#2}}^r \left(v := e, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \end{aligned}$$

- **HSAMPLE**

Now $c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$, $\widehat{e}_k = \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}))$, $\widehat{b}_1 = (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_k/v]$ and $\widehat{b}_2 = (\widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s)$ for some v , \widehat{b} and \widehat{e}_k . It is easy to see that for any cs we have $\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} = \text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}))$ and using Definition 4.1.V we get $|\text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}))| = N_s$ and even $\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} = N_s$. So we now can derive:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_k/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}]^{\text{cs}}} \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_k/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_k/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket (|v| = N_s)[\widehat{e}_k/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}]^{\text{cs}}} \wedge \llbracket |v| = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}]^{\text{cs}}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}]^{\text{cs}}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}))]} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2})] \in \llbracket \widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \end{aligned}$$

- **HHMAC**

We now know for some $v, v_k, v_p, \widehat{e}_k, \widehat{e}_p, n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}''$ and \widehat{b} that:

$$\begin{aligned} - c &= v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_p, v_k) & - I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 &\vdash \text{pub}(v_p) \\ - \widehat{e}_k &= \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'')) & - \widehat{b}_1 &= (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_h/v] \\ - \widehat{e}_h &= \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'', v_p)) & - \widehat{b}_2 &= (\widehat{b} \wedge |v| = N_s) \\ - I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 &\vdash v_k = \widehat{e}_k \end{aligned}$$

Using Definition 4.1.V we have for all cs, s_p and \widehat{e}_p that $|\text{cs}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'', s_p))| = N_s$ and thus even $\llbracket \widehat{\text{cg2s}}(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'', \widehat{e}_p)) \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} = N_s$. We now show what is required with Theorem 4.2.C and 5.1.D:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} \subseteq \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket v_k = \widehat{e}_k \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \text{pub}(v_p) \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'')) \wedge \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \llbracket (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}_h/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket \llbracket \widehat{e}_h \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'')) \wedge \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_h \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}}]}^{\text{cs}} \wedge \llbracket |v| = N_s \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_h \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}}]}^{\text{cs}} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'')) \wedge \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\llbracket \widehat{e}_h \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}^{\text{cs}}]}^{\text{cs}} \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \left(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'', s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}[v:=\text{cs}(r \blacktriangledown \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}'', n_{\#}'', s_p))]}^{\text{cs}} \right) \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \exists n_{\text{id}}', n_{\#}'. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\widehat{\text{key}}(n_{\text{id}}', n_{\#}')) \wedge \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}', n_{\#}', s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \widehat{\text{hmac}}(n_{\text{id}}', n_{\#}', s_p)] \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_I^r \left(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \vee \text{H_KEY}_I^r \left(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_p, v_k), n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \right) \end{aligned}$$

- **HIFLEN**

In this case we have that $c = (|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2)$ for some e, n, c_1 and c_2 . We also know for some $n_{\#_a}$ and $n_{\#_b}$ that $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_a} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge |e| = n\} c_1 \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$ and $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_b} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(|e| = n)\} c_2 \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$ and $n_{\#_1} = \max(n_{\#_a}, n_{\#_b})$. By induction we know that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge |e| = n \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(|e| = n) \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. We now show the required relation with Theorem 4.2.C:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \underline{st} \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((|e|_{\underline{st}} = n \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}) \wedge \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. (|e|_{\underline{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((|e|_{\underline{st}} = n \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge |e| = n \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}) \wedge \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. (|e|_{\underline{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(|e| = n) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs}) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((|e|_{\underline{st}} = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge |e| = n \rrbracket_I^r) \wedge \left(|e|_{\underline{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(|e| = n) \rrbracket_I^r \right) \right) \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((|e|_{\underline{st}} = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)) \wedge \left(|e|_{\underline{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \right) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

- **HIFEQ**

In this case we have that $c = (e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2)$ for some e_1, e_2, c_1 and c_2 and we know for some $n_{\#_a}$ and $n_{\#_b}$ that $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_a} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge e_1 = e_2\} c_1 \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$, $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#_b} : \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(e_1 = e_2)\} c_2 \{n_{\#_2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$ and $n_{\#_1} = \max(n_{\#_a}, n_{\#_b})$. We also have $I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \text{pub}(e_1)$ and $I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \text{pub}(e_2) \vee I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash e_2 = \widehat{cg}2s(\widehat{cg})$. By induction we can then derive both $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge e_1 = e_2 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(e_1 = e_2) \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. We now show the required relation with Theorem 4.2.C and 5.1.D:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \text{pub}(e_1) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \wedge \llbracket \text{pub}(e_2) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \vee e_2 = \widehat{cg}2s(\widehat{cg}) \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). (\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \left((\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = cs(cg)) \wedge \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right) \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \left((\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = cs(cg)) \wedge \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right) \wedge \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \left((\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = cs(cg)) \wedge \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge e_1 = e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right) \wedge \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \wedge \neg(e_1 = e_2) \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}^{cs} \right) \right) \right\} \subseteq \\ &= \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left((\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \left((\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). cs(cg) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \right) \wedge \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \right) \wedge \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \right) \right) \right\} = \\ &= \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n_{\#_2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

- **HSEQ**

For some $c_1, c_2, n_\#$ and \widehat{b} we know now that $c = c_1 ; c_2$ and also that both $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#1} : \widehat{b}_1\} c_1 \{n_\# : \widehat{b}\}$ and $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_\# : \widehat{b}\} c_2 \{n_{\#2} : \widehat{b}_2\}$. We now have by induction that $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_\#, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r)$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. Theorem 5.2.B gives us $n_\# = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#2}$ and with Theorem 5.2.C we can show the required relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &\subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n_\#, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r) = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r) \subseteq \\ &\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n_{\#2}, \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_2, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)) = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1 ; c_2, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

- **HCONSEQ**

We know for some $\widehat{b}, \widehat{b}'_1$ and \widehat{b}'_2 that $I \cdot \widehat{b}_1 \vdash \widehat{b}'_1, I \cdot \widehat{b}_2 \vdash \widehat{b}'_2$ and $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#1} : \widehat{b}'_1\} c \{n_{\#2} : \widehat{b}'_2\}$. By induction we now have $\llbracket \widehat{b}'_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. Using Theorem 4.2.C and 5.1.D we can deduce $\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \llbracket \widehat{b}'_1 \rrbracket_I^r$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r$ and subsequently, using Theorem 5.2.C, we can derive the required relation:

$$\llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \llbracket \widehat{b}'_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$$

- **HCONST**

We know now for some $\widehat{b}, \widehat{b}'_1$ and \widehat{b}'_2 that $\widehat{b}_1 = \widehat{b} \wedge \widehat{b}'_1, \widehat{b}_2 = \widehat{b} \wedge \widehat{b}'_2$ and $\text{VARS}_{:=}(c) \cap \text{VARS}(\widehat{b}) = \emptyset$. We also know that $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#1} : \widehat{b}'_1\} c \{n_{\#2} : \widehat{b}'_2\}$ and so by induction we have $\llbracket \widehat{b}'_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r)$. We can now use $\text{VARS}_{:=}(c) \cap \text{VARS}(\widehat{b}) = \emptyset$ to establish that for any v such that $v \in \text{VARS}_{:=}(c)$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} v &\notin \text{VARS}(\widehat{b}) && \text{(Simple deduction)} \\ \forall \widehat{e}. \widehat{b} &= (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}/v] && \text{(Definition 3.1.I)} \\ \forall \text{st}, \text{cs}, \widehat{e}. \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} &= \llbracket (\widehat{b})[\widehat{e}/v] \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}} && \text{(Simple deduction)} \\ \forall \text{st}, \text{cs}, \widehat{e}. \text{st} \in \text{st}_2 &\Rightarrow \text{st} [v := \llbracket \widehat{e} \rrbracket_{\text{st}}^{\text{cs}}] \in \text{st}_2 && \text{(Theorem 4.3.C)} \end{aligned}$$

Now, finally we can apply Lemma 5.2.A to prove the required relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \widehat{b}_1 \rrbracket_I^r &= \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \cap \llbracket \widehat{b}'_1 \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \cap \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \subseteq \\ &\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \cap \llbracket \widehat{b}'_2 \rrbracket_I^r) = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n_{\#2}, \llbracket \widehat{b}_2 \rrbracket_I^r) \end{aligned}$$

□

5.2.3 Commands and safety

Definition 5.2.D. *Safety of a possibly forking command for an invariant, cryptogram record, identity number, sequence number and precondition is expressed by the judgment $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{id}, n_\#, \text{st}, c)$ for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{id}, n_\#, \text{st}$ and c :*

$$\frac{n_\# = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n'_\# \quad \text{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c, n'_\#, \text{st}')}{\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{false}, n_{id}, n_\#, \text{st}, c)} \text{SAFEWP}$$

$$\frac{n_\# = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_\# \quad \text{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n'_\#, \text{st}') \quad \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, n_{id}, n'_\#, \text{st}', c_2)}{\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, n_{id}, n_\#, \text{st}, c_1 ; c_2)} \text{SAFESEQ}$$

$$\frac{n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#} \quad \underline{\text{st}} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \quad \text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1}, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c_2)}{\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, \mathbf{fork}(c_1); c_2)} \text{SAFEFORK}$$

Theorem 5.2.F. *Relaxing the precondition of a safe possibly forking command:*

$$\forall I, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, c, r, \underline{\text{st}}_1, \underline{\text{st}}_2. \underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \underline{\text{st}}_1 \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1, c) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_2, c)$$

Proof. For some $I, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, c, r, \underline{\text{st}}_1$, and $\underline{\text{st}}_2$ such that $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \underline{\text{st}}_1$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1, c)$, we prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_2, c)$. We continue the proof by performing induction on the derivation of $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1, c)$:

- **SAFEWP**

Now we have $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ for some $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$. Since $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \underline{\text{st}}_1$ clearly also $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. Applying SAFEWP now finishes the proof.

- **SAFESEQ**

Now we have for some $c_1, c_2, n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ that $c = c_1 ; c_2$, $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}', c_2)$. Since $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \underline{\text{st}}_1$ clearly also $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. Applying SAFESEQ finishes the proof.

- **SAFEFORK**

Now for some $c_1, c_2, n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ we have $c = \mathbf{fork}(c_1); c_2$, $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}}_1 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1}, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_1, c_2)$. Since $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \underline{\text{st}}_1$ it follows that also $\underline{\text{st}}_2 \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and we invoke the induction hypothesis to get $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1}, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}_2, c_2)$. Applying SAFEFORK now finishes the proof. □

Theorem 5.2.G. *The deduction rules for forking commands establish safety:*

$$\forall I, r, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \widehat{b}, c. I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c \Rightarrow \exists b_{\text{fork}}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r, c)$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on the derivation of $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c$ according to Definition 3.2.C for some $I, r, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \widehat{b}$ and c :

- **FLift**

Now we know that there exists a $n'_{\#}$ and \widehat{b}' such that $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\}$. Using Theorem 5.2.B and 5.2.E we can derive $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n'_{\#}$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n'_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b}' \rrbracket_I^r)$ and with the rule SAFEWP we conclude $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{false}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r, c)$.

- **FSeq**

Now we know that $c = c_1 ; c_2$ for some c_1 and c_2 . There must also exist a $n'_{\#}$ and \widehat{b}' such that $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c_1 \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\}$ and $I \cdot n_{\text{id}} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b}' \vdash c_2$. With Theorem 5.2.B and 5.2.E we derive $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#}$ and $\llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b}' \rrbracket_I^r)$ and using the induction hypothesis we can derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b}' \rrbracket_I^r, c_2)$. Applying SAFESEQ gives $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \llbracket \widehat{b} \rrbracket_I^r, c_1 ; c_2)$.

- **FFork**

Now we know that $c = \mathbf{fork}(c_1) ; c_2$ for some c_1 and c_2 . There must also exist a $n'_{\#}$, $n''_{\#}$ and \widehat{b}' such that $I \cdot n_{id} \vdash \{n_{\#} : \widehat{b}\} c_1 \{n'_{\#} : \widehat{b}'\}$ and $I \cdot n_{id} + \mathbf{1} \cdot n''_{\#} \cdot \widehat{b} \vdash c_2$. Using Theorem 5.2.B and 5.2.E we can derive $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#}$ and also $[[\widehat{b}]]_I^r \subseteq \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, [[\widehat{b}]]_I^r)$. By induction we now get $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{id} + \mathbf{1}, n''_{\#}, [[\widehat{b}]]_I^r, c_2)$ and finally we get $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, [[\widehat{b}]]_I^r, \mathbf{fork}(c_1) ; c_2)$ after applying the rule **SAFESEQ**. □

5.3 Safe crypto threads

5.3.1 Crypto threads

Definition 5.3.A. *Crypto threads:* $\underline{t} \in \underline{\mathbb{T}}$

$$\underline{t} ::= (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) \quad (n_{id}, n_{\#} \in \mathbb{N}, \underline{st} \in \underline{\text{ST}}, c \in \mathbb{C}, \bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}^*)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c, \bar{c}. \quad \mathbf{id}((n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) &\equiv n_{id} \\ \forall n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c, \bar{c}. \quad \mathbf{seq}((n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) &\equiv n_{\#} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 5.3.B. *Make a concrete version of a crypto thread:*

$$\forall n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c, \bar{c}. (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) \downarrow \psi \equiv (\underline{st} \downarrow \psi \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})$$

5.3.2 Crypto threads and safety

Definition 5.3.C. *Safety of a possibly forking crypto thread given an invariant I and the cryptogram record r :*

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(-, -) : \mathbb{B} \times \underline{\mathbb{T}} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall b_{\text{fork}}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c, \bar{c}. \quad \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})) \\ \equiv \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, c ; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.3.A. *A concrete version of a safe possibly forking crypto thread has not failed:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}) \Rightarrow \forall \psi. \neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{t} \downarrow \psi)$$

Proof. We start by rewriting the goal using Definition 2.4.A, 5.3.A and 5.3.B as:

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c, \bar{c}. \underline{t} = (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}) \Rightarrow c \neq \mathbf{fail}$$

We will prove this by showing that assuming $c = \mathbf{fail}$ leads to a contradiction for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, c$ and \bar{c} such that $\underline{t} = (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t})$. First we use 5.3.C to derive it must be so that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{id}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}))$. Then proceed with a case analysis of the derivation thereof:

- **SAFEWP**

Now $\underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(\mathbf{fail} ; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$ for some $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' . Since $\text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(\mathbf{fail} ; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{st}') = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(\mathbf{fail}, \$_{\text{key}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + n'_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{id}}^r(\overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')) = \emptyset$ this implies that $\underline{st} \in \emptyset$ which is clearly impossible. So, we have arrived at a contradiction.

- SAFESEQ

Now we know $\underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{id}}^r(\text{fail}, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$ for some $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' . Since $\text{WP}_{I, \text{id}}^r(\text{fail}, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}') = \emptyset$ this implies that $\underline{st} \in \emptyset$ which is clearly impossible. So, we have arrived at a contradiction.

- SAFEFORK This case is clearly impossible.

□

5.4 Safe crypto thread pools

Definition 5.4.A. *Safety of a crypto thread pool given some invariant I and the generated cryptogram record r :* $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, -) : \mathbb{B} \times \underline{T}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \text{b}_{\text{fork}}. \quad \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \varepsilon) &\equiv \text{true} \\ \forall \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}, \bar{t}. \quad \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t} :: \bar{t}) &\equiv \text{id}(\underline{t}) = |\bar{t}| \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}) \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{false}, \bar{t}) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.4.A. *All threads in a safe thread pool are safe:*

$$\forall I, r, \text{b}_1, \underline{t}, \bar{t}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_1, \bar{t}) \wedge \underline{t} \in \bar{t} \Rightarrow \exists \text{b}_2. \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_2, \underline{t})$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on \bar{t} for some I, r, b_1 and \underline{t} . So given $\underline{t} \in \bar{t}$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{b}_1)$ we need to prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{b}_2)$ for some b_2 :

- $\bar{t} = \varepsilon$

This case is impossible as $\underline{t} \in \bar{t}$.

- $\bar{t} = \underline{t}' :: \bar{t}'$

If $\underline{t} = \underline{t}'$ we are done according to Definition 5.4.A since then $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_1, \underline{t})$. Otherwise it must hold that $\underline{t} \in \bar{t}'$ and Definition 5.4.A now gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{false}, \bar{t}')$. So invoking the induction hypothesis finishes the proof in this case.

□

Theorem 5.4.B. *Replace a safe thread with another in a safe thread pool preserves safety:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}_1, \underline{t}_2, \bar{t}_1, \bar{t}_2, \bar{t}_a, \bar{t}_b. \quad &\bar{t}_1 = \bar{t}_a ++ (\underline{t}_1 :: \bar{t}_b) \wedge \bar{t}_2 = \bar{t}_a ++ (\underline{t}_2 :: \bar{t}_b) \wedge \\ &\text{id}(\underline{t}_1) = \text{id}(\underline{t}_2) \wedge (\forall \text{b}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}, \underline{t}_1) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}, \underline{t}_2)) \wedge \\ &\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_1) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_2) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on \bar{t}_a for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}_1, \underline{t}_2, \bar{t}_1, \bar{t}_2$ and \bar{t}_b . So given $\bar{t}_1 = \bar{t}_a ++ (\underline{t}_1 :: \bar{t}_b)$, $\bar{t}_2 = \bar{t}_a ++ (\underline{t}_2 :: \bar{t}_b)$, $\text{id}(\underline{t}_1) = \text{id}(\underline{t}_2)$, $\forall \text{b}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}, \underline{t}_1) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}, \underline{t}_2)$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_1)$, we need to prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_2)$:

- $\bar{t}_a = \varepsilon$

Now we have that $\bar{t}_1 = \underline{t}_1 :: \bar{t}_b$ and $\bar{t}_2 = \underline{t}_2 :: \bar{t}_b$. Since $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_1)$, we know from Definition 5.4.A:

- $\text{id}(\underline{t}_1) = |\bar{t}_b|$ and thus also $\text{id}(\underline{t}_2) = |\bar{t}_b|$
- $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}_1)$ and thus also $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}_2)$
- $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{false}, \bar{t}_b)$

From Definition 5.4.A it clearly follows then that also $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t}_2)$ and we are done.

- $\bar{t}_a = \underline{t}'_a :: \bar{t}'_a$

Since now we have $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{false}, \bar{t}'_a \uparrow\uparrow (\underline{t}_1 :: \bar{t}_b))$ according to Definition 5.4.A, a simple application of the induction hypothesis finishes the proof in this case. □

5.5 Safe crypto worlds

5.5.1 Crypto worlds

Definition 5.5.A. *Crypto worlds:* $\underline{w} \in \underline{W}$

$$\underline{w} ::= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright \bar{t} \rangle \quad (\bar{\alpha} \in A^*, \beta \in B, \gamma \in \Gamma, r \in R, \bar{t} \in T^*)$$

$$\forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, r, \bar{t}. \quad |\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright \bar{t} \rangle| \equiv |\text{keys}(\gamma)| + |\text{cgs}(r)|$$

Definition 5.5.B. *Update an HMAC function γ for a single cryptogram given the coin tosses ψ and record r :*

$$\gamma \boxplus_r^\psi \varepsilon \equiv \gamma$$

$$\forall \text{cg}, \bar{\text{cg}}. \quad \gamma \boxplus_r^\psi \text{cg} :: \bar{\text{cg}} \equiv \begin{cases} \gamma[(s_k, s_p) := s_h] \boxplus_r^\psi \bar{\text{cg}} & \text{(if } (s_k, s_p) \notin \text{dom}(\gamma) \text{ and} \\ & \text{cg} = \text{hmac}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, s_p) \text{ and} \\ & \text{cg} \in r \text{ and } (r \nabla \text{cg})(\psi) = s_h) \text{ and} \\ & \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}) \in r \text{ and} \\ & (r \nabla \text{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}))(\psi) = s_k \\ \gamma \boxplus_r^\psi \bar{\text{cg}} & \text{(otherwise)} \end{cases}$$

Definition 5.5.C. *Make a concrete version of a crypto world:*

$$\forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, r, \bar{t}, \psi. \quad (\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright \bar{t} \rangle) \downarrow \psi \equiv \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot (\gamma \boxplus_r^\psi \text{cgs}(r)) \triangleright \bar{t} \downarrow \psi \rangle$$

5.5.2 Initial crypto world

Definition 5.5.D. *The initial crypto world given an attacker and protocol command:*

$$\forall c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \quad \underline{w}_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)$$

$$\equiv$$

$$\langle [\text{step}, \text{step}] \cdot [] \cdot \bar{\emptyset} \cdot [[] \cdot [] \cdot []] \triangleright [(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \cdot \$_{\text{key}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \cdot \underline{st}_\varepsilon \triangleright \text{fork}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \circ [c])] \rangle$$

Theorem 5.5.A. *Two important properties of the initial crypto world:*

$$\forall c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \quad |\underline{w}_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)| = \mathbf{0} \wedge \forall \psi. \quad \underline{w}_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c) \downarrow \psi = \underline{w}_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)$$

Proof. This follows directly from 5.5.D. □

5.5.3 Crypto worlds and safety

Definition 5.5.E. *Safe crypto worlds given an invariant I :*

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, r, \bar{t}. \text{SAFE}_I(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle) \\
& \quad \equiv \\
& \text{SAFE}_I(r) \wedge \text{keys}(\gamma) \cap \text{strs}(r) = \emptyset \wedge \text{cgs}(r) \prec |\bar{t}| \wedge \forall \underline{t} \in \bar{t}. \text{seq}(\underline{t}) \prec_{\text{id}(\underline{t})} \text{cgs}(r) \wedge \\
& \exists b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}, \bar{t}_1, \bar{t}_2. \bar{t} = (\bar{t}_2 ++ (\underline{t} :: \bar{t}_1)) \wedge \left(\forall r'. \text{SAFE}_I(r + r') \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^{r+r'}(b_{\text{fork}}, (\underline{t} :: \bar{t}_1) ++ \bar{t}_2) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.5.B. *A concrete version of a safe crypto world has not failed:*

$$\forall I, \underline{w}. \text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}) \Rightarrow \forall \psi. \neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$$

Proof. Using Definition 5.5.A we assume $\text{SAFE}_I(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \rangle)$ for some $I, \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, r, \bar{t}$ and ψ and now must show $\neg \text{FAILED}(\langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot (\gamma \boxplus_{\bar{t}}^{\psi} \text{cgs}(r)) \blacktriangleright \bar{t} \downarrow \psi \rangle)$. With Definition 2.4.B this becomes $\forall \underline{t} \in \{\bar{t}\}. \neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{t} \downarrow \psi)$. From 5.5.E we know $\text{SAFE}_I(r)$ and with 5.4.A we derive $\forall \underline{t} \in \{\bar{t}\}. \exists b_{\text{fork}}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, \bar{t})$. Theorem 5.3.A now finishes this proof. \square

6 Soundness of proof system

6.1 The attacker

Definition 6.1.A. *Attacker crypto stores:*

$$\text{ATT}_{\text{ST}} \equiv \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall e. \exists s \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s) \right\}$$

Theorem 6.1.A. *Updating an attacker crypto store with an expression results in another attacker crypto store:*

$$\forall \underline{\text{st}}, v, e. \underline{\text{st}} \in \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}} \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}$$

Proof. For some $\underline{\text{st}}, v$ and e we assume $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}$ and thus $\underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}}' \mid \forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}'} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s) \right\}$. Now we need to prove $\underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}}' \mid \forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}'} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s) \right\}$ or equivalently $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] } = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$. According to Theorem 4.3.A it is sufficient to show $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket (e')[e/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$, but this is straightforward since from $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}$ we know $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$ which also implies that $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket (e')[e/v] \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$. \square

Theorem 6.1.B. *An attacker command respects attacker store states for the weakest precondition:*

$$\forall I, c_{\text{attacker}}, r, \underline{\text{st}}, n_{\#}. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I) \wedge \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \wedge \underline{\text{st}} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}} \Rightarrow \\ \underline{\text{st}} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_{\text{attacker}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}})$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on c_{attacker} . For some $I, r, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}'$, and $n_{\#}$ we assume that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I)$, $\text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}})$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}'$ and $\underline{\text{st}}' = \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}$, and we show that $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_{\text{attacker}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. From Definition 6.1.A and Definition 4.2.C we can already establish that $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$ and from Theorem 6.1.A we know that $\forall v', e'. \underline{\text{st}} [v' := \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}'$.

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{skip}$ $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})$

Now $\underline{\text{st}} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_{\text{attacker}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and so definitely $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_{\text{attacker}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$.

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{stuck}$

Now $\underline{\text{st}} \subseteq \underline{\text{ST}} = \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(\text{stuck}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and so definitely $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(\text{stuck}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$.

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{fail}$ $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{fork}(c')$

These cases cannot occur since $\text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}})$

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{snd}(e)$

Now we have $\text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)) \wedge \underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and we know $\underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}'$ and $\forall e'. \exists s \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)$. So we have $\underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid (\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)) \wedge \underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and we are done.

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = \text{rcv}(v)$

Now $\text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(\text{rcv}(v), n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s. \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and from $\forall v', e'. \underline{\text{st}} [v' := \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}'$ we know that $\forall s. \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}'$. So we have $\underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s. \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2_{\underline{\text{S}}}(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and we are done.

- $c_{\text{attacker}} = v := e$

We know $\text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(v := e, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and from $\forall v', e'. \underline{\text{st}} [v' := \llbracket e' \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}'$ we know that $\underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}'$. So we have $\underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\}$ and we are done.

- $C_{\text{attacker}} = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s$

Now $\text{WP}_{\text{I.ATTID}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n_{\#}, \dot{st} \right) =$

$$\left\{ \dot{st} \mid \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{st} \right\}$$

according to Definition 5.2.C. Since we also have $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\text{I})$ as an assumption, it follows from Definition 3.2.E that $(\widehat{\text{key}}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}), \text{true}) \in \text{I}$. Theorem 4.2.G and 5.1.D then give that if $\text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r)$, then for all $cs \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r)$ we have that $cs(\text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#})) = r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#})$ and there must exist an s_k such that $r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) = s2s(s_k)$. Using Theorem 4.3.B and 4.3.C we now have:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \in \dot{st} &\Rightarrow (\forall v', e'. \dot{st} [v' := [e']_{\dot{st}}] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow (\dot{st} [v := s2s(s_k)] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &(\text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := s2s(s_k)] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &(\text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, n_{\#})] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I.ATTID}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s, n_{\#}, \dot{st} \right) \end{aligned}$$

- $C_{\text{attacker}} = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)$

According to Definition 5.2.C we now have $\text{WP}_{\text{I.ATTID}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n_{\#}, \dot{st} \right) =$

$$\left\{ \dot{st} \mid \exists s_p. \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_{\text{I}}^r(v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) \vee \text{H_KEY}_{\text{I}}^r(v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) \right) \right\}$$

We now perform a case analysis:

- $\forall cs \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \dot{st}(v_k) = cs(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$

Using Theorem 5.1.D we can deduce that $\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) \in \{\text{cgs}(r)\}$ and we know from Definition 5.1.E that for any \dot{st} such that $\exists s_k. \dot{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k)$ it must be so that $\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) \in [\text{I}]$. Theorem 4.2.H then gives us that if there exists such a \dot{st} we also have for any s_p that $\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in [\text{I}]$ and that there must exist a s_h such that $cs(\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p)) = s2s(s_h)$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \in \dot{st} &\Rightarrow (\forall e'. \exists s [e']_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s) \wedge \forall v', e'. \dot{st} [v' := [e']_{\dot{st}}] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &(\exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \dot{st} [v := s2s(s_h)] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &(\exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge (\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := s2s(s_h)] \in \dot{st})) \Rightarrow \\ &(\exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge (\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st})) \Rightarrow \\ &\left(\begin{array}{l} \exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \exists n''_{\text{id}}, n''_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \dot{st}(v_k) = cs(\text{key}(n''_{\text{id}}, n''_{\#})) \wedge \\ (\text{hmac}(n''_{\text{id}}, n''_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \dot{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{hmac}(n''_{\text{id}}, n''_{\#}, s_p)] \in \dot{st}) \end{array} \right) \Rightarrow \\ \exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \text{H_KEY}_{\text{I}}^r(v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) &\Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I.ATTID}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n_{\#}, \dot{st} \right) \end{aligned}$$

- $\nexists n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \dot{st}(v_k) = cs(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$

Now we can deduce using Theorem 6.1.A:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \in \dot{st} &\Rightarrow (\forall e'. \exists s [e']_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s) \wedge \forall v', e'. \dot{st} [v' := [e']_{\dot{st}}] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &(\exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \exists s_k \dot{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \dot{st} [v := s2s(s)] \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &\exists s_p \dot{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \text{H_ATT}_{\text{I}}^r(v, \dot{st}(v_k), s_p, \dot{st}, \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &\dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I.ATTID}}^r \left(v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n_{\#}, \dot{st} \right) \end{aligned}$$

- $C_{\text{attacker}} = q ? c_1 : c_2$

Using the abbreviations $\dot{st}_1 = \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_1, n\#, \dot{st})$ and $\dot{st}_2 = \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st})$ we have by induction that $\dot{st} \subseteq \dot{st}_1$ and $\dot{st} \subseteq \dot{st}_2$. We now proceed with a case analysis of q :

– $q = (|e| = n)$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \in \dot{st} &\Rightarrow ([e]_{\dot{st}} = n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}) \wedge ([e]_{\dot{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}) \Rightarrow \\ &([e]_{\dot{st}} = n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_1) \wedge ([e]_{\dot{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \Rightarrow \\ \dot{st} \in \left\{ \dot{st} \mid ([e]_{\dot{st}} = n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n\#, \dot{st})) \wedge ([e]_{\dot{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st})) \right\} &\Rightarrow \\ \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) & \end{aligned}$$

– $q = (e_1 = e_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \in \dot{st} &\Rightarrow \exists s_1. [e_1]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_1) \wedge \exists s_2. [e_2]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_2) \wedge \dot{st} \in \dot{st} \Rightarrow \\ &\left(\begin{array}{l} \exists s_1. [e_1]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_1) \wedge \exists s_2. [e_2]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_2) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} = [e_1]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}) \wedge ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} \neq [e_2]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}) \end{array} \right) \Rightarrow \\ &\left(\begin{array}{l} \exists s_1. [e_1]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_1) \wedge \exists s_2. [e_2]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_2) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} = [e_1]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_1) \wedge ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} \neq [e_2]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \dot{st}_2) \end{array} \right) \Rightarrow \\ \dot{st} \in \left\{ \dot{st} \mid \begin{array}{l} (\exists s_1. [e_1]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_1)) \wedge \\ (\exists s_2. [e_2]_{\dot{st}} = s2s(s_2) \vee \exists cg. \forall cs \in \odot_{[I]}(r). cs(cg) = [e_2]_{\dot{st}}) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} = [e_2]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n\#, \dot{st})) \wedge \\ ([e_1]_{\dot{st}} \neq [e_2]_{\dot{st}} \Rightarrow \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st})) \\ \dot{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) \end{array} \right\} &\Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

- $C_{\text{attacker}} = c_1 ; c_2$

We have by induction that $\dot{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n\#, \dot{st})$ and $\dot{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st})$. So with Theorem 5.2.C we can derive:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n\#, \dot{st}) \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n\#, \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_2, n\#, \dot{st})) &= \\ \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(c_1 ; c_2, n\#, \dot{st}) & \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 6.1.C. *Executing an attacker command in parallel with a safe command preserves safety:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall I, C_{\text{attacker}}, c, n\#, r, \dot{st}. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I) \wedge \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(C_{\text{attacker}}) \wedge \\ \dot{st} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}} \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} + 1, n\#, \dot{st}, c) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, \$_{\text{key}}(C_{\text{attacker}}), \dot{st}, \text{fork}(C_{\text{attacker}}); c) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Given some $I, C_{\text{attacker}}, c, n\#, r$ and \dot{st} such that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(I), \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(C_{\text{attacker}}), \dot{st} = \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}$ and also $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} + 1, n\#, \dot{st}, c)$, we must show $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, \$_{\text{key}}(C_{\text{attacker}}), \dot{st}, \text{fork}(C_{\text{attacker}}); c)$. After invoking Theorem 6.1.B we immediately get $\dot{st} \subseteq \text{WP}_{I, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}}^r(C_{\text{attacker}}, \mathbf{0}, \dot{st})$ and now invoking SAFEFORK finishes the proof. □

6.2 Safety and execution

6.2.1 Consecutive execution triples

Definition 6.2.A. *Consecutive execution triples consisting of a key sampling number, crypto store and command:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, r, \underline{st}_1, \underline{st}_2, c_1, c_2. (n_{\#1} \cdot \underline{st}_1 \cdot c_1) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#2} \cdot \underline{st}_2 \cdot c_2) \\ \equiv \\ \forall n'_{\#}, \underline{st}'. n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}') \Rightarrow \\ n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n'_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}') \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6.2.A. *Execution triples for a sequential composition:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, c_1, c_2, c, r, \underline{st}_1, \underline{st}_2, \underline{st}. n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1; c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1; c, n_{\#}, \underline{st}) \wedge \\ (n_{\#1} \cdot \underline{st}_1 \cdot c_1) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#2} \cdot \underline{st}_2 \cdot c_2) \Rightarrow n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2; c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2; c, n_{\#}, \underline{st}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. For some $I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, c_1, c_2, \bar{c}, r, \underline{st}_1, \underline{st}_2$ and \underline{st} for which we know $n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1; c) + n_{\#}$, $\underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1; c, n_{\#}, \underline{st})$ and $(n_{\#1} \cdot \underline{st}_1 \cdot c_1) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#2} \cdot \underline{st}_2 \cdot c_2)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1; c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1; c, n_{\#}, \underline{st})) \Rightarrow \\ (n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \underline{st}))) \Rightarrow \\ (n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n_{\#}, \underline{st}))) \Rightarrow \\ (n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2; c) + n_{\#} \wedge \underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2; c, n_{\#}, \underline{st})) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 6.2.B. *Safety for consecutive execution triples and sequential composition:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, n_{\#2}, c_1, c_2, c, r, \underline{st}_1, \underline{st}_2. (n_{\#1} \cdot \underline{st}_1 \cdot c_1) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#2} \cdot \underline{st}_2 \cdot c_2) \wedge \\ (\neg \exists c'. c_1 = \mathbf{fork}(c')) \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, \{\underline{st}_1\}, c_1; c) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}, \{\underline{st}_2\}, c_2; c) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. For some $I, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, c_1, c_2, c, r, \underline{st}_1$ and \underline{st}_2 we assume that $\neg \exists c'. c_1 = \mathbf{fork}(c')$. We also assume that $(n_{\#1} \cdot \underline{st}_1 \cdot c_1) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#2} \cdot \underline{st}_2 \cdot c_2)$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, \{\underline{st}_1\}, c_1; c)$. Now we will show that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}, \{\underline{st}_2\}, c_2; c)$ with a case analysis on the derivation of $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#1}, \{\underline{st}_1\}, c_1; c)$:

- SAFEWP

Here we have for some $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' that $n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1; c) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1; c, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$. Invoking Theorem 6.2.A then gives us $n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2; c) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2; c, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$. Applying the rule SAFEWP finishes the proof.

- SAFESEQ

Now there must exist some $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' such that $n_{\#1} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{st}_1 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}', c)$. With Definition 6.2.A we can then derive $n_{\#2} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_2) + n'_{\#}$, and $\underline{st}_2 \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}')$ so applying the rule SAFESEQ results in $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#2}, \{\underline{st}_2\}, c_2; c)$ and we are done.

- SAFEFORK

This case is clearly impossible since $\neg \exists c'. c_1 = \mathbf{fork}(c')$.

□

6.2.2 Safe deterministic execution

Theorem 6.2.C. *Performing a XSEND step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread and ensures publicness of the sent expression:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, e, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{snd}(e) \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c})) \wedge \exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2s(s)$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{snd}(e) \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, e$ and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{snd}(e); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) \text{ and } \exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2s(s)$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{snd}(e)) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\left(\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \right) \Rightarrow (\underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \left(\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \right)$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \text{snd}(e)) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. We now proceed with a case analysis of the derivation of $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{snd}(e); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$:

- **SAFEWP**

In this case we know there must exist some $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ such that $n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{snd}(e); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{snd}(e); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. From Definition 5.2.C it is now clear that $\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2s(s)$.

- **SAFESEQ**

For a $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ we have that $n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{snd}(e)) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{snd}(e), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$, $b_{\text{fork}} = \text{true}$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}', \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. From Definition 5.2.C it is now clear that $\exists s. \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{\text{st}}} = s2s(s)$.

- **SAFEFORK**

This case is clearly impossible. □

Theorem 6.2.D. *Performing a XRECEIVE step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, s, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{rcv}(v) \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{rcv}(v) \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, s$ and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{rcv}(v); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{rcv}(v)) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{rcv}(v), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \forall s. \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\} \Rightarrow (\underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \\ (\underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}'))$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \text{rcv}(v)) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)] \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := s2s(s)]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. □

Theorem 6.2.E. *Performing a XASSIGN step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, e, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v := e \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v := e \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, e$ and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, v := e; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}], \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(v := e) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(v := e, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \right\} \Rightarrow \\ \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot v := e) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}] \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := [e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}], \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

Theorem 6.2.F. *Performing a XSCHEDULE step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, \bar{\alpha}, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}) \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}) \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, \bar{\alpha}$, and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}' \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha})) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

Theorem 6.2.G. *Performing a XSKIP step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread:*

$$\forall I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ c :: \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ \text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}))$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ c :: \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c$ and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

We now proceed with a case analysis of the derivation of $\text{SAFE}_I^r(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}))$:

- SAFEWP

In this case we know there must exist some $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ such that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. Definition 5.2.A now allows us to show: $n_{\#} =$

$\$_{\text{key}}(\mathbf{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c})) + n'_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\mathbf{skip}) + \$_{\text{key}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c})) + n'_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \\ & \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{skip}, \$_{\text{key}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c})) + n'_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')) = \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \end{aligned}$$

Now we have established that $\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}) = c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})$, $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and also $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. So applying SAFEWP finishes the proof.

- SAFESEQ

For a $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ we have that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\mathbf{skip}) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$, $\text{b}_{\text{fork}} = \mathbf{true}$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}', \overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}))$. So we know $n_{\#} = n'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \underline{\text{st}}'$ and $\overline{\text{CMD}}(c :: \bar{c}) = c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})$ and Theorem 5.2.F then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ and we are done.

- SAFEFORK This case is clearly impossible. □

Theorem 6.2.H. *Performing a XSEQ step preserves safety of the selected crypto thread:*

$$\forall I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c_1, c_2, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1; c_2 \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1 \circ c_2 :: \bar{c}))$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1; c_2 \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c_1, c_2$ and \bar{c} and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1 \circ c_2 :: \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c_1; c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c_2 :: \bar{c}))$$

But this is obvious as $c_1; c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}) = c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(c_2 :: \bar{c})$ □

Theorem 6.2.I. *Performing a XFORK step preserves safety of the crypto thread pool:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall I, r, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c, \bar{c}, \underline{\text{t}}, \underline{\text{t}}_1, \underline{\text{t}}_2, \bar{\underline{\text{t}}}. \exists n'_{\#}. \underline{\text{t}} = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \mathbf{fork}(c) \circ \bar{c}) \wedge \\ & \underline{\text{t}}_1 = (n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c}) \wedge \underline{\text{t}}_2 = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c \circ []) \wedge \\ & \text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}} :: \bar{\underline{\text{t}}}) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}}_1 :: (\underline{\text{t}}_2 :: \bar{\underline{\text{t}}})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We must prove that for some $I, \bar{c}^g, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, c, \bar{c}, \underline{\text{t}}, \underline{\text{t}}_1, \underline{\text{t}}_2$ and $\bar{\underline{\text{t}}}$ there exists some $n'_{\#}$ such that $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}}_1 :: (\underline{\text{t}}_2 :: \bar{\underline{\text{t}}}))$ and where:

- $\underline{\text{t}} = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \mathbf{fork}(c) \circ \bar{c})$
- $\underline{\text{t}}_1 = (n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})$
- $\underline{\text{t}}_2 = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c \circ [])$
- $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}} :: \bar{\underline{\text{t}}})$

From Definition 5.4.A we know that $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}})$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{false}, \bar{\underline{\text{t}}})$. Using Definition 5.4.A it is now sufficient to show there exists a $n'_{\#}$ so that we have both $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{true}, \underline{\text{t}}_1)$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^{\text{f}}(\mathbf{false}, \underline{\text{t}}_2)$. This means

that we must show $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + 1, n'_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \mathbf{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{false}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c; \mathbf{skip})$ for some $n'_{\#}$. Now we proceed with a case analysis of $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \mathbf{fork}(c); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$:

- **SAFEWP**

Now we have for some $n''_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ that $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\mathbf{fork}(c); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. From Definition 5.2.C we can conclude that it must be so that $\text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\mathbf{fork}(c); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \emptyset$. But then $\underline{\text{st}} \in \emptyset$ which is clearly impossible and so we have a contradiction.

- **SAFESEQ**

Now we know there exist a $n''_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ such that $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\mathbf{fork}(c), n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and according to Definition 5.2.C $\text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\mathbf{fork}(c), n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') = \emptyset$. Again we have $\underline{\text{st}} \in \emptyset$ which is impossible and so we have arrived at a contradiction.

- **SAFEFORK**

Now we have for some $n'_{\#}$, $n''_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n''_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$ and also that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + 1, n'_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. First, we can derive from Definition 5.2.A and 5.2.C that $(n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot \mathbf{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{true}, n_{\text{id}} + 1, n'_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, \mathbf{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ follows then from Theorem 6.2.B. Subsequently, from Definition 5.2.A and 5.2.C we derive that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + n''_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c) + \$_{\text{key}}(\mathbf{skip}) + n''_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c; \mathbf{skip}) + n''_{\#}$ and:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') &= \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c, \$_{\text{key}}(\mathbf{skip}) + n''_{\#}, \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(\mathbf{skip}, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')) \\ &= \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r(c; \mathbf{skip}, n''_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we use SAFEWP to establish $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{false}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c; \mathbf{skip})$. □

6.2.3 Safe branching execution

Theorem 6.2.J. *Performing a XIFTRUE or XIFFALSE step with a length condition preserves safety of the selected crypto thread and only one of the two rules is possible:*

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall I, r, \mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, e, n, c_1, c_2, \bar{c}. \\ &\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright |e| = n ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ &(|[e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}| = n \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c})) \vee \\ &(|[e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}| \neq n \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_1) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_2)) \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_2 \circ \bar{c}))) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright |e| = n ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, e, n, c_1, c_2$ and \bar{c} . We finish the proof only for the case that $|[e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}| = n$. The case where $|[e]_{\underline{\text{st}}}| \neq n$ is analogous. Let $n'_{\#}$ denote the result of $n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1))$ and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to establish that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, |e| = n ? c_1 : c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A and Theorem 1.4.A we know that for all $n''_{\#}$ that:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\#} &= \$_{\text{key}}(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \max(\$_{\text{key}}(c_1), \$_{\text{key}}(c_2)) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow \\ n_{\#} &= \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$n'_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n''_{\#}$$

From Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n''_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' since $|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}| = n$:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(|e| = n ? c_1 : c_2, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) &\Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \left\{ \underline{st} \mid \left(|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}| = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(c_1, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) \right) \wedge \right. \\ &\left. \left(|\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}| \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(c_2, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) \right) \right\} \Rightarrow \\ &\left(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(c_1, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) \right) \wedge \left(\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \neq n \Rightarrow \underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(c_2, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ &\underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(c_1, n''_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right) \end{aligned}$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \cdot |e| = n ? c_1 : c_2) \Rightarrow_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r (n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \cdot c_1)$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

Theorem 6.2.K. *Safety of a crypto thread that is about to perform a XIFTRUE or XIFFALSE step with an equality condition, ensures specific properties of the compared expressions:*

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, e_1, e_2, c_1, c_2, \bar{c}. \\ &\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \\ &\exists s. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s) \wedge (\exists s. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s) \vee \exists \text{cg}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(\underline{st}). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \text{cs}(\text{cg})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, e_1, e_2, c_1, c_2$ and \bar{c} . We can already show $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ using Definition 5.3.C and we must show $\exists s. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s)$ and $\exists s. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = s2s(s) \vee \exists \text{cg}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket}(\underline{st}). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \text{cs}(\text{cg})$.

- **SAFEWP**

In this case we know there must exist some $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' such that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right)$. From Definition 5.2.C it is now clear that the required statements hold.

- **SAFESEQ**

For a $n'_{\#}$ and \underline{st}' we have that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2) + n'_{\#}$, $\underline{st} \in \text{WP}_{I, n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}' \right)$, $\text{b}_{\text{fork}} = \text{true}$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \underline{st}', \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. From Definition 5.2.C it is now clear that the required statements hold.

- **SAFEFORK** This case is clearly impossible.

\square

Theorem 6.2.L. *Performing a XIFTRUE or XIFFALSE step with an equality, preserves safety of the selected crypto thread and only one of the two rules is possible:*

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, e_1, e_2, c_1, c_2, \bar{c}. \\ &\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c})) \wedge \Rightarrow \\ &\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c})) \vee \\ &\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} \wedge \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_1) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_2)) \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_2 \circ \bar{c})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{st}, e_1, e_2, c_1, c_2$ and \bar{c} . We finish the proof only for the case that $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\underline{st}}$. The opposite case is analogous. Let $n'_{\#}$ denote the result of $n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1))$ and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to establish that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It

is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \{\text{st}\}, c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A and Theorem 1.4.A we know that for all $n''_{\#}$ that:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\#} &= \$_{\text{key}}(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \max(\$_{\text{key}}(c_1), \$_{\text{key}}(c_2)) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow \\ n_{\#} &= \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n''_{\#} \Rightarrow \\ & n'_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(c_1) + n''_{\#} \end{aligned}$$

From Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n''_{\#}$ and st' since $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2, n''_{\#}, \text{st}') \Rightarrow \\ \text{st} \in & \left\{ \text{st} \mid \begin{aligned} & (\exists s_1. \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s_2 s(s_1)) \wedge (\exists s_2. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s_2 s(s_2)) \vee \exists \text{cg}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \text{cs}(\text{cg}) = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \wedge \\ & (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n''_{\#}, \text{st}')) \wedge (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n''_{\#}, \text{st}')) \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \\ & (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n''_{\#}, \text{st}')) \wedge (\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \Rightarrow \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_2, n''_{\#}, \text{st}')) \Rightarrow \\ & \text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(c_1, n''_{\#}, \text{st}') \end{aligned}$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \cdot e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2) \Rightarrow_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(n'_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \cdot c_1)$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \{\text{st}\}, c_1; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

6.2.4 Safe nondeterministic execution

Theorem 6.2.M. *Safety of a crypto thread that is about to perform a XSAMPLE step ensures that:*

$$\forall I, r, \text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \text{st}, v, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow n_{\#} > \mathbf{0}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \text{st}, v$ and \bar{c} . We can already show $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\text{st}\}, v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ using Definition 5.3.C and we must show $n_{\#} > \mathbf{0}$

- **SAFEWP**

In this case we know there must exist some $n'_{\#}$ and st' such that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + n'_{\#}$ and $\text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), n'_{\#}, \text{st}')$. Since $\$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) = \mathbf{1} + \$_{\text{key}}(\overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ according to Definition 5.2.A, so clearly $n_{\#} > \mathbf{0}$.

- **SAFESEQ**

For a $n'_{\#}$ and st' we have that $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s) + n'_{\#}$, $\text{st} \in \text{WP}_{I \cdot n_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s, n'_{\#}, \text{st}')$, $\text{bfork} = \mathbf{true}$ and $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, \text{st}', \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. Since $\$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s) = \mathbf{1}$ according to Definition 5.2.A, so clearly $n_{\#} > \mathbf{0}$.

- **SAFEFORK** This case is clearly impossible.

\square

Theorem 6.2.N. *Performing a XSAMPLE step preserves safety of the selected thread:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall I, r, \text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \text{st}, v, \text{cg}, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I^r(r) \wedge \text{cg} = \mathbf{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \wedge \text{cg} \in \mathbf{cgs}(r) \wedge \\ & \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - \mathbf{1} \cdot \text{st} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{bfork}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{bfork}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \text{st}, v, \text{cg}$ and \bar{c} . On top of that, we also assume $\text{SAFE}_I^r(r)$, $\text{cg} = \mathbf{key}(n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#} - \mathbf{1})$ and $\text{cg} \in \mathbf{cgs}(r)$ and now we must prove

$\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{N}_s; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know for all $\text{n}'_{\#}$ that $\text{n}_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{N}_s) + \text{n}'_{\#} \Rightarrow \text{n}_{\#} = \mathbf{1} + \text{n}'_{\#} \Rightarrow \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} = \text{n}'_{\#} \Rightarrow \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + \text{n}'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C and 5.1.E we know since $\text{SAFE}_1(r)$ and $\text{cg} \in \text{cgs}(r)$ for any $\text{n}'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ that:

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{N}_s, \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')) &\Rightarrow (\text{key}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(\text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1})] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \\ &(\underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow (\underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \in \text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(\text{skip}, \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')) \end{aligned}$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(\text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{N}_s) \Rightarrow_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r (\text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}, \{\underline{\text{st}} [v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

Theorem 6.2.O. *Safety of a crypto thread that is about to perform a XHMACNEW or XHMACOLD step constrains the crypto string used as the key and ensures a public payload:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \text{I}, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, v_k, v_p, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c})) &\Rightarrow \\ \exists \text{S}_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = \text{s2s}(\text{S}_p) \wedge \left(\exists \text{S}_k. \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{s2s}(\text{S}_k) \vee \exists \text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(\text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#})) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{N}_s \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $\text{I}, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, v_k, v_p$ and \bar{c} . We can already show $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ using Definition 5.3.C and we must now show that $\exists \text{S}_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = \text{s2s}(\text{S}_p)$ and either $\exists \text{S}_k. \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{s2s}(\text{S}_k)$ or $\exists \text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(\text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}))$:

- SAFEWP
In this case there exist some $\text{n}'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ such that $\text{n}_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c})) + \text{n}'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$. So $\text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}), \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \neq \emptyset$ and according to Definition 5.2.C the required propositions hold.
- SAFESEQ
For a $\text{n}'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$ we have $\text{n}_{\#} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)) + \text{n}'_{\#}$, $\underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}')$, $\text{b}_{\text{fork}} = \text{true}$ and $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}', \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. So $\text{WP}_{\text{I-n}_{\text{id}}}^r(v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), \text{n}'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}') \neq \emptyset$ and according to Definition 5.2.C the required propositions hold.
- SAFEFORK This case is clearly impossible.

\square

Theorem 6.2.P. *Performing an HMACOLD or HMACNEW step with a crypto string that is not a key preserves safety of the selected thread:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \text{I}, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, v_k, v_p, \text{s}, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c})) \wedge \\ \left(\nexists \text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(\text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#})) \right) &\Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := \text{s2s}(\text{s})] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\text{s}}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $\text{I}, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, \text{n}_{\text{id}}, \text{n}_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, v, v_k, v_p, \text{s}$ and \bar{c} . We also assume that $\nexists \text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}. \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[\text{I}]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(\text{n}'_{\text{id}}, \text{n}'_{\#}))$ and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_1^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\text{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \text{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := \text{s2s}(\text{s})] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that

$\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$ and from Definition 5.2.C we know for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}' \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}') \vee \text{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}') \right) \right\} \Rightarrow \\ & (\exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \exists s_k. \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \wedge \forall s. \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \Rightarrow \\ & \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \in \text{WP}_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}' \right) \end{aligned}$$

Combining derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)) \Rightarrow_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)] \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}[v := s2s(s)]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

Theorem 6.2.Q. *Performing an HMACOLD or HMACNEW step with a crypto string that is a key preserves safety of the selected thread:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, v, v_k, v_p, s_p, \text{cg}, \bar{c}. \text{SAFE}_I(r) \wedge \text{cg} \in \text{cgs}(r) \wedge \\ & \text{cg} = \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \wedge \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#})) \wedge \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \\ & \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c})) \Rightarrow \text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c})) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We assume that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p) \circ \bar{c}))$ for some $I, r, \text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}, n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, v, v_k, v_p, s_p$ and \bar{c} . We similarly assume that $\text{SAFE}_I(r), \text{cg} \in \text{cgs}(r), \text{cg} = \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p), \forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$ and $\underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p)$. Those are all the assumptions we make and now we must prove $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}))$. We can already use Definition 5.3.C to derive that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}\}, v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p); \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. It is then sufficient to prove:

$$\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$$

From Definition 5.2.A we know that for all $n'_{\#}$ we have $n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p)) + n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = n'_{\#} \Rightarrow n_{\#} = \$_{\text{key}}(\text{skip}) + n'_{\#}$. Observe that from $\forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$ we know that $\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) \in \text{cgs}(r)$ according to Theorem 5.1.D. Since $\text{SAFE}_I(r)$ we can now conclude that for any n'_{id} and $n'_{\#}$ such that $\forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{[I]}(r). \underline{\text{st}}(v_k) = \text{cs}(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$ if must be so that $n'_{\text{id}} = n'_{\text{id}}$ and $n'_{\#} = n'_{\#}$. From Definition 5.2.C we can now derive for any $n'_{\#}$ and $\underline{\text{st}}'$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{st}} \in \text{WP}_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{hmac}(v_k, v_p), n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}' \right) \Rightarrow \\ & \underline{\text{st}} \in \left\{ \underline{\text{st}} \mid \exists s_p. \underline{\text{st}}(v_p) = s2s(s_p) \wedge \left(\text{H_ATT}_I^r(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}') \vee \text{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}') \right) \right\} \Rightarrow \\ & \text{H_KEY}_I^r(v, \underline{\text{st}}(v_k), s_p, \underline{\text{st}}, \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow (\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p)] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \\ & (\text{cg} \in \text{cgs}(r) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \in \underline{\text{st}}') \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \in \underline{\text{st}}' \Rightarrow \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \in \text{WP}_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r \left(\text{skip}, n'_{\#}, \underline{\text{st}}' \right) \end{aligned}$$

Combining the derived facts allows us to conclude $(n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \cdot v \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} N_s) \Rightarrow_{I-n_{\text{id}}}^r (n_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}] \cdot \text{skip})$ and Theorem 6.2.B then gives us $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{\text{st}}[v := r \blacktriangledown \text{cg}]\}, \text{skip}; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$. \square

6.3 The expected probability of failure

6.3.1 The expected probability of failure

Definition 6.3.A. The expected probability of failure for some number of execution steps and a crypto world:

$$\forall \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}. \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] \equiv \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi))$$

Theorem 6.3.A. The expected probability of failure for a safe crypto world for which only a deterministic execution step is possible respects a fixed bound:

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, \underline{w}, \underline{w}', \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}}. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}) \wedge (\forall \psi, \pi, w'. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w' \Rightarrow \pi = \mathbf{1} \wedge w' = \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi) \wedge \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}} \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{w})] \leq \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}}$$

Proof. Given a $\mathbf{I}, \underline{w}, \underline{w}', \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}}$ such that $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}), \forall \psi, \pi, w'. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w' \Rightarrow \pi = \mathbf{1} \wedge w' = \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$ and $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}}$ we know for all ψ that $\neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ with Theorem 5.5.B and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{\substack{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w'}} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, w')) \right) &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) = \\ \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] &\leq \mathbf{q}_{\text{bound}} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 6.3.B. The expected probability of failure for a safe world configuration for which no execution step is possible is equal to zero:

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, \underline{w}, \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}) \wedge (\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} = \mathbf{0} \vee \forall \psi. \neg \exists \pi, w'. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w') \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] = \mathbf{0}$$

Proof. Given a $\mathbf{I}, \underline{w}$ and \mathbf{n}_{step} such that $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w})$ and $(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} = \mathbf{0} \vee \forall \psi. \neg \exists \pi, w'. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w')$ we can already establish for all ψ that $\neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ with Theorem 5.5.B. Now we proceed with a case analysis of \mathbf{n}_{step} using Definition 2.4.B:

- $\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} = \mathbf{0}$ Here we know for all ψ that $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi) = \mathbf{0}$ and so:

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] = \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$$

- $\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} = \mathbf{n}' + \mathbf{1}$ Here, for all ψ we have $\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi) = \sum_{\substack{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w'}} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}', w'))$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{\substack{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{\pi} w'}} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}', w')) \right) &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0} \end{aligned}$$

□

6.3.2 Safety and the expected probability of failure

Lemma 6.3.A. Auxiliary lemma for Theorem 6.3.C:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \mathbf{I}, \underline{w}, \underline{st}, \underline{t}, r, n_{\text{step}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, c, \bar{c}. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I}) \wedge \\
& \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}) \wedge n_{\text{step}} + 1 \leq N_{\psi} \wedge \underline{w} = \langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) :: \underline{t} \rangle \wedge \\
& \left(\forall \underline{w}'. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}') \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} \right) \Rightarrow \\
& \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] \leq \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. For some $\mathbf{I}, \underline{w}, \underline{st}, \underline{t}, r, n_{\text{step}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \bar{\alpha}, \beta, \gamma, c$ and \bar{c} we assume that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I}), \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}), n_{\text{step}} + 1 \leq N_{\psi}$, $\underline{w} = \langle \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c}) :: \underline{t} \rangle$ and:

$$\forall \underline{w}'. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}') \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$$

We now need to prove $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] \leq \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$. We can already deduce the following facts from the assumptions using the abbreviation $\underline{t} = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ \bar{c})$:

- $\neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ (By Theorem 5.5.B)
- $\text{keys}(\gamma) \cap \text{strs}(r) = \emptyset$ (By Definition 5.5.E)
- $\text{cgs}(r) \prec |\underline{t} :: \underline{t}|$ or equivalently $\text{cgs}(r) \prec \mathbf{1} + |\underline{t}|$ (By Definition 5.5.E)
- $\forall \underline{t}' \in \underline{t} :: \underline{t}. \text{seq}(\underline{t}') \prec_{\text{id}(\underline{t}')} \text{cgs}(r)$ and thus $n_{\#} \prec_{n_{\text{id}}} \text{cgs}(r)$ (By Definition 5.5.E)
- For some $\bar{c}_{\square}, \bar{s}$ and \bar{c}_{\blacksquare} we have $r = [\bar{c}_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}_{\blacksquare}]$ (By Definition 5.1.A)
- $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(r)$ (By Definition 5.5.E)
- $\forall r'. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(r + r') \Rightarrow \forall \underline{t}' \in \underline{t} :: \underline{t}. \exists b_{\text{fork}}. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}^{r+r'}(b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t}')$ (By Theorem 5.4.A)
- $\forall r'. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(r + r') \Rightarrow$
 $\exists b_{\text{fork}}. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}^{r+r'}(b_{\text{fork}}, n_{\text{id}}, n_{\#}, \{\underline{st}\}, c; \overline{\text{CMD}}(\bar{c}))$ (By Definition 5.3.C and 5.4.A)

Throughout this proof we implicitly use, amongst others, Definition 5.3.A, 5.3.B, 5.5.A and 5.5.C. Now we perform a case analysis of c :

- $\boxed{c = \text{skip}}$ Here we perform a case analysis of \bar{c}

– $\boxed{\bar{c} = []}$

Inspecting Definition 2.3.G we can easily see for all ψ that $\text{VALUE}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ and using Theorem 2.3.B that $\neg \exists \pi, w. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w$ and so Theorem 6.3.B finishes the proof.

– $\boxed{\bar{c} = c' :: \bar{c}'}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XSKIP. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{\mathbf{1}}{\rightsquigarrow} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c' \circ \bar{c}') :: \underline{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.G that $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}'|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

- $c = \text{stuck}$

Inspecting Definition 2.3.G we can easily see for all ψ that $\text{VALUE}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ and using Theorem 2.3.B that $\neg \exists \pi, w. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w$ and so Theorem 6.3.B finishes the proof.

- $c = \text{fail}$

Since $\exists b_{\text{fork}}. \text{SAFE}_1^{r+r'}(b_{\text{fork}}, \underline{t})$ we can use Theorem 5.3.A to get $\neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{t} \downarrow \psi)$. However, according to Definition 2.4.A we also know that $\text{FAILED}(\underline{t} \downarrow \psi)$. So we have a contradiction and this case is impossible.

- $c = \text{snd}(e)$

From Theorem 6.2.C we know that there exists a s such that $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s2s(s)$. So e evaluates to s in the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$. From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XSEND. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot s :: \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.C that $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}'|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

- $c = \text{rcv}(v)$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XRECEIVE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. Now we perform a case analysis of β :

- $\beta = []$

It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot [] \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} [v := s2s(\varepsilon)] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

- $\beta' = s :: \beta'$

It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{1}{\rightsquigarrow} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta' \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} [v := s2s(s)] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

Since $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.D that $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}'|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

- $c = v := e$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XASSIGN. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step

$\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{1} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta' \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r} \triangleright (\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.E that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} \leq \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|)}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} = \frac{(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}}$$

- $\boxed{c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible steps for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ are determined by the rule XSAMPLE. Observe that we can already derive from the assumptions that $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\mathbf{b}_{\text{fork}}, (\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} N_s \circ \bar{c}))$ for some \mathbf{b}_{fork} and thus $\mathbf{n}_{\#} > \mathbf{0}$ using Theorem 6.2.M. Now note that from $\mathbf{n}_{\#} \preceq_{\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}} \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r})$ we then know $\mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \notin \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r})$ and now we perform a case analysis on whether $\mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket$:

- $\boxed{\mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \in \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket}$

The rule XSAMPLE determines precisely one transition for each string s_k of size \mathbf{N}_s . For the sampled string s_k the resulting world configuration is determined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}'(s_k) &= [\bar{c}\bar{g}_{\square} ++ [\mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1})] \cdot \bar{s} ++ [s_k] \cdot \bar{c}\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}] \\ \underline{w}'(s_k) &= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r}'(s_k) \triangleright (\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} \cdot \underline{\text{st}} [v := s_{2s}(s_k)] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

From $\text{SAFE}_I(\mathbf{r})$ and 5.1.D one can see that we definitely get $\text{SAFE}_I(\mathbf{r}'(s_k))$ for any $s_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r})$ and for such a s_k we also have $\mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cap \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r}'(s_k)) = \emptyset$ and $|\underline{w}'(s_k)| = |\underline{w}| + 1$. It is clear that for such an s_k we also have $\mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}'(s_k)) \prec \mathbf{1} + \bar{t}$, $\mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1} \preceq_{\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}} \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}'(s_k))$ and $\forall \bar{t}' \in \bar{t}. \mathbf{seq}(\bar{t}') \preceq_{\text{id}(\bar{t}')} \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}'(s_k))$. Since for any s_k and \mathbf{r}'' such that $|s_k| = \mathbf{N}_s$, $s_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\text{SAFE}_I(\mathbf{r}'(s_k) + \mathbf{r}'')$, there must exist a \mathbf{r}''' such that $\mathbf{r}'(s_k) + \mathbf{r}'' = \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}'''$, we may derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.N that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}'(s_k))$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}, \underline{w}')) \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{s_k \in \{s_k \mid |s_k| = \mathbf{N}_s\}} (2^{\mathbf{N}_s} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_k) \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\ &= \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = \mathbf{N}_s\}} \left(2^{\mathbf{N}_s} \times \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_k) \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\ &= \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = \mathbf{N}_s\}} (2^{\mathbf{N}_s} \times \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_k))]) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r})|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} + \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = \mathbf{N}_s \wedge s \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r})\}} (2^{\mathbf{N}_s} \times \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_k))]) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} + \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = \mathbf{N}_s \wedge s \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r})\}} \left(2^{\mathbf{N}_s} \times \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} \right) \leq \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} + \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} = \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}|)}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} \leq \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 2 \times \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} = \frac{(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{\mathbf{N}_s}} \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{\mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{id}}, \mathbf{n}_{\#} - \mathbf{1}) \notin \llbracket \mathbf{I} \rrbracket}$

The rule XSAMPLE determines precisely one transition for each string s_k with \mathbf{N}_s as size. If we denote with \mathbf{n}_k the length of $\bar{c}\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}$ (i.e. $\mathbf{n}_k = |\bar{c}\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|$) and if for a given ψ we denote with $\psi(s_k)$ the list

$\psi[:n_k] ++ s_k :: (\psi[n_k + 1 :])$, then we know that $\psi(s_k)[n_k] = s_k$ and $\forall n. n \neq n_k \Rightarrow \psi[:n] = \psi(s_k)[:n]$. Now (if for a given sampled string s_k and coin tosses ψ we compute the concrete world configuration as $\underline{w}' \downarrow \psi(s_k)$) we can represent all resulting world configurations as:

$$\begin{aligned} r' &= [\bar{c}g_{\square} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot \bar{c}g_{\blacksquare} ++ [\mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#} - 1)]] \\ \underline{w}' &= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r' \triangleright (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} - 1 \cdot \underline{st}[v := \lambda \psi. \psi[n_k]] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

From $\mathbf{key}(n_{id}, n_{\#} - 1) \notin \mathbf{cgs}(r)$ we immediately get $\mathbf{SAFE}_1(r')$ and obviously $\mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cap \mathbf{strs}(r') = \emptyset$ and $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}| + 1$. It is also clear that $\mathbf{cgs}(r') \prec \mathbf{1} + \bar{t}$, $n_{\#} - 1 \preceq_{n_{id}} \mathbf{cgs}(r')$ and $\forall \bar{t}' \in \bar{t}. \mathbf{seq}(\bar{t}') \preceq_{id(\bar{t}')} \mathbf{cgs}(r')$. Since for any r'' such that $\mathbf{SAFE}_1(r' + r'')$ there clearly exists a r''' such that $r' + r'' = r + r'''$ we may derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.N that $\mathbf{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} E[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi \times \mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n, w')) \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = N_s\}} (2^{-N_s} \times \mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \downarrow \psi)[\psi(s_k)]\underline{w}') \right) = \\ &= \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = N_s\}} \left(2^{-N_s} \times \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \downarrow \psi)[\psi(s_k)]\underline{w}') \right) = \\ &= \sum_{s_k \in \{s \mid |s| = N_s\}} \left(2^{-N_s} \times \frac{1}{|\Psi_{n_k=s}|} \times \sum_{|\Psi_{n_k=s}|} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) = E[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{c = v \stackrel{s}{\leftarrow} \mathbf{hmac}(v_k, v_p)}$

From Theorem 6.2.O we know $\exists s_k. \underline{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k) \vee \exists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\mathbb{I}]}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = \mathbf{cs}(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}))$ and that there must exist some s_p such that $\underline{st}(v_p) = s2s(s_p)$. We now perform a case analysis:

- $\boxed{\nexists n'_{id}, n'_{\#}. \forall cs \in \odot_{[\mathbb{I}]}(r). \underline{st}(v_k) = \mathbf{cs}(\mathbf{key}(n'_{id}, n'_{\#}))}$

There exist some s_k such that $\underline{st}(v_k) = s2s(s_k)$ and $s_k \notin \bar{s}$. We now perform another case analysis:

- * $\boxed{(s_k, s_p) \in \mathbf{dom}(\gamma)}$

So there exists some s_h such that $\gamma(s_k, s_p) = s_h$. One can see from Definition 5.5.B that for all ψ we have that $(\gamma \boxplus_{\Gamma}^{\psi} \bar{c}g)(s_k, s_p) = s_h$. From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XHMACOLD. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{1} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st}[v := s2s(s_h)] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\mathbf{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.P that $\mathbf{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $E[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}'|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

- * $\boxed{(s_k, s_p) \notin \mathbf{dom}(\gamma)}$

One can see from Definition 4.1.F, 5.1.C, 5.5.B that we have $(\gamma \boxplus_{\Gamma}^{\psi} \bar{c}g)(s_k, s_p) = \perp$ for all $\psi \in$

$\Psi_{s_k \notin \text{cgs}} \cdot$ Considering only these ψ , the rule XHMACNEW determines precisely one transition for each string s_h of size N_s and we can represent all resulting worlds as:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma'(s_h) &= \gamma[(s_k, s_p) := s_h] \\ \underline{w}'(s_h) &= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma'(s_h) \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st}[v := s_h] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

We now can derive for any s_h that $\text{keys}(\gamma'(s_h)) \cap \text{strs}(r) = \emptyset$ and $|\underline{w}'(s_h)| = |\underline{w}| + 1$.

We derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.P that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}'(s_h))$ and so using Theorem 4.1.D:

$$\begin{aligned} E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ &= \frac{|\Psi_{s_k \in \text{cgs}}|}{|\Psi|} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin \text{cgs}}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\text{cgs}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin \text{cgs}}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w')) \right) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin \text{cgs}}} \left(\sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (2^{-N_s} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h) \downarrow \psi)) \right) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (2^{-N_s} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h) \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h) \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h))]) = \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'(s_h)|}{2^{N_s}} \right) = \\ &= \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} \right) = \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \\ &= \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}| + n_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}| + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}| + 1}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

$$- \forall cs \in \text{C}[\mathbb{I}](r). \text{st}(v_k) = cs(\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}))$$

From Theorem 5.1.D we know that $\text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) \in r$ and we perform another case analysis:

$$* \text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) \in \mathbb{I}$$

So we know there exists some s_k such that $r \blacktriangledown \text{key}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}) = s_k$ and $s_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma)$. Since $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbb{I})$ we can derive with Theorem 4.2.H that $\text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \mathbb{I}$. We now perform yet another case analysis:

$$\cdot \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(r)$$

So we know there exists some s_h such that $r \blacktriangledown \text{hmac}(n'_{\text{id}}, n'_{\#}, s_p) = s_h$. One can see from Definition 4.1.F, 5.1.C, 5.5.B that we have $(\gamma \boxplus_r^{\psi} \text{cgs})(s_k, s_p) = s_h$ for all $\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin \text{cgs}}$. Considering only these ψ , the rule XHMACOLD determines precisely one transition and we can represent all resulting worlds as:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{st}[v := s_h] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$$

Obviously $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$ and since $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.Q that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}')$. Since then we know $E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\
&\frac{|\Psi_{s_k \in |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}|}{|\Psi|} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \\
&\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, w')) \right) \leq \\
\frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) &\leq \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} \left(\frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \right) = \\
\frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|)}{2^{N_s}} &\leq \frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 2 \times \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\text{hmac}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}, s_p) \notin \text{cgs}(\mathfrak{r})}$$

One can see from Definition 4.1.F, 5.1.C, 5.5.B that we have $(\gamma \boxplus_{\text{r}}^{\psi} \text{c}_{\text{g}})(s_k, s_p) = \perp$ for all $\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}$. Considering only these ψ , the rule XHMACNEW determines precisely one transition for each string s_h of size N_s and we can represent all resulting worlds as:

$$\begin{aligned}
r'(s_h) &= [\text{c}_{\text{g}} \square \uparrow \uparrow [\text{hmac}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}, s_p)] \cdot \bar{s} \uparrow \uparrow [s_h] \cdot \text{c}_{\text{g}} \square] \\
\underline{w}'(s_h) &= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r'(s_h) \triangleright (\mathfrak{n}_{\text{id}} \cdot \mathfrak{n}_{\#} \cdot \text{st}[v := s_h] \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

One can see that we only get $\text{SAFE}_I(r'(s_h))$, $\text{keys}(\gamma) \cap \text{strs}(r'(s_h)) = \emptyset$ and $|\underline{w}'(s_h)| = |\underline{w}| + 1$ if $s_h \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(\mathfrak{r})$. It is also clear that $\text{cgs}(r'(s_h)) \prec 1 + |\bar{t}|$ and $\mathfrak{n}_{\#} \prec_{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{id}}} \text{cgs}(r'(s_h))$ for such a s_h and obviously also $\forall \underline{t}' \in \bar{t}. \text{seq}(\underline{t}') \prec_{\text{id}(\underline{t}')} \text{cgs}(r'(s_h))$. Since for any r'' such that $\text{SAFE}_I(r'(s_h) + r'')$ there clearly exists a r''' such that $r'(s_h) + r'' = \mathfrak{r} + r'''$ we derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.Q that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}'(s_h))$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) = \\
&\frac{|\Psi_{s_k \in |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}|}{|\Psi|} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \\
&\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow w'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, w')) \right) \leq \\
\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{s_k \notin |\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}} \left(\sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (2^{-N_s} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h) \downarrow \psi)) \right) &\leq \\
\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h) \downarrow \psi)) \right) &\leq \\
\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h))]) &\leq \\
\frac{|\text{c}_{\text{g}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{|\text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(\mathfrak{r})|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s \wedge \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(\mathfrak{r})\}} (\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}'(s_h))]) &\leq \\
\frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s \wedge \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(\mathfrak{r})\}} \left(\frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w} + 1|)}{2^{N_s}} \right) &\leq \\
\frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w} + 1|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}| + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}})}{2^{N_s}} &\leq \frac{\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 2 \times \mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \\
&\frac{(\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (\mathfrak{n}_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$* \boxed{\text{key}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}) \notin [I]}$$

Since $\text{key}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}) \in \mathfrak{r}$ we now know from Theorem 5.1.E there must exist a \mathfrak{n}_k such that $\mathfrak{r} \blacktriangleright \text{key}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}) = \lambda \psi. \psi[\mathfrak{n}_k]$. We now perform yet another case analysis:

$$\cdot \boxed{\text{hmac}(\mathfrak{n}'_{\text{id}}, \mathfrak{n}'_{\#}, s_p) \in \text{cgs}(\mathfrak{r})}$$

From Theorem 5.1.E we can likewise conclude there must exist a \mathbf{n}_h for which it holds that $\mathbf{r} \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}, \mathbf{s}_p) = \lambda \psi. \psi[\mathbf{n}_h]$. One can see from Definition 4.1.G, 4.1.E, 5.1.C, 5.5.B that we then have for all ψ such that $\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|}$ and $\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}$:

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma \boxplus_r^\psi c\bar{g})(\mathbf{r} \blacktriangledown \mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}))(\psi, \mathbf{s}_p) &= (\gamma \boxplus_r^\psi c\bar{g})(\psi[\mathbf{n}_k], \mathbf{s}_p) = \\ \psi[\mathbf{n}_h] &= \mathbf{r} \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}, \mathbf{s}_p) \end{aligned}$$

Considering only these ψ , the rule XHMACOLD determines precisely one transition and we can represent all resulting worlds as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{w}}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r} \blacktriangleright (\mathbf{n}_{id} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{st}}[v := \lambda \psi. \psi[\mathbf{n}_h]] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{\mathbf{t}} \rangle$$

Clearly $|\underline{\mathbf{w}}'| = |\underline{\mathbf{w}}|$ and we derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.Q that $\mathbf{SAFE}_T(\underline{\mathbf{w}}')$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{\mathbf{w}})] &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi)) = \\ &= \frac{|\Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \in |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|} + |\Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}|}{|\Psi|} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \\ &= \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|} \cup \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \frac{|c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}| + |\mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \\ &= \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|} \cup \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}} \left(\sum_{\underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{w}'} (\pi \times \mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \mathbf{w}')) \right) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|} \cup \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}, \underline{\mathbf{w}})] \leq \\ &= \frac{|\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{\mathbf{w}}| + |\underline{\mathbf{w}}|)}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}}^2 + \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{\mathbf{w}}| + 2 \times \mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + |\underline{\mathbf{w}}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \\ &= \frac{(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{\mathbf{w}}|}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{hmac}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}, \mathbf{s}_p) \notin \mathbf{cgs}(r)}$$

If we denote with \mathbf{n}_h the length of $c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}$ (i.e. $\mathbf{n}_h = |c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare}|$) one can see from Definition 4.1.G, 4.1.E, 5.1.C, 5.5.B that we have:

$$(\gamma \boxplus_r^\psi c\bar{g})(\mathbf{r} \blacktriangledown \mathbf{key}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}))(\psi, \mathbf{s}_p) = \perp$$

for all ψ such that $\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{n}_h}$ and $\psi \in \Psi_{\mathbf{n}_k \notin \mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cup \mathbf{strs}(r)}$. Considering only these ψ , the rule XHMACNEW determines precisely one transition for each string \mathbf{s}_h of size N_s . If for a given ψ we denote with $\psi(\mathbf{s}_h)$ the list $\psi[: \mathbf{n}_h] ++ \mathbf{s}_h :: (\psi[\mathbf{n}_h + 1 :])$, then we know that $\psi(\mathbf{s}_h)[\mathbf{n}_h] = \mathbf{s}_h$ and $\forall \mathbf{n}. \mathbf{n} \neq \mathbf{n}_h \Rightarrow \psi[: \mathbf{n}] = \psi(\mathbf{s}_h)[: \mathbf{n}]$. Now (if for a given sampled string \mathbf{s}_h and coin tosses ψ we compute the concrete world configuration as $\underline{\mathbf{w}}' \downarrow \psi(\mathbf{s}_h)$) we can represent all resulting world configurations as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}' &= [c\bar{g}_{\square} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{s}} \cdot c\bar{g}_{\blacksquare} ++ [\mathbf{hmac}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}, \mathbf{s}_p)]] \\ \underline{\mathbf{w}}' &= \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r}' \blacktriangleright (\mathbf{n}_{id} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\#} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{st}}[v := \mathbf{r}' \blacktriangledown \mathbf{hmac}(\mathbf{n}'_{id}, \mathbf{n}'_{\#}, \mathbf{s}_p)] \triangleright \mathbf{skip} \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{\mathbf{t}} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

One can see that we obviously have $\mathbf{SAFE}_T(\mathbf{r}')$, $\mathbf{keys}(\gamma) \cap \mathbf{strs}(\mathbf{r}') = \emptyset$ and $|\underline{\mathbf{w}}'| = |\underline{\mathbf{w}}| + 1$. It is clear that $\mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}') \prec \mathbf{1} + \bar{\mathbf{t}}$ and $\mathbf{n}_{\#} \preccurlyeq_{\mathbf{n}_{id}} \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}')$ for such a \mathbf{s}_h . We obviously also have $\forall \bar{\mathbf{t}}' \in \bar{\mathbf{t}}. \mathbf{seq}(\bar{\mathbf{t}}') \preccurlyeq_{id(\bar{\mathbf{t}}')} \mathbf{cgs}(\mathbf{r}')$. Since for any \mathbf{r}'' such that $\mathbf{SAFE}_T(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}'')$ there clearly exists a \mathbf{r}''' such that $\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}'' = \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}'''$ we derive from Definition 5.5.E and Theorem 6.2.Q that $\mathbf{SAFE}_T(\underline{\mathbf{w}}')$ and so:

$$\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{\mathbf{w}})] = \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\mathbf{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(\mathbf{n}_{\text{step}} + \mathbf{1}, \underline{\mathbf{w}} \downarrow \psi)) =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{|\Psi_{n_k \in n_h}| + |\Psi_{n_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)}|}{|\Psi|} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n_k \notin n_h} \cup \Psi_{n_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) \leq \\
& \frac{|\underline{c} \boxplus \blacksquare| + |\text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n_k \notin n_h} \cup \Psi_{n_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')) \right) \leq \\
& \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n_k \notin n_h} \cup \Psi_{n_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)}} \left(\sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} (2^{-N_s} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi(s_h))) \right) = \\
& \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n_k \notin n_h} \cup \Psi_{n_k \notin \text{keys}(\gamma) \cup \text{strs}(r)}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi(s_h))) \right) \leq \\
& \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi(s_h))) \right) = \\
& \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + 2^{-N_s} \times \sum_{s_h \in \{s \mid |s|=N_s\}} \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi_{n=s_h}|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n=s_h}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) \right) = \\
& \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) = \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{|\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} + \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \\
& \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}| + n_{\text{step}})}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + |\underline{w}| + 1)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}
\end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{c = q ? c : c}$ Here we perform a case analysis of q :

– $\boxed{q = (|e| = n)}$ Now we perform a case analysis on the length of $\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}}$:

* $\boxed{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = n}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XIFTRUE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow^1 \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_2) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_1)) \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{\Gamma} \rangle$$

For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

* $\boxed{\llbracket e \rrbracket_{\text{st}} \neq n}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XIFFALSE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow^1 \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{\text{key}}(c_1) - \$_{\text{key}}(c_2)) \cdot \underline{\text{st}} \triangleright c_2 \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{\Gamma} \rangle$$

For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

Since $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.J that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times (|\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|)}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

– $\boxed{q = (e_1 = e_2)}$

Using Theorem 6.2.K we have a s_1 such that $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{\text{st}} = s_2 s(s_1)$ and again we perform a case analysis:

$$* \quad \boxed{\exists s. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s)}$$

So we also have a s_2 such that $\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s_2)$. Now we perform a case analysis on s_1 and s_2 :

$$\cdot \quad \boxed{s_1 = s_2}$$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XIFTRUE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{1} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{key}(c_2) - \$_{key}(c_1)) \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$$

For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

$$\cdot \quad \boxed{s_1 \neq s_2}$$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XIFFALSE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{1} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{key}(c_1) - \$_{key}(c_2)) \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_2 \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$$

For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$.

Since $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.L that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}} + 1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}} + 1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

$$* \quad \boxed{\neg \exists s. \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = s2s(s)}$$

Observe we can derive $\text{SAFE}_I^r(\text{b}_{\text{fork}}, (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright e_1 = e_2 ? c_1 : c_2 \circ \bar{c}))$ from the assumptions for some b_{fork} and thus for some cg that $\forall \text{cs} \in \odot_{\llbracket I \rrbracket}(r). \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = \text{cs}(\text{cg})$ using Theorem 6.2.K. From Theorem 5.1.D one can even see that for this cg we have $\text{cg} \in \text{cgs}(r)$ and $\text{cg} \notin \llbracket I \rrbracket$. So using Definition 5.1.E we conclude that there must exist a $n \leq N_{\psi}$ such that $\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st} = \lambda \psi. \psi[n]$ and so clearly $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st}$.

With Definition 4.1.D we now can partition the set Ψ into two disjoint sets $\Psi_{n \neq s_1}$ and $\Psi_{n = s_1}$ and it is straightforward to see from Theorem 4.1.B that $|\Psi_{n = s_1}| = 2^{N_s \times (N_{\psi} - 1)}$, $|\Psi_{n \neq s_1}| = (2^{N_s} - 1) \times 2^{N_s \times (N_{\psi} - 1)}$ and $|\Psi| = 2^{N_s \times N_{\psi}}$. From Definition 2.3.F we know for all $\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}$ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XIFFALSE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all $\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}$ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \xrightarrow{1} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose:

$$\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{id} \cdot n_{\#} - (\$_{key}(c_1) - \$_{key}(c_2)) \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_2 \circ \bar{c}) :: \bar{t} \rangle$$

Since $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w})$ and $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket_{st} \neq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket_{st}$ it now follows from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.K that $\text{SAFE}_I(\underline{w}')$. Now we derive $E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ and so finally:

$$E[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w})] = \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) =$$

$$\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \left(\sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n = s_1}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) + \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}} + 1, \underline{w} \downarrow \psi)) \right) \leq$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \left(\sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n=s_1}} (\mathbf{1}) + \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}'} (\pi \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')) \right) \right) = \\
& \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n=s_1}} (\mathbf{1}) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}} \left(\sum_{\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi} (\mathbf{1} \times \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) \right) \right) = \\
& \frac{|\Psi_{n=s_1}|}{|\Psi|} + \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi_{n \neq s_1}} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) \right) \leq \\
& 2^{-N_s} + \left(\frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi)) \right) = 2^{-N_s} + \text{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \\
& 2^{-N_s} + \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}
\end{aligned}$$

- $\boxed{c = \text{fork}(c)}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XFORK. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright \underline{t}_1 :: \underline{t}_2 :: \bar{\iota} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. We chose here $\underline{t}_1 = (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c \circ [])$, $\underline{t}_2 = (n_{\text{id}} + \mathbf{1} \cdot n'_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright \text{skip} \circ \bar{c})$ and some $n'_{\#}$ that must exist according to Theorem 6.2.I. Note that from $\text{cgs}(r) \prec [\underline{t} :: \bar{\iota}]$ it clearly follows that $\text{cgs}(r) \prec [\underline{t}_1 :: \underline{t}_2 :: \bar{\iota}]$. Also note that obviously $\text{seq}(\underline{t}_1) \prec_{\text{id}(\underline{t}_1)} \text{cgs}(r)$ and $\text{seq}(\underline{t}_2) \prec_{\text{id}(\underline{t}_2)} \text{cgs}(r)$. Since $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from Theorem 6.2.I that also $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\text{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and invoking Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously $\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$.

- $\boxed{c = \text{sched}(\bar{\alpha}')}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XSCHEDULE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} :: \bar{\alpha}' \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ c_2 :: \bar{c}) :: \bar{\iota} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.F that $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\text{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

- $\boxed{c = c_1 ; c_2}$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XSEQ. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \rightsquigarrow \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot r \triangleright (n_{\text{id}} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \underline{st} \triangleright c_1 \circ c_2 :: \bar{c}) :: \bar{\iota} \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from derived facts and Theorem 5.4.B and 6.2.H that $\text{SAFE}_1(\underline{w}')$. Now we can derive $\text{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ from the assumptions and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since obviously:

$$\frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + 2 \times n_{\text{step}} + 1 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n_{\text{step}}+1)^2 + (n_{\text{step}}+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

□

Theorem 6.3.C. *The expected probability of failure for a safe crypto world has the following upper bound:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w}. \text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I}) \wedge \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}) \wedge n_{\text{step}} \leq N_{\psi} \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$$

Proof. The proof goes by induction on n_{step} . So for some \mathbf{I} and \underline{w} such that $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w})$ and $n_{\text{step}} \leq N_{\psi}$, we need to prove that $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, \underline{w})] \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$. Before we go over the different inductive cases, we can already use Theorem 5.5.B to establish for all ψ that $\neg \text{FAILED}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$.

- $n_{\text{step}} = 0$

Theorem 6.3.B finishes the proof.

- $n_{\text{step}} = n' + 1$

From Definition 5.5.A we know there exists some $\bar{\alpha}$, β , γ , \mathbf{r} and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ such that $\underline{w} = \langle \bar{\alpha} \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r} \triangleright \bar{\mathbf{t}} \rangle$. We proceed with a simultaneous case analysis of $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$:

$$- \bar{\alpha} = \varepsilon \vee \bar{\mathbf{t}} = \varepsilon$$

Inspecting Definition 2.3.G we can easily see for all ψ that $\text{VALUE}(\underline{w} \downarrow \psi)$ and using Theorem 2.3.B that $\neg \exists \pi, w. \underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{\pi}{\rightsquigarrow} w$ and so Theorem 6.3.B finishes the proof.

$$- \bar{\alpha} = \text{step} :: \bar{\alpha}' \wedge \bar{\mathbf{t}} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} :: \bar{\mathbf{t}}'$$

Invoking Lemma 6.3.B finishes the proof.

$$- \bar{\alpha} = \text{rotate} :: \bar{\alpha}' \wedge \bar{\mathbf{t}} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} :: \bar{\mathbf{t}}'$$

From Definition 2.3.F we know for all ψ that the only possible step for \rightsquigarrow starting from the world configuration $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi$ is determined by the rule XROTATE. This rule is deterministic for a given world and has $\mathbf{1}$ as associated probability. It is clear from this rule that for all ψ we have as only execution step $\underline{w} \downarrow \psi \overset{\mathbf{1}}{\rightsquigarrow} \underline{w}' \downarrow \psi$, where we chose $\underline{w}' = \langle \bar{\alpha}' \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathbf{r} \triangleright \bar{\mathbf{t}}' ++ [\mathbf{t}] \rangle$. For this chosen \underline{w}' it clearly holds that $|\underline{w}'| = |\underline{w}|$. Since $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w})$ it now follows immediately from Definition 5.5.E that $\text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}')$. By induction we can now derive $\mathbb{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n', \underline{w}')] \leq \frac{n'^2 + n' \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}}$ and Theorem 6.3.A finishes the proof since $\frac{n'^2 + n' \times |\underline{w}'|}{2^{N_s}} \leq \frac{n'^2 + 2 \times n' + 1 + n' \times |\underline{w}| + |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{(n'+1)^2 + (n'+1) \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}} = \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |\underline{w}|}{2^{N_s}}$.

□

6.3.3 Validity and an upper bound on the probability of failure

Lemma 6.3.B. *The initial crypto world is safe for an attacker command and verified protocol:*

$$\forall \mathbf{I}, c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \wedge \text{VERIFIED}_{\mathbf{I}}(c) \Rightarrow \exists \mathbf{I}. \text{SAFE}_{\mathbf{I}}(\underline{w}_{\varepsilon}(c_{\text{attacker}}, c))$$

Proof. For some \mathbf{I} , c_{attacker} and c such that $\text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}})$ and $\text{VERIFIED}_{\mathbf{I}}(c)$ we can already use Definition 3.2.F to derive $\text{ATT}_{\text{INV}}(\mathbf{I})$ and $\mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{1} \cdot n_{\#} \cdot \text{true} \vdash c$ for some $n_{\#}$. It is now sufficient to prove according to Definition 5.5.E and 5.5.D that:

- $\text{keys}(\bar{\emptyset}) \cap \text{strs}([\] \cdot [\] \cdot [\]) = \emptyset \cap \emptyset = \emptyset$ (Trivial)
- $[\] \prec \mathbf{1}$ (Trivial)
- $\mathbf{1} \prec_{\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}} [\]$ (Trivial)

• $\text{SAFE}_I(\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket \cdot \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket \cdot \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket)$ (Trivial)

• $\forall r. \text{SAFE}_I^f(\text{true}, \llbracket (\text{ATT}_{\text{ID}} \cdot \mathbb{S}_{\text{key}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \cdot \text{ST}_\varepsilon \triangleright \text{fork}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \circ c) \rrbracket)$

To show this we assume some r and according to Definition 5.3.C and Theorem 5.2.F it is then sufficient to show $\text{SAFE}_I^f(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, \mathbb{S}_{\text{key}}(c_{\text{attacker}}), \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}, \text{fork}(c_{\text{attacker}}); c; \text{skip})$. But then, it is also sufficient to show $\text{SAFE}_I^f(\text{true}, \text{ATT}_{\text{ID}}, \mathbb{S}_{\text{key}}(c_{\text{attacker}}), \text{ATT}_{\text{ST}}, \text{fork}(c_{\text{attacker}}); c)$ according to Definition 5.2.C and Definition 5.3.C. With Theorem 6.1.C and 5.2.F it becomes sufficient to show $\text{SAFE}_I^f(\text{true}, \mathbf{1}, n_\#, \text{ST}, c)$. Since we already have $I \cdot \mathbf{1} \cdot n_\# \cdot \text{true} \vdash c$, Theorem 5.2.G immediately finishes the proof. \square

Theorem 6.3.D. *The expected probability of failure for the initial world of a verified protocol:*

$$\forall I, n_{\text{step}}, c_{\text{attacker}}, c. \text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}}) \wedge \text{VERIFIED}_I(c) \Rightarrow \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)) \leq \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2}{2^{N_s}}$$

Proof. For some $I, n_{\text{step}}, c_{\text{attacker}}$ and c such that $\text{ATT}_{\text{CMD}}(c_{\text{attacker}})$ and $\text{VERIFIED}_I(c)$, we choose N_ψ such that $N_\psi > n_{\text{step}}$. Using Lemma 6.3.B we know that $\text{SAFE}_I(w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c))$. Theorem 5.5.A and 6.3.C then give the following upper bound on the probability of failure:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)) &= \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c))) = \\ \frac{1}{|\Psi|} \times \sum_{\psi \in \Psi} (\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c) \downarrow \psi)) &= \text{E}[\text{PR}_{\text{FAILED}}(n_{\text{step}}, w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c))] \leq \\ \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2 + n_{\text{step}} \times |w_\varepsilon(c_{\text{attacker}}, c)|}{2^{N_s}} &= \frac{n_{\text{step}}^2}{2^{N_s}} \end{aligned}$$

\square